

FORWARD WP3: Co-creation and implementation of thematic groups

T3.2 Thematic action plans: Report on the Action Plans co-create by the Thematic Working Groups

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List of abbreviation and acronym

ERA	European Research Area
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESF	European Social Fund
EU	European Union
EU-FP	European Union Framework Programme
FP	Framework programme
FWD	FORWARD
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
HE	Horizon Europe
KOM, KoM	Kick-Off Meeting
RD	Research and Development
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OP	Operational Programme
ORs	Outermost Regions
R+D+i	Research, Development, and Innovation
R&I, R-I, R+i	Research and Innovation
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises

List of the members of FORWARD consortium

Table 1 List of the 24 members of the FORWARD H2020 project

Name	Short name	Country
GOBIERNO DE CANARIAS	GOBCAN	Spain
FUNDO REGIONAL PARA A CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA	FRCT	Portugal
ARDITI - AGÊNCIA REGIONAL PARA O DESENVOLVIMENTO DA INVESTIGAÇÃO, TECNOLOGIA E INOVAÇÃO - ASSOCIAÇÃO	ARDITI	Portugal
NEXA - AGENCE RÉGIONALE DE DÉVELOPPEMENT D'INVESTISSEMENT ET D'INNOVATION	NEXA	France
COLLECTIVITÉ TERRITORIALE DE MARTINIQUE	CTM	France
COLLECTIVITÉ TERRITORIALE DE GUYANE	CTG	France
GUADELOUPE REGION	REG GUA	France
COLLECTIVITÉ DE SAINT MARTIN	COMSM	France
DÉPARTEMENT DE MAYOTTE	CDM	France
UNIVERSIDAD DE LA LAGUNA	ULL	Spain
UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA	ULPGC	Spain
CONSORCIO PARA EL DISEÑO, CONSTRUCCIÓN, EQUIPAMIENTO Y EXPLOTACIÓN DE LA PLATAFORMA OCEÁNICA DE CANARIAS	PLOCAN	Spain
INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO DE CANARIAS SA	ITC	Spain
INSTITUTO DE ASTROFÍSICA DE CANARIAS	IAC	Spain
UNIVERSIDADE DOS AÇORES	UAç	Portugal
CAMARA DO COMERCIO E INDUSTRIA DOS AÇORES	CCIA	Portugal
UNIVERSIDADE DA MADEIRA	UMa	Portugal
UNIVERSITÉ DE LA RÉUNION	UR	France
UNIVERSITÉ DES ANTILLES	UA	France
UNIVERSITÉ DE GUYANE	UG	France
GUYANE DEVELOPPEMENT INNOVATION	GDI	France

CONSTRUCTION ÉNERGIES RENOUVELABLES ET ALTERNATIVES GUADELOUPE SYNERGÎLE	Synergîle	France
CHAMBRE CONSULAIRE INTERPROFESSIONNELLE DE SAINT- MARTIN	CCISM	France
CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL	CE	Spain

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The FORWARD project brings together 24 members of three nationalities (i.e., Spanish, Portuguese, and French) from nine Outermost Regions. The members are the nine local governments of the ORs, seven universities and other institutions as commerce chambers, public organizations dedicated to innovation and science, and development agencies or innovation clusters (Table 1). This EU-FP project intends to improve ORs' excellence in research and innovation potential, supporting their participation in the EU Framework Programme.

The Work Package 3, titled "*Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans*", is at the center of the FORWARD project. It creates a space of discussion between experts of ORs, continental Europe, and Third Countries (currently are involved: Palestine; Mexico; Tunisia; and Brazil). The time of common work and exchange around a defined thematic should foster collaboration and consortium creation around the Thematic Working Groups. During the first phase, the TWGs had for mission the co-creation of action plans which will help to structure the work of the thematic groups, the completion of their objectives and facilitate the win of EU-FP calls.

The mapping of the Research and Innovation ecosystem of the ORs, overseen by the WP2 (Diagnostics of ORs' R&I ecosystems), concluded that the low representativity of the ORs in EU-FP calls is due to European, national, and regional public policies which do not enough support the participation of outermost regions in the European Research Area; a lack of strategy which impedes the connection of ORs to major European networks; and few numbers of organizations which are involved in FP. The TWGs are designed to answer those problems helped by the WP4 (Capacity building and training activities) and the WP5 (Networking activities).

Opportunities of EU-FP funding for the ORs for the current Framework Programme (FP9) Horizon Europe are stronger on Pillar II and III (67.2 billion) without excluding Pillar I. Widening 2.0 is endowed with 2.96 billion and is adapted to the ORs. The transversal programme Widening 2.0 aims to facilitate access to EU-FP funds. The TWGs are particularly aware of that context and organize their activities in that way.

The effect of the worldwide Covid-19 epidemic is non-negligible on the FORWARD project and particularly on WP3, which was supposed to include face-to-face activities. Although the activity calendar and format were partially affected and had to be adjusted, partners were still able to organize multiple meetings between the Sub-coordinators, Deputies, and Facilitators of the TWGs and ensure an easy exchange of good practices and deep collaboration and interaction among the TWG members. A survey will be conducted on the WP3 actors (TWG members) to evaluate their perception of the Covid-19 over the entire implementation of the work package. The results of the survey will be included in the next WP3 deliverable (D3.3).

The activities of the eight Thematic Working Groups were launched between November 2020 and February 2021 with 527 registered members with almost 50% of active members. The thematic come from Social Sciences to Biodiversity passing through Marine and Universe Sciences, Energy and Climate, Agriculture and Biotechnologies, Information and Communication Technology and of course Health, applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies. The TWGs were guided to co-create their action plan while respecting the autonomy and the decision-making capacity of each thematic group. This two-months process allows the members coming from the nine ORs, with a majority from Canary Islands, Madeira, and Azores, to work online and offline.

A large proportion of the registered members of the TWGs come from academia followed by SME and local government, while the NGO sector and other members of the civil society are less represented.

The members judged the level of their skills in writing proposals between "low" to "average", as their international R&I networking. The average experience in the EU-FP funded programmes is self-evaluated between a "very low level" to a "low level".

The proportion of females in the TWGs is around 37% against 63% for the male, which is not so far from the European average females' proportion in science and technology of 2019.

The eight thematic action plans are presented with a short introduction of the context and the main objectives of the group. They are composed of a list of actions with details, start and end date, resource needs, and expected outcomes. All the actions listed are in consistency with the TWGs and the FORWARD project aims.

Two strategies are applied in the TWGs: the first one consists to start to work as an established consortium (TWG1-TWG2-TWG5) by the selection of appropriate calls and the drafting of projects; the second consists of establishing the conditions to create projects with members coming from different areas and with different expertise. All TWGs remain particularly attentive to the coming EU-FP calls.

The analysis of the action plans highlights the need for local data, at the scale of ORs, to foster the development of international collaborative projects. It also indicates that among the different types of actions three seem more relevant and were chosen by the TWGs: "Planning and co-creation", "Dissemination and communication" and "Mapping and Inventory".

The phase of implementation of these action plans already started in March 2021. It will run at least up to June 2022, after validation of the demand of extension of the FORWARD project. To achieve the aims of the project, the TWGs will need a high engagement of the members, which the FORWARD project will seek to ensure throughout the next year. To be able to do what they know the best: **“find and innovate”** ORs experts will need the full support of the project partners but also from the local governments, and European Commission to convert this transoceanic dynamic into concrete actions.

INTRODUCTION

The FORWARD project

The FORWARD project is based on low participation of European Outermost Regions (then after ORs) in framework programme Horizon 2020 (FP8). This low representativeness was explained by the fragmentation of the research community at the conception of the FORWARD project (FORWARD, 2018).

The Work Package 2 (Diagnostics of ORs' R&I ecosystems): introduced its final report such as WP2 _ Nine regional diagnoses and joint strategy for OR R&I ecosystem performance (FORWARD-Nexa, 2020).

"[...] Though the participation of lagging behind regions has been analyzed in depth [Makkonen et al. 2015; Pontikakis et al. 2018], Outermost regions remain a blind spot. Collective representations, reflected in the article 349 of the Treaty on European Union, point out the inherent, structural characteristics of these territories, that would inhibit the participation to collaborative, competitive, calls for projects: small ecosystems, with limited and fragmented research and innovation capacities; physical isolation and lack of integration in the networks; specific challenges and research topics, largely ignored by the calls for projects of the FP, etc.. Such determinist "handicap rhetoric" naturalizes the obstacles to H2020, homogenizes highly singular territories and neglects their ongoing realizations and exceptional potential.

The Forward project offers an opportunity to question these representations. What is the actual performance of Outermost Regions in terms of FP participation? How do they compare to other European Regions? Are they isolated from the networks that dominate the scene? Do the participation determinants identified by the literature apply to Outermost Regions? Do they face specific challenges? What are the similarities and differences between the outermost regions? How do they compare to each other in terms of organization and participation to FP? Do they share the same assets and weaknesses? [...]"

The first outcomes of the WP2¹ suggest three main reasons which can explain the weak participation of the ORs in EU-FP calls and funded projects (FORWARD-Nexa, 2019).

- European, national, and regional public policies do not enough support the participation of outermost regions in the European Research Area;
- A lack of strategy impedes the connection of ORs to major European networks;
- Few organizations are involved in FP.

The larger potential of research activities in these places, therefore, remains unexplored such as biodiversity, biotechnologies based on ORs specific species, perfect places of experimentation, marine sciences, and large coastal areas, etc.

The FORWARD project intends to improve ORs' excellence in research and innovation potential, supporting their participation in EU-FP projects and helping to connect research activities. And this should be done with territories physically far from the major research centers.

The project analyses research and innovation ecosystems and rely on the results of the mapping, the inventory, and the analysis done (WP2), implement tailored actions as capacity building and networking sessions (WP4² & WP5³).

This Outermost Regions project is funded by the programme H2020-EU.5. – **“SCIENCE WITH AND FOR SOCIETY”**⁴ which has for aim the recruitment of new talent for science, the pairing of scientific excellence with social awareness and responsibility, and the building of effective cooperation between science and society. The call through which the project was funded is: SWAFS-22-2018⁵ **“Mobilising Research Excellence in EU Outermost Regions (OR)”**

The FORWARD project brings together 24 members of three nationalities (i.e., Spanish, Portuguese, and French) from nine ORs by alphabetic orders: Azores, Canary Islands, French Guiana, Guadeloupe, La Réunion, Madeira, Martinique, Mayotte, Saint-Martin. The members are the nine local governments of the ORs, seven universities and other institutions as

¹ WP1: Diagnostic of the ORs' R&I ecosystem

² WP4: Capacity building and training activities

³ WP5: Networking activities

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020-EU.5>.

⁵ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_Swafs-22-2018

commerce chambers, public organizations dedicated to innovation and science, development agencies or innovation clusters. See list of the FORWARD consortium (Table 1) at the page 11.

The FORWARD project is composed of eight (8) Work Packages (see Figure 1). In addition of four (4) essential transversal Work Package i.e., the “Management and coordination” (WP1), the “Dissemination and communication” (WP8), and the “Monitoring, evaluation and performance” (WP7), the project is articulated around five (5) packages. The kernel of the project proposes to co-create and implement thematic action plans (WP3) on the base of a Research and Innovation ecosystem analysis (WP2) using training (WP4) and networking (WP5) activities to ease ORs participation in EU calls, by among other redesigning the regional policies (WP6).

Figure 1 Descriptive diagram of the FORWARD project structure, eight Work Packages out of nine

The Work Package 3 is one of the pillars of the FORWARD project and is at the center of the project aims because it includes for a long period the actors of Research, Development, and Innovation of the Outermost Regions.

The WP3 will benefit from the training offered by the WP4, the networking actions supported by the WP5, and the expertise of the WP8 for communication and dissemination.

The Work Package 3: Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans

The Work Package 3 “Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans” is at the center of the FORWARD project and it is structured by the information on the Research-Development and Innovation in the Outermost Regions (WP2) and supported by the “Capacity building and the trainings activities” (WP4) and “Networking activities” (WP5).

The description given in the Grant Agreement of the project (FORWARD, 2018) is:

“Critical mass and connectivity among ORs and between ORs and continental Europe are some of the main obstacles ORs faced with to access EU framework programme. The aim of this work package is to reinforce the actual and reveal the potential competitive advantages of Outermost Regions in their respective sectors of fields of expertise and the identification of common interests. To fulfil this aim, a number of thematic working groups, composed of experts from ORs or from other countries, will be established and they will meet and work together for the definition and implementation of thematic action plans in accordance with WP2 results and with the feedback of ORs’ R&I communities. These action plans will contribute to foster collaboration on common thematic among ORs, between ORs and third countries as well as continental Europe stakeholders.”

In another word, the WP3 should create a space of discussion between experts of ORs and other countries. The time of common work and discussion around a defined thematic should foster collaboration and consortium creation around the Thematic Working Groups.

One of the displayed objectives of FORWARD-H2020 is the submission of at least one project to EU-FP calls for each TWG (FORWARD-ITC-Synergîle, 2020).

The Thematic Working Group concept

The Thematic Working Group (TWG) was presented in the Grant Agreement of the project (FORWARD, 2018) and thorough by the task T3.1 “Building thematic working group in key common strategic fields of expertise” (FORWARD-ITC, 2020).

The concept of the TWG is based on the set up of a digital space of discussion and work where FORWARD brings together ORs experts and representatives from European and Third Countries (FORWARD, 2018). Each TWG focuses their work on a defined theme with possible

collaboration with other groups. The TWGs were designed to be agile and smooth since the conception of the project (FORWARD, 2018).

The management of the thematic working groups is described in detail by D3.1 “Guidelines: T3.1 Thematic working groups and thematic action plans methodology” (FORWARD-ITC, 2020). The TWGs are managed by a Sub-Coordinator selected by the Steering Committee based on her/his profile. A deputy may be named by the Sub-coordinator to support/replace her/him if necessary. In fact, a Deputy was named for each TWG except for two of them.

The sub-coordinators were trained (10/28/2020) before the kick-off meeting of the TWGs (January-February 2021) to manage the action plan co-creation phase and conduct the digital meetings on Teams Microsoft. Full documentation has been made available with regular updates based on the needs identified (FORWARD-ITC, 2020).

Two facilitators from the same ORs of the Sub-Coordinator were designated to aid the management of the TWG. The role of the facilitator is essential in the management of the TWG particularly for the digital aspects (*e.g.* organization of the online meetings, internal coordination, reporting, dissemination of the documents, continuous communication with TWG members.). The first months of operation have shown that without a designated or available facilitator the meetings do not take place.

The guideline D3.1 (FORWARD-ITC, 2020) also mentioned that:

“In the event that a group is composed of members from more than one institution in the same OR, it is recommended, but not compulsory, that they designate a Regional Contact Point to manage the TWG at the regional level. “

In fact, no Regional Contact Point was designated. The choice was made to not activate this option at this time (FORWARD-ITC, 2020). This possibility would be considered for the future if the conditions are met *i.e.*, number of members in an outermost region and true dynamic at the regional scale.

To fit with the EU requirement, the TWG must respect the quadruple-helix approach and thus associate research institutes, SMEs, local government, and civil society as NGO (Yawson, 2009).

The Action Plan: concept and expected format

As indicated above each TWG should propose and implement a Thematic Action Plan to encourage collaboration on common thematic between stakeholder at the scale of ORs, Europe, and Third countries (FORWARD-ITC, 2020).

The action plan is composed of a list of objectives and actions to reach them. These actions should structure the work, the discussion within the TWG, and with the other groups.

The expected format of the action plans was detailed in the Thematic Working Group Guideline (FORWARD-ITC-Synergîle, 2020).

The list of actions should be sort in the spreadsheet with at least eight (8) columns:

- Action
- Details and venue
- Start and end dates
- Resources
- Person in charge of the activity
- Co-organiser
- Expected results
- Level of advancement

The list of actions is completed with the list of the members and the list of achievements (FORWARD-ITC, 2020).

The action plan is a dynamic document that will evolve with the advance of the completion of the actions, the composition of the TWG, and the EU-FP calls. The document will have to be frequently updated, after each significant change and/or at a defined period.

CONTEXT

Context of Research and Innovation in Outermost Regions

WP2 (Diagnostics of ORs' R&I ecosystems) oversaw the mapping of the Research and Innovation ecosystem of the ORs. The main obstacles to EU-FP programme were listed at the introduction (page 16).

The WP2 proposed to classify the performance of the OR in the usage of EU-FP in four groups. The normal performer, the Canary Islands; the out-performers, Azores and Madeira, the under-performers, French Guiana, Guadeloupe, La Réunion and Martinique; and the non-performers Mayotte and Saint-Martin (FORWARD-Nexa, 2019) at the page 32.

The WP2 explains broadly the composition of the Thematic Working Group and the issue to recruit experts and stakeholders in the ORs such as Saint-Martin and Mayotte.

For more details on Research and Innovation in the ORs the reader should refer to the deliverable D2.2 (*WP2: Nine regional diagnoses and joint strategy for OR R&I ecosystem performance*) where the full analysis is provided for the ORs for which information on R-I ecosystem are available (FORWARD-Nexa, 2020).

Future opportunity in term of EU funding

The current European Framework Programme IX, Horizon Europe (2021-2027) is based on three Pillars plus one transversal (Figure 2). In the following order:

- Pillar I: Excellent Science, 25 billion of dotation;
- Pillar II: Global Challenges 1 European Industrial Competitiveness, 53.5 billion of dotation;
- Pillar III: Innovative Europe 13.6 billion;
- Transversal Pillar: Widening 2.0, 2.96 billion of dotation.

An element of comparison, during the two last framework programmes the ORs received 40.8 (FP7: 2007-2013) and 80.3 (FP8: 2014-2020, named Horizon 2020) million of euros. Almost

one hundred (100) organizations have been involved in projects and 55 in the position of coordinator, and 26 projects for mono-beneficiaries⁶.

Pillar I is composed of the European Research Council (funding organisation), the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (researcher training and mobility), and Research Infrastructures (Figure 2). This Pillar is designed to fund and to develop outstanding researchers and organizations, particularly those who already proved their excellence.

Pillar II and Pillar III are focused on solving global challenges. These two Pillars can be viewed as a bridge between, top-level research, civil society, and industry, using innovation as the key element of future growth.

All Pillars will offer important possibilities for the ORs to bring forward their assets with EU added value, also taking into account the stage of development (Technological Readiness Level, TRL) expected at EU level and the level of TRL in which local stakeholders are working.

The transversal Pillar Widening 2.0 aims to help member states with weaker research systems undertake reforms and win more EU research grants. This Pillar will try to plug the gap in Research, Development, and Innovation, that fits very well with the ORs situation.

Figure 2 Descriptive scheme of the Horizon Europe Framework Programme 9 and its pillars

⁶ Mono-Beneficiaries are here Small and Medium Enterprises which are funded by the EIC - European Innovation Council (old **SME Instrument**), part of the EU's Horizon 2020 programme.

Word Health Context

From March 11th, 2020 the World Health Organisation (WHO) declared that the propagation of the SARS-Cov-2 cause of the Covid-19 disease can be qualified as an epidemic. That declaration reduces and, in some cases, totally stops travel within European space but also outside.

The effect of this world health issue has inevitably impacted EU funded projects, including FORWARD, and especially its activities planned face-to-face such as WP3, WP4, and WP5. To a certain extent, this has implied meetings postponed, closed offices, and work reorganization. For WP3 activities, the partners have adjusted the activity planning, as described subsequently.

Initially the kick-off meeting of the Sub-Coordinators should have been organized during a FORWARD event allowing the Sub-coordinator to meet but also to be trained at the digital meeting management. The kick-off meeting was organized with Teams Microsoft in December 2020 during a two hours video-conference. The follow-up meeting of the Sub-coordinators which should be organized also during a FORWARD meeting was organized virtually, on the same platform.

The final meeting of the project at Brussels should be the only event where the Sub-coordinators will have the possibility to come together and discuss their experience and the good practices. Some thoughts are underway between the WP3 task leaders to organize several Sub-coordinators meetings before the end of the project. The aim will be to ease the setup of consortiums linking several themes.

The positive point of the worldwide epidemic is that the situation allows to organize more meetings between the Sub-coordinators, Deputies and Facilitators to ease the exchange of good practices and foster more collaboration and interaction between the TWGs. One should also note that a second positive aspects the popularization of the video-conference with more members comfortable with the associated software (*e.g.*; GoToMeeting, Skype, Zoom, Jitsi Meet, etc.).

Table 2 Calendar of task T3.2 and T3.3 of the FORWARD-H2020 project

Delivery	Expected (January 2020)	Realized or planned
Task T3.2 Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans	January 2019-July 2020	December 2020-March 2021
D3.2 Thematic action plans	June 2020	April 2021
Task T3.3 Sustainability of thematic working group	July 2020-December 2021	March 2021-June 2022
D3.3 Sustainability solutions for thematic working groups	December 2021	June 2022

THE THEMATIC WORKING GROUPS

The process of selection of the Sub-coordinators (FORWARD-ITC, 2020) and the mapping of the ORs Research and Innovation (FORWARD-Nexa, 2020) allow the creation of eight (8) Thematic Working Groups (Table 3) validated by the FORWARD Steering Committee during the first semester of 2020. The full list of the Thematic Working Groups is presented in the following table. One thematic was dropped from the initial TWGs list (FORWARD-ITC, 2020) **Tourism, eco-tourism, nature tourism, cultural tourism**, and integrated to the TWG2 due to its strong connections with social sciences. One should note that the TWG4 has a sub-group “Smart city and Tourism” which tackle the digital aspect of tourism.

Table 3 List of the Thematic Working Groups with number of registered and active members

	Name	Number of registered	Number of active members
TWG1	Health, applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies	84	28
TWG2	Social sciences and social innovation	130	78
TWG3	Earth, space and universe sciences	26	13
TWG4	Information and Communications Technology	49	25
TWG5	Climate change and Energy transition	65	33
TWG6	Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering	57	26
TWG7	Biodiversity conservation and restoration	61	30
TWG8	Marine sciences & technologies	73	36

Thematic Working Group schedule

The co-creation and implementation of the action plan included in task T3.2 (*Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans*) and task T3.3 (*Sustainability of thematic working group*) were organized in two phases with three steps as visible in Figure 3. These two phases

were designed to spread from December 2020 to December 2021, the requested extension of the FORWARD project allows the experimentation of TWGs within the project up to June 2022.

Figure 3 Phasing of the co-creation and implementation of the Thematic Action Plan as presented in the D3.1

Phase 1 is composed of step 1, the Kick-Off Meeting of the TWGs which announced the beginning of the exchanges of the ORs experts with for goal the co-creation of the action plans and the establishment of consortiums. The second component of phase 1 is step 2 the co-creation of the thematic action, a four-meeting process described in the annex of the D3.1 (FORWARD-ITC, 2020).

Phase 2 starts since the action plan was validated by the TWG members. This phase should spread up to the end of the project (at this date, June 2021). The TWGs of the ORs should continue after the end of the FORWARD project once they will prove their efficiency and find the proper functioning and the adapted funding.

The initial meeting of the TWGs Sub-coordinators was held on the Teams Microsoft platform on September 17th, 2020 (Table 4). The initial training session was held one month later at the end of October. The first follow up meeting was at the beginning of December 2020 and allowed the beginning of the TWGs' activities in January with their Kick-off Meeting. One exception that must be mentioned here is the TWG2 Social sciences and social innovation, which launched its activities on November 26th, 2020 (FORWARD-Synergile, 2021).

To facilitate the writing of this report and get the feedback of the Sub-coordinators, Deputies, and Facilitators of the thematic working groups the WP3 leader (ITC) and the task T3.2 leader (Synergîle) organized a digital follow up meeting on March 17th, 2021. The aims of the meeting were to collect the comments of the actors, inventory the current issues, and prepare the synergies between the TWGs. A third meeting is planned for the middle of April 2021 (Table 2) to set the collaboration and exchange between the TWG, particularly the ones with transversal activities as TWG2 (Social sciences and social innovation), TWG4 (Information and Communication Technologies), TWG5 (Climate Change and Energy Transition) and TWG7 (Biodiversity conservation and restoration).

Table 4 Calendar of the main events of the TWGs coordination

Sub-coordinators kick-off meeting	17 th September 2020
Initial training of the Sub-coordinators	28 th October 2020
Follow up session with Sub-coordinators	3 rd December 2020
TWG meetings: work on the definition of action plans.	December 2020 – March 2021
Second follow up meeting: feedback on Action Plan	17 th March 2021
Deadline for submission of task T3.2: Report on TWG's Action Plan	15 th April 2021
Third follow up meeting: coordination of collaboration between the TWGs	28 th April 2021

Analyse of the co-creation phase

The organizations chosen and applied by the TWGs are different for each working group. The number of meetings organized, and their frequency is a first proof (Table 5). That aspect will be more detailed in the section “**ANALYSE OF THE THEMATIC ACTION PLANS**” and in the Annex I of this document with the full action plan version (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Table 5 Calendar of the meetings by TWG

	KOM	WS1	WS2	WS3	WS4	WS5	Meeting phase 2
TWG1	4 Mar 21	offline exchange			offline validation		13 Apr21
TWG2	26 Nov 20	26 Jan 21	25 Feb 21				

TWG3	18 Jan 21	05 Feb 21	24 Feb 21	4 Mar 21	+offline activities		
TWG4	12 Jan 21	19 Jan 21	26 Jan 21	04 Feb 21	09 Feb 21	24 Feb 21	29Mar21
TWG5	27 Jan 21	09 Feb 21	19 Mar 21	16 Apr 21	+offline activities		
TWG6	14 Jan 21	21 Jan 21	28 Jan 21	04 Feb 21	11 Feb 21	26 Feb 21	April21
TWG7	12 Jan 21	26 Jan 21	09 Feb 21	23 Feb 21	+offline activities -		
TWG8	5 Feb 21	Week 22 Feb	-	-	-	26 Mar 21	

The composition of the TWGs is heterogeneous, Canary Islands and Madeira are highly represented followed by the Azores. The French territories are low represented (Figure 4). One should note the absence of Mayotte and St Martin in some TWG. This low representativity can be due to the absence of structures of research or their lack of maturity (FORWARD-Nexa, 2020). The number of the members of the TWGs is around 527 registered plus 66 since the beginning of the work of the thematic groups. Only half of the registered members are considered as active (i.e., attend the meeting, answer to email and survey). Possibility offers to register new members after the kick-off meeting was a reason for the successful achievement of co-creation of the thematic action plans with the recruitment of persons better aware of the running of the TWGs and their aims. One should highlight the contribution of members highly motivated who actively participate in two or three TWGs.

Figure 4 Distribution of the TWG members by Outermost Regions

A large proportion of the registered members are from university followed by SMEs and local government, while the NGO sector and other members of the civil society are less represented. That imbalance can have some effect on the quadruple-helix concept (Simona Cavallini, 2016). It was well evaluated by the TWGs and will be fixed with adapted and innovative recruitment campaigns at the scale of each group (Figure 5). The follow-up recruitment campaigns will aim to enrol future members of consortiums but also experts will help to structure the themes between ORs, to ease the creation of projects. One should note that, for the co-creation phase, the dissemination and communication of the WP3 recruitment achieved a positive response in terms of TWG members' enrolment and engagement. Regarding external communication, WP3 aims and actions, as well as TWGs meetings, were

promoted on the project channels. A dedicated webpage was created on the project website to describe in detail each of the TWG's scope and work. Regarding internal communication within the members, great efforts were done by the "coordination team" *i.e.* Deputy, Sub-coordinator, and Facilitator to ensure a smooth implementation of the activities and promote fruitful discussions and knowledge transfer within the TWG members. In the new implementation phase, further indicators and feedback will be collected to feed D3.3 on the sustainability of the TWGs. The aim will be to outline the most effective initiatives for group management and collaboration & best sharing within members.

Figure 5 Distribution of the TWGs members by kind of structures

Profile of the TWGs members

A deeper analysis in the quadruple-helix classification of the registered members of the TWGs was done. It allows us to propose a profile of the members (Figure 6). The University class groups the universities and the public research institutes. The SMEs class groups the private structure including the large firm. The Local Government class, the structures associated or dependent on regional governance. And the NGO class groups the independent associations and the structures not related to the three first classes.

Figure 6 Member profile distribution on the base of the quadruple-helix innovation concept of the eight Thematic Working Groups.

The distribution shows clearly that the University class is varying between 48% to 79% within the TWGs (Table 6). The Local Governments are represented in all TWGs at the level of 15%. the SMEs are less represented between 1.4% for TWG1 (Health) to 26.9% for TWG4 (ITC). The low number of SMEs in applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies, and Marine Sciences and Technologies should be adjusted with a more adapted communication campaign around those TWGs. Those two themes have many applications and have a broad ecosystem of associated enterprises as the TWG4 (ITC). The NGOs have a very low representation because of the need of structuration and international vision to solicit EU-FP funds. Some dedicated actions can be designed to help them to fill this gap. The percentage of members coming from NGO in the TWG are from 0% for the TWG6 (Agriculture and Biotechnologies) to 3.8% for the TGW4. The NGO are mainly associations of actors which are trying to structure their field at a regional scale.

Table 6 Representativity of the four classes of the quadruple-helix concept, based on the registration form of the Thematic Working Groups

Working Group	University	SMEs	Local Government	Civil Society
TWG1	78.8 %	9.1 %	10.6 %	1.5 %
TWG2	69.2 %	7.7 %	20.0 %	3.1 %
TWG3	73.3 %	10.0 %	13.3 %	3.3 %
TWG4	48.1 %	26.9 %	21.2 %	3.8 %
TWG5	58.5 %	16.9 %	21.5 %	3.1 %
TWG6	72.9 %	10.2 %	16.9 %	0.0 %
TWG7	77.8 %	4.8 %	14.3 %	3.2 %
TWG8	79.7 %	1.4 %	17.6 %	1.4 %

During the registration, it is asked to the future members to self-evaluate their capacities and experience in the EU project: writing proposal skills; International R&I networking; and participation in European FP funding programs (Figure 7).

The members judged their skills in writing proposals between a “low level” to an “average level”. The percentage of “very high level” is around 10% for five out of the eight TWGs. All TWGs have more than 30% of “high level” (Table 7).

Figure 7 Self-evaluation of the Thematic Working Groups during their registration.

The members declared to have a “low level” to an “average level” for the international networking in Research and Innovation. Three TWGs (3, 4 and 5) have a mean level between “average level” to “high level”. 31% is the minimum declared a “high level” in International R&I networking (Table 7).

The members also declared to have a “very low level” to “low level” experience in the EU-FP funded programmes. The TWG4 and TWG5 are the ones which have a better average. Looking in detail the “very high level” answers are between 3 to 10 % and the “very low level” answers are around 20 %.

One can conclude that the average profile is members who declared to have a low to average level in writing, international networking, and participation in the EU-FP programmes. Three TWG (TWG3, TWG4 and TWG5) seem to have more experts in proportion but it is not significant. Each TWG has in their members a portion of people who declared a level of expertise from “high level” to “very high level”.

Table 7 Self-evaluation of the Thematic Working Groups during their registration, percentage of answers by group and question.

Working Group	Questions asked	level			
		Very low	Low	High	Very high
TWG1	Writing proposal skills	24.2 %	25.8 %	47.0 %	3.0 %
	International R&I networking	19.7 %	34.8 %	31.8 %	13.6 %
	Participation in European FP funding programs	27.3 %	37.9 %	28.8 %	6.1 %
TWG2	Writing proposal skills	18.8 %	40.6 %	32.8 %	7.8 %
	International R&I networking	18.5 %	40.0 %	33.8 %	7.7 %
	Participation in European FP funding programs	29.2 %	35.4 %	26.2 %	9.2 %
TWG3	Writing proposal skills	10.0 %	23.3 %	60.0 %	6.7 %
	International R&I networking	13.3 %	30.0 %	50.0 %	6.7 %
	Participation in European FP funding programs	16.7 %	36.7 %	36.7 %	10.0 %
TWG4	Writing proposal skills	13.5 %	34.6 %	40.4 %	11.5 %
	International R&I networking	13.7 %	25.5 %	49.0 %	11.8 %
	Participation in European FP funding programs	21.6 %	27.5 %	33.3 %	17.6 %
TWG5	Writing proposal skills	10.8 %	33.8 %	44.6 %	10.8 %
	International R&I networking	6.2 %	40.0 %	46.2 %	7.7 %
	Participation in European FP funding programs	14.1 %	35.9 %	39.1 %	10.9 %
TWG6	Writing proposal skills	20.3 %	32.2 %	42.4 %	5.1 %
	International R&I networking	20.7 %	32.8 %	36.2 %	10.3 %
	Participation in European FP funding programs	24.1 %	32.8 %	39.7 %	3.4 %
TWG7	Writing proposal skills	14.3 %	50.8 %	31.7 %	3.2 %

	International R&I networking	14.3 %	36.5 %	39.7 %	9.5 %
	Participation in European FP funding programs	22.2 %	41.3 %	31.7 %	4.8 %
TWG8	Writing proposal skills	11.0 %	43.8 %	35.6 %	9.6 %
	International R&I networking	16.2 %	32.4 %	39.2 %	12.2 %
	Participation in European FP funding programs	19.4 %	36.1 %	37.5 %	6.9 %

Gender Balance

It is not obvious to analyse the gender balance in a project based on the volunteering of a scientific community with a proven disparity. The current composition of the TWGs is mainly due to the initial recruitment phase and the enrolment using the network of the members of the TWGs. No proceedings were conducted to enrol a defined proportion of females.

The proportion of females in the TWG is around 37% against 63% for the males, which is not so far from the European average females' proportion in science and technology of 2019⁷.

The proportion of females in the management of the TWGs is varying between 12% for the Sub-coordinators and 67% for the Facilitators, with 17% for the Deputies.

At the scale of the members of the TWGs (Table 8) the minimum of the representation is for the TWG3 (Earth system, on space and universe Science) with 14% and the maximum around 52% for the TWG2 (Social Sciences).

One TWG has a percentage of females noticeably lower than the continental average, as mentioned above is the TWG3. That low value can be explained by the low representativity of females in Earth and Space Sciences evaluated to 20% in the USA by Wilson et al. in 2016⁸.

⁷ Eurstat 2021

⁸ https://www.americangeosciences.org/sites/default/files/ExitSurvey_2016_final_0.pdf

Table 8 Gender ratio within the Thematic Working Groups

	Number		Percentage	
	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>
Sub-coordinator	1	7	12%	88%
Deputy	1	5	17%	83%
Facilitator	10	5	67%	33%
TWG1 <i>Health, applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies</i>	27	39	41%	59%
TWG2 <i>Social sciences and social innovation</i>	33	31	52%	48%
TWG3 <i>Earth system, on space and Universe Sciences</i>	4	25	14%	86%
TWG4 <i>Information and Communication Technologies</i>	15	32	32%	68%
TWG5 <i>Climate Change and Energy Transition</i>	19	46	29%	71%
TWG6 <i>Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering</i>	24	35	41%	59%
TWG7 <i>Biodiversity conservation and restoration</i>	22	41	35%	65%
TW8 <i>Marine Science & technologies</i>	28	46	38%	62%

The progress of the Thematic Working Groups

The discussions with the Sub-coordinators, Deputies, and Facilitators allow the WP3 leader and T3.2 task leader to identify some issues during the TWGs meetings. Particularly around the communication platform which is in an improvement phase to facilitate the operation of the TWGs. Moreover, the tools proposed (e.g., SWOT Analysis, S.M.A.R.T objectives, How/How diagram) were not always well-known by some of the members as it was the first time they used them.

The size of the groups is determinant for the hold of fruitful meetings. With up to 18 to 20 persons, a positive dynamic can be maintained. Above that number, in video-conference configuration, the maintenance of the positive dynamic may start to be more complex with less active participants and less chance to have fruitful collaboration. The sub-grouping seems the solution, many TWGs made that choice to allow experts to talk on specific subjects before the validation of the TWG. The reorganization of the group in sub-groups with higher interaction does not have to be perceived as a counterproductive action but as a tool to ease the discussions and allow the creation of high-level projects.

The duration of this two months co-creation phase was considered too long for some TWG members who expected to work on more concrete actions right from the beginning, particularly on an EU-FP call or to elaborate a consortium. This situation pushed some members to be less present, waiting for Phase 2 - Implementation. That effect will be evaluated with a survey of satisfaction that will be addressed to the members at the beginning of the implementation to have their perceptions between phase 1 (co-creation of the action plan) and phase 2 (implementation and more action to build project). The demand of a member to be withdrawn from a TWG is rare, only three were counted since the kick-off meetings of the TWGs.

The main issues reported by the TWGs are related to the communication platform. Teams Microsoft gave some difficulties to the users particularly for the ones who were used to work with another communication platform like Google, Zoom, GoToMeeting, Jitsi Meet, or a mix of all. The first analysis done by Synergîle which oversees that digital tool showed that those issues come from a lack of identification. The user does not log on to their attributed account and does not have enough rights to access and modify documents (i.e., file, video, survey, etc). That can be explained by too many digital accounts but also by an unsafe usage of the numerical tools.

Evaluation of the feedback of the Sub-coordinators, Deputies, and Facilitators allows us to edit a table of satisfaction of the communication platform used within the TWG and its configuration (Table 9). The evaluation was done from a first facilitator meeting on February 17th, 2021 and the Sub-coordinators, Deputies, and Facilitators' meeting on March 17th, 2021 (Table 4). The table will have to be confirmed by the future survey. Three points are

problematic: the technical ease of use, the remote work tools, and ease to welcome new members. The actions which have been conducted to improve those points are special training for the Facilitators and the modification of the rules of sharing of a document. A full analysis is on way to propose an adapted numerical tool to fit better with the TWG concept. During this time, all possible actions and support are done to ease the usage of the selected digital platform by all the actors of the TWGs.

Table 9 Evaluation of communication platform of the WP3 of FORWARD (Teams Microsoft)

Parameter	Evaluation
Friendliness	Good
Technical ease	Medium
Organization ease	Good
Workshop efficiency	Good
Remote work tools	Medium
Ease to welcome new member	Medium

Group dynamics and co-creation motivation

The group dynamic during the first phase was positive. It allows having the eight action plans on time. The number of members has increased during this first phase. The meetings were held in a warm atmosphere, with a real connection between the members. The members' willingness to contribute to future projects can be evaluated as full.

One cannot conclude at this stage on the efficiency of the TWG concept, but the signals are positive so far. The members are involved, inquire for the next meetings, solicit their networks, and take initiatives for the good of the group.

This group dynamic will be monitored during the implementation phase, through frequent surveys. That monitoring process was not launched during the first phase because of the high solicitation of the TWGs members.

More details of the operation of the TWGs are provided in the next two sections (THE THEMATIC ACTION PLAN LIST and ANALYSIS OF THE ACTION PLAN).

THE THEMATIC ACTION PLANS

The eight (8) action plans are presented in this section with a table of the list of actions and a short presentation based on the full presentation edited by each Thematic Working Group. The full presentation of the thematic action plans is available in the Annex I of the document (FORWARD-Synergîe, 2021).

To not alter the vision of the TWG, the introductions of the action plan were not modified in this document. The short introductions presented are a selection of the more relevant information for this document which tries to inventory the actions and define how they should be supported to foster the submission and the win of a maximum number of the project to the Horizon Europe calls (EU-FP9) by the ORs. However, the objective of proposals' submission in response to EU-FP calls is not mandatory for the TWGs. It is one among others, it is completed with the aim of structuration of the eight thematic fields at the scale of the ORs. TWGs will work with the aim of presenting proposals in mind; nevertheless, the key aims of the action plans' implementation will be networking, knowledge & best practice transfer, and increased learning to engage in FP and prepare a good-quality proposal submission.

The action plan of the eight (8) thematic working groups of the FORWARD project are all particular but respect the guidelines (FORWARD-ITC, 2020) edited by ITC with the description of the action, details, expected outcomes, starting and ending time, and state of advancement.

The dynamic of two-months co-creation processes produced different visions in terms of objective and methodology to achieve the goals of the TWG but also of the project. Each thematic action plan has its own logic, based on long thoughts and intense exchange between ORs experts. A full analysis is proposed in the next section which tries to classify the actions, propose possible support and synergies between the TWG and their sub-groups.

TWG1 Action plan

TWG1 : Health, Applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies

This section only presents an introduction of the action plan, the full version is available in the Annex I-TWG1 (FORWARD-Synergile, 2021).

Sub-coordinator: Dr Jacob Lorenzo-Morales

Facilitator: Dr Paloma Bernal and Elizabeth Carrillo

Number of registered members: 84

Number of women: 27 (41%), **number of men:** 39 (59%)

Estimated active members: 29

Profile of the members

The members of the TWG1 are mainly from Canary Island and Madeira, more than 55%, followed by Guadeloupe, Azores, and Martinique. At this stage, there is only one OR missing to be complete: Saint-Martin.

The members are for the large majority coming from academia (i.e., university, university hospital and public hospital) with 79%. 9% of the members are SMEs and 10% are related to the local governments.

The level in proposal writing is self-evaluated by the members as “low level” to “average level”, but 47% declared it as “high level”. The experience in EU-FP funding programmes is for 65% of the members from “low level” to “very low level”. The international R&I networking is at an “average level” but with 13% at a “very high level”.

The balance between males and females on the 84 registered members is good with 41% to 59%. These percentage correspond to the average percentage of females in science and technology in UE⁹.

Health in EU-FP programmes

From the extensive data mining activity done in WP2, mainly from CORDIS, we identified 21 projects funded by H2020 in Health and applied medical technologies, diagnostics and therapies. The global amount received by ORs is €7.5M, corresponding to 5% of the total amount given to the projects where OR participated. By region, we concluded that Canaries is

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/fr/web/products-eurostat-news/-/edn-20200210-2>

an outstanding OR involved in H2020 health projects, followed by Azores & Madeira with minor participation, and finally there is a limited participation of French ORs in H2020. Considering organizations with at least two funded projects we can see that two universities, a consulting group and the Canarian Health Service are the main H2020 players.

For the analysis of the grant schemes and Project types we included: 1) Collaborative projects from H2020 Challenge 1 (health), 2) Marie Curie Projects and ERANETs. The main conclusion is 74% of projects cover: Training, Networking, Capacities, etc., meaning that we were more successful in getting funding towards actions supporting R+i rather than R+i itself (26%).

The TWG1 presents a wide experience in the field of tropical and emerging diseases. For instance, the Sub-coordinator of the TWG1 is currently the director of the University Institute of Tropical Diseases and Public Health of the Canary Islands at the University of La Laguna. This Institution presents more than 15 years of experience in diagnosis, treatment, vector surveillance and prevention of tropical and emerging diseases including COVID-19. Moreover, the IUETSPC collaborates with many institutions in America, Africa and Asia working in this field which has produced many scientific publications and congress communications. Some of the partners also present wide experience in antiparasitic agents, vector control and diagnosis of tropical and emerging diseases in ORs.

The thematic working group 1 have defined their aims as:

- ✓ **submit at least one applications** under the calls for the EU [Horizon Europe](#) and/or the next [4th Health programme](#) *The number of applications will certainly depend on the dynamics of the group itself, the opportunities created and those associated with the calls that will open*
- ✓ **organize at least one international thematic event**
- ✓ **at least two training activities** according to members' needs

These aims are aligned with the training actions planned (WP4), and the networking plan (WP5), and are based on the R+i diagnostic performed (WP2), the RIS3 strategy, and the specific needs/barriers stated by R+i actors. We expect that TWG1 participants will benefit from its participation by:

- ✓ finding funding opportunities and support in the proposal development processes

- ✓ get customized guidance on choosing relevant calls, topics and types of actions
- ✓ acquire training and receive assistance on proposal writing and consortia establishment
- ✓ improving their skills when approaching EU research projects

Priority in Funding

Within the TWG1 we will prioritise when possible R+i projects rather than R+i supporting actions and/or R+i training actions. In any case TWG1 will do its best to reach and provide a suitable option for the higher number of members as possible.

TWG1 proposals to be developed will fit mainly in the Pilar 2, CLUSTER 1: HEALTH. The second possibility, because the “Tropical Diseases” is not related to any of the official topics, is called the 4th Pilar (Widening participation and strengthening the ERA), with the submission to a COST ACTION to support this research field.

The list of actions

The actions list if the Thematic Action plan of the TWG1 is presented below. Only the columns: Action; Details, Date, Resource and Expected outcome are presented.

This action plan is based on five main objectives and 19 actions. On these actions three have been declared finished, four in progress and twelve are planned.

Table 1 Action of the Action Plan of the thematic working group 1 : Health, applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies

Nº	Actions	Details/Venue	Start/end	Resources	Expected results
OBJ 1	Management: Development of the TWG1 management tasks to achieve goals within the set scope, time, quality and budget specifications.	All the documents, online conferences and results will be uploaded in TEAMS+DRIVE	Sept20 - Dec21		
1.1	Implementation of cooperation and communication tools		Sept20 - March21		
1.1.1	Setting up, short training and implementation of online tools	MST - TWG Collaborative Space	Feb-Mar21	MST	MST - TWG tool implemented
1.2	TWG Meetings		Sept20 - Dec21		
1.2.1	First international sub-coordinators meeting and training	MST - TWG Collaborative Space	sept-20	TWG Meetings Templates	Meeting Minutes: Advancements, agreements and next actions planning + Recording + presentations
1.2.2	TWG1 Kick-off meeting	MST - TWG Collaborative Space	March21	TWG Meetings Templates	Agenda + Recording + presentations
1.2.3	TWG1 meetings	MST - TWG Collaborative Space	March-Dic 21	TWG Meetings Templates	Meeting Minutes: Advancements, agreements and next actions planning + Recording + presentations
1.3	Reporting		Dec21		
1.3.1	First annual TWG1 Reporting	MST - TWG Collaborative Space	Dec21	Report Template	TWG Report
OBJ 2	Focusing: Selecting key research fields and subjects	All the documents, online conferences and results will be uploaded in TEAMS+DRIVE	March-Jun21		
2.1	Creating specific TW Sub-groups		March-Jun21		
2.1.1	Filling in TWG Members' profiles	MST - TWG Collaborative Space + Google Drive	March21	Tailored Member Profile template (ERC pannels + past projects)	Draft catalogue of member profiles
2.1.2	Analysis of TWG1 Members' profiles	MST - TWG Collaborative Space + Google Drive	April21	Member Profile template	Draft catalogue of member profiles by sub-thematic area
2.1.3	Creation of specific sub-groups	MST - TWG Collaborative Space + Google Drive	May-Jun21	Member Profile template + feedback from meetings	Catalogue of member profiles by areas of interest
OBJ 3	Networking: Establishment of networks between the ORs and external actors to build consortia	To be carried out in close cooperation with WP5 Leaders	Jan-Dec21		
3.1	Identifying key institutions/actors/stakeholders		Jul-Sept21		
3.1.1	Creation of a list of institutions with ongoing collaborations	MST - TWG Collaborative Space + Google Drive	Jul-Sept21	Database	Creation of a channel on TEAMS "TWG1 Partner" + Creation of a folder on Google Drive "TWG1 Partner"
3.1.2	Creation of a list of key institutions/actors (ORs, EU, LATAM, USA, ROW)	MST - TWG Collaborative Space + Google Drive	Jul-Sept21	Database	Creation of a channel on TEAMS "TWG1 Partner" + Creation of a folder on Google Drive "TWG1 Partner"
3.2	Identifying External Networking Events		Jan-Dec21		
3.2.1	Identification and dissemination among TWG1 members of (regional, national or/and EU level) events	MST - TWG Collaborative Space + Google Drive	Jan-Dec21	Database	Creation of a channel on TEAMS "TWG1 Events" with factsheets with information of the calls + Creation of a folder on Google Drive "TWG1 Events"

3.3	Promoting TWG Networking Activities		Oct-Dec21		
3.3.1	TWG1 thematic event: Health in the ORs (synergy with WP5 Networking)		Oct-Nov21		increase the opportunities to build and to promote new projects
3.3.2	Sub-thematic Networking event (focused in the most relevant scientific area)		Oct-Nov22		increase the opportunities to build and to promote new projects
OBJ 4	Implementation: fostering the participation of OR's organizations in European R+i programmes	All the documents, online conferences and results will be uploaded in TEAMS+DRIVE	Jan-Dec21		
4.1	Identifying funding opportunities		Jan-Dic21		
4.1.1	Identification of specific calls and topics of interest	MST - TWG Collaborative Space + Google Drive	Feb-Dec21	Database	Creation of a channel on TEAMS "TWG1 Funding opportunities" with factsheets with information of the calls + Creation of a folder on Google Drive "TWG1 Partner" with factsheets with information of the calls
4.2	Building potential consortium		Sept-Dec21		
4.2.1	Identification of active partners in TWG1 areas	MST - TWG Collaborative Space + Google Drive	Sept-Oct21	Database	Creation of a channel on TEAMS "TWG1 Partner" + Creation of a folder on Google Drive "TWG1 Partner"
4.2.2	Identification of networking platforms (linked with brokerage events finding)	MST - TWG Collaborative Space + Google Drive	March-Dec21	Database	Creation of a channel on TEAMS "TWG1 platforms" + Creation of a folder on Google Drive "TWG1 Partner"
4.3	Improving member's knowledge about international projects				
4.3.1	Identification of TWG1 member's needs	MST - TWG Collaborative Space + Google Drive	April21	Google form	List of possible future actions
4.3.2	Training/s	MST - TWG Collaborative Space + Google Drive	Jan-Dic21	MST	Agenda + recording + presentations
OBJ 5	Dissemination: Disseminating TWG activities.	All the documents, online conferences and results will be uploaded in TEAMS+DRIVE	Jan-Dic21		
5.1	Dissemination of TWG1 activities		Jan-Dic21		
5.1.1	Disseminate the TWG1 activities done through FORWARD channels (social media, web...)		Jan-Dic21	Template	Higher number of TWG1s news (+ synergy with other TWGs)
5.1.2	Disseminate the TWG1 profiles - Stakeholders (outside Ors)		Sept-Dic21	Catalogue of members + conclusions about sub-thematic areas	Higher number of TWG1s news + registered members in networking/consortia building platforms

TWG2 Action Plan

TWG2 : Social sciences and social innovation

This section only presents an introduction of the action plan, the full version is available in the Annex I-TWG2 (FORWARD-Synergile, 2021).

Sub-coordinator: Prof. Philippe Jean-Pierre

Facilitator: Dr Evelyne Tarnus and Dr Philippe Holstein

Number of registered members: 130

Number of women: 33 (52%), **number of men:** 31 (48%)

Estimated active members: 78

Profile of the members

The members of the TWG2, the only TWG directly related to social sciences, are mainly coming from Canary Islands (27%) followed by Madeira (16%). Almost 70% of the members are from universities (i.e. university or public research organizations). The local governments and related organizations group 20% of the members of the TWG2.

The writing proposal skill, the international R&I networking, and the participation in EU-FP programmes are self-evaluated by the TWG as “very low level” to “low level” (Figure 7). But a detailed analysis shows that 41% of the members estimate their proposal writing skills and their experience in EU-FP programmes at a “high level” to a “very high level” (Table 7). Less than a third of the members self-declared to have a “very low level” for the three parameters considered.

The TWG2 is the only group with a balanced number between females and males with more females (52%) than males (48%).

EU-FP in OR of the thematic

Analysis of CORDIS database shows that Social sciences Research & Innovation (SSRI)-related projects constitute the major field of participation of the ORs in EU-FP8 H2020. 53 of the 239

projects (corresponding to 112 on 364 participations) identified were tagged as related to "Social sciences"¹⁰ (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Social sciences also represent the largest percentage of EU contribution (25%) awarded to the Outermost Regions. The participation is however concentrated, with a clear lead from the Canary Islands (53% of the participation in EU contribution) and Madeira (27%), and the remarkable implication of 11 organizations (out of 67) that account for 60% of the total number of participations of the ORs.

Motivation of the TWG2 members

The motivation of the TWG was evaluated with a survey. The respondents, Social Sciences stakeholders, were invited to indicate whether the suggested levers constitute (or not) motives for them to participate in Horizon Europe projects. If all propositions received positive feedback (from 68 to 92% of adhesion), the "Collective" and "Goal oriented" levers look more acclaimed than "mean oriented" and "Individual" aspects (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

The survey also measured the personal ambition of the respondents. 66% of them - 25 people - intend to submit at least a project in the next programme (68% of them targeting one project and as a partner) and 76% set as an objective to get funded (29 people). These results show that the stakeholders are intrinsically motivated and feel rather confident in terms of chance of success.

Finally, the specific expectations of the respondents toward this working group and action plan were also collected. 23 actions, organized within six (6) categories, were submitted to the group's prioritization:

- Boosting your connectivity with partners
- Developing your interest in participating in EU projects
- Developing your technical skills
- Developing your other soft skills
- Anticipating future calls for proposals
- Improving ORs social sciences visibility towards EU partners

¹⁰ The role of social scientists may be underestimated since the mapping only takes into account projects dealing with social sciences and not the projects that may incorporate social sciences expertise.

The analysis shows that the respondents principally look for:

- technical training - particularly to identify their added value at EU level, to better understand EU policies in their respective fields of research, as well as to better know how to define Impacts of research –
- networking within ORs and with continental EU partners. Importantly, the connection with geographical basins as well as the development of other (soft) skills are not high-priority actions for the group.

Introduction of the Action Plan

Considering the regional R&I characteristics and dynamics in each OR, the "territorial experience" of the R&I ecosystems in terms of FP participation, the FP knowledge, experience and ambition of the social sciences group members, and the forthcoming opportunities in Horizon Europe, the ambition of the Social Sciences R&I group is to address European and OR's social challenges through the collaborative production of knowledge and solutions, supported by a stronger participation in the European Research Area and the associated Horizon Europe programme.

With respect to the regional diversity, our objective regarding Horizon Europe is to:

- Systematize and accelerate the dynamics of more advanced regions: the Azores, the Canary Islands, Madeira,
- Increase the participation of starting regions: Guadeloupe, French Guiana, La Reunion, Martinique,
- Develop the participation of new coming regions: Mayotte, Saint-Martin.

To reach this challenging and realistic ambition, the following action plan foresees two strategic objectives supported by a transversal support action:

- To develop R&I collaboration within ORs (A)
- To turn the Working group into an incubator for Horizon Europe projects (B)
- Build long-term perspective through a distributed coordination system (C)

The list of actions

The actions list if the Thematic Action plan of the TWG2 is presented below. Only the columns: Action; Details, Date, Resource and Expected outcome are presented.

The action plan is composed of four main objectives, three sub-objectives and ten actions. In this list of actions, one has been launched and in progress, one has been planned and the rest should be launched soon.

Table 10 List of actions of the Action Plan of the thematic working group 2 : Social sciences and social innovation

N°	Actions	Start/end	Resources	Expected results	Level of advancement
1	Develop R&I collaboration within ORs				
1.1	Mobilize Humanities and Social sciences to understand and boost R&I in ORs				
1.1.1	action 1 : Develop an original expertise on small and/or remote regional R&I systems	April 2021	Remote meetings	Co-Publications	To be launched
1.1.2	action 2: Mobilize the knowledge produced to contribute to the design and implementation of regional, national and European policies regarding R&I in the OR, such as Research Excellence, Innovation Capacities, Smart Specialization, Horizon Europe participation, etc.	End of 2021	Remote meetings + WP6 connexion	Policy briefs	To be launched
1.1.3	action 3 : Encourage the use of Responsible Research and Innovation principles - which implies that societal actors (researchers, citizens, policy makers, business, third sector organizations, etc.) work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society - in the Social Sciences Research & Innovation fields	2nd semester 2021	Online trainings	RRI capacities	To be launched
1.2	Build critical masses (including NGO) on targeted R&I fields to contribute to the European Research Area				
1.2.1	action 4: Map priority fields/research issues with EU added value, and animate dedicated subgroups that will implement a networking plan to increase the connections and cooperation between the ORs.	April 2021	Workshops, Stakeholders profile, Horizon Europe Opportunities, European Research Area ambition for Humanities and Social Sciences	Networking Co-publications	To be launched
1.2.2	action 5: Raise awareness on ORs stakeholders and initiatives through the conception and dissemination of a directory of stakeholders, a handbook of inspiring projects and an observatory of EU projects on humanities and social sciences involving ORs	April 2021	OR Participation database, Stakeholders survey, Sub-contracting for handbooks and matchmaking event	Directory of stakeholders Projects database Handbooks of projects	In progress
2	Turn the Social Sciences R&I group into an incubator for Horizon Europe projects				
2.1	Define and implement a joint capacity-building programme for Social Sciences between ORs				
2.1.1	action 6 : Identify volunteer institutions in all ORs to co-create and implement a joint programme aiming at empowering Social Sciences R&I stakeholders, according to their specific FP knowledge and experiences (through activities such as webinars to demystify Horizon European, provision of easy-to-use starting tools, webinars to share good practices, testimonials...)	April 2021	OR R&I Officers network and WP4 tools	Capacity plan for HSS at regional level Resources center with easy-to-use tools	To be launched
2.2	Connect with EU dynamic organizations in domains of expertise				
2.2.1	action 7: Identify the main EU champions in the R&I fields (as defined in action 5) and implement activities to start collaborations (online meetings to promote the ORs expertise, for instance)	Depends on action 6	OR R&I Officers network	Social Sciences projects database	To be launched
2.3	Detect opportunities and support the development of proposals				

2.3.1	action 8 : Examine the work programmes and organize Ideation workshops in each sub groups (defined in action 5)	Depends on action 6	OR R&I Officers network	Proposals Ideas	To be launched
2.3.2	action 9: Provide expert support all along the project development cycle: from the proposal ideas to the negotiation phase after selection; this action requests coordination between ORs regional support organizations.	Depends on action 6	OR R&I Officers network	Proposals submissions	To be launched
3	Build long-term perspective through a distributed coordination system				
3.1	Group management and implementation structure				
3.1.1	action 10: Based on a call for volunteers, this action will start with the definition of a group's coordination system which ensures members' adhesion and commitment, but also the effective implementation of the priority actions by sharing responsibilities among members.	April 2021	Remote meetings	Comitology	Planned

TWG3 Action Plan

TWG3 : Earth system, on space and Universe Sciences

This section only presents an introduction of the action plan, the full version is available in the Annex I - TWG3 (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Sub-coordinator: Eng. Pedro Silva (Azores, Portugal)

Deputy: Eng. Rui Martins (AIRCenter) and Eng. Mariana Ávila (AIRCenter)

Facilitator: Lina Silveira (FRCT), Marta Vergilio (FRCT) and Eduardo Braga (CCIA)

Number of registered members: 27

Number of women: 4 (14%), **number of men:** 25 (86%)

Estimated active members: 13

Profile of the members

The TWG Members' origin changed along the process and, in March 2021, the group has increased in number of enrolled members, from 19 to 27 (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021). The dominating region is Madeira, with seven members. The biggest difference is that the group ended up having representatives from the nine ORs, even if just one from French Guiana, one from Saint Martin and one from Mayotte (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

The TWG3 Members are mainly affiliated to Universities (12), followed by R&D Institutions (8) and Public Administration (3). The TWG3 has a quite diverse representation in the private/entrepreneurship sector, considering the whole group, with representatives from SME's, Business Incubator/Innovation Center and Large Companies that contribute with a diverse vision of the thematic (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Most of the registered members declare to have a "high level" to a "very high level" in writing proposal (63%), a "high level" to a "very high level" in international R&I networking (51%) and a "high level" to a "very high level" in participation in EU-FP funding programs (40%) lower to the number of members which declare a "low level" to a "very low level" (60%) (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

As indicated before, TWG3 has an unbalanced gender distribution with 14% of females for 86% of males. This unbalance was described by Wilson et al. in 2016¹¹, and is related to the Earth and universe sciences.

This diverse composition of members leads to an Action Plan in which everyone could identify their vision and needs. It was a challenge, but the Sub-coordinator was conscious and, therefore, we have applied a diverse methodology that integrated everyone and promoted online and offline participation (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Introduction of the action plan

The co-creation phase of the action plan was conducted in respect of the Guidelines (FORWARD-ITC, 2020) during three workshops held after the kick-off meeting, mixing online and offline activities.

The Action Plan orientation/guidelines to take into account by the TWG3 when defining the actions/tasks for its implementation are the following:

- ✓ Adapt the goal to apply to specific measures that can be verified and measured;
- ✓ Have in mind that the group has only twelve (12) months to implement (target short, medium and long time actions and their articulation in time), within and beyond the FORWARD project;
- ✓ Actions must be attained through the joint forces of the TWG3 members: much more can be achieved by collaboration than competition;
- ✓ Make full use of the potential and resources that the TWG3 members have together, in terms of capacity sharing, networking, experience and knowledge;
- ✓ Empower the group by strengthening the collaboration between the members, the TWG's and other networks that you can identify as relevant to the TWG3 goals.

These guidelines helped TWG3 to keep focused on goals and define, together, actions that were possible to implement taking into account that this is a non-financed group of volunteer experts. This was also a chance to think “out of the box” and focus the actions definition solely on the added value of the expertise and joint knowledge that the TWG3 can have. It has also been a challenge, along the process, to keep the members engaged by solely appealing to a common recognition of the importance and advantages of participating in the TWG. Therefore, it was important and still is important to reinforce along the Workshop and activities to integrate in the AP the advantages of the network opportunities, mutual creation

¹¹ https://www.americangeosciences.org/sites/default/files/ExitSurvey_2016_final_0.pdf

of sources of information that can be of an added value for its members and knowledge transfer, which that can bring, as well, exchange of experiences in FP (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Presentation of the action plan

Within the framework of increasing OR participation on coming European FP funding opportunities, the Action Plan focuses on specific actions in two main lines: 1) enabling Strategic Positioning of the ORs by defining common agendas and priorities, identifying synergies and better coordinate OR interest representation in the EC and 2) Build Capacity by stimulating OR organizations to lead projects and increase networking efforts in areas that build upon existing capacity while carrying consultation between industry and public entities.

This Action Plan was developed based on the joint vision of the partners involved in this TWG and translated into actions considered as main priorities that can lead to an increase of the OR participation on coming European FP funding opportunities. These actions are a result of the common understanding of what is considered as strengths of weaknesses common to the OR in the topic of Earth Science, Space and Universe.

Vision on Action Plan and closure notes

Vision of the TWG3 for the coming decade is to monitor and decisively contribute to reach the UN sustainable development goals, summarized in three main global challenges: climate change, digital transformation and population dynamics. This should be done through an international, distributed and collaborative network and contribute to foster job creation and knowledge driven economic development based on scientific excellence. To do so, ORs should explore its strengths, such as those associated with its geographic location, the recognition as living labs, existing operational monitoring infrastructures, qualified human resources and proximity between I&D sector (Public and Private), the Public Administration, Private Sector and further relevant stakeholders (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

The FP funding opportunities are excellent tools to bring together experts from different parts of the world that share the same vision and that are willing to work together in order to contribute to the UN sustainable development goals. However, sometimes these collaborations are not maintained beyond the duration of an action/project and are not explored in other areas. Also, in some cases the institutions are not open to new collaborations

with different partners. For all the reasons described above, this TWG believes that only joining, strengthening and creating new efforts through scientific collaborations between the ORs can lead to a wider vision of what is needed and can be developed for tackling the three main global challenges.

The list of actions

The actions list if the Thematic Action plan of the TWG3 is presented below. Only the columns: Action; Details, Date, Resource and Expected outcome are presented.

This action plan is based on three goals, with seven sub-objectives and 18 actions. The actions are planned to start soon.

Table 11 List of actions of the Action Plan of the thematic working group 3 : Earth system, on space and Universe Sciences

EU Commission Lobby					
Activity 1.1 Accessing the possibility of a Brussels representation of the OR's to aggregate the technical/scientific needs and capacities of the regions to the EC		April to September 2021			
Task 1.1.1 Gather Interests inside and outside of the TWG	Online questionnaire to verify the interest of OR's scientific community	April to September 2021	Google forms	Online questionnaire	Planned
Task 1.1.2 Definition of objectives	Online Meeting to define the typology of this entity and compromise from all parties	April to October 2021	Microsoft Teams	List of objectives	Planned
Task 1.1.3 Regular communication via mailing list with monthly info of Horizon Europe opportunities		April to October 2021 onwards	Mailing list	Monthly emails	Planned
Activity 1.2 Recognize islands as Living Labs					
Task 1.2.1 Definition of Statement	Meeting	April to May 2021	Microsoft Teams	Document	Planned
Task 1.2.2 EU Communication	Meeting to formalize the statement	May 2021	Microsoft Teams	Document finalized	Planned
Task 1.2.3 Submission of the document to the EU commission	Email	May 2021	Mailing list	Document submitted	Planned
Activity 1.3 Management of the Action Plan					
Task 1.3.1. Coordination meetings to follow-up and manage the proposed actions	Meeting	April to October 2021	Microsoft Teams	Minutes of Meeting	Planned
Cooperation between OR's Institutions					
Activity 2.1 Common Scientific Agendas Definition					
Task 2.1.1 Identifying R&D&I profiles (Research Groups belonging to partner organizations or in direct contact)	Online form to define the interests of the various entities concerning the Earth, Space and Universe Science	May 2021	Google forms	Online form	Planned
Task 2.1.2 Identify areas where intersection of business, scientific, and defence can coexist by means of dedicated informal meeting	Definition of online form to be completed by, at least, one institution per OR.	June to August 2021	Google forms	Completed forms	Planned
Task 2.1.3 "Matchmaking" event	Online meeting to present the results, propose synergies and possible common scientific agendas	September-21	Microsoft Teams	Results report	Planned
Activity 2.2 Stimulate OR institutions to lead projects and take advantage of the installed capacity					
		April to October 2021			Planned

Task 2.2.1 Identification of EU programs and calls	Compile the most interesting calls from Horizon Europe (responsible)	April 2021	Horizon Europe Website	Document compiling the most interesting calls	Planned
Task 2.2.2 Identification of proposal writing training opportunities	Presentation and brainstorm on the achieved results (online meeting)	May 2021	Microsoft Teams	List of common interest calls	Planned
Task 2.2.3 Identification of priority areas of interest to push funding for OR's	Creation of possible consortiums	May to October 2021	Microsoft Teams	Definition of project proposals	Planned
Task 2.2.4 Organise dedicated meetings with other TWG to identify potential synergies for collaboration	Refine and compile the most interesting calls from Horizon Europe (responsible)	April to June 2021	Microsoft Teams	Definition of project proposals	Planned
Activity 2.3 Consultation with industry and public entities to identify synergies within existing and future infrastructures (across ORs)		April to October 2021			
Task 2.3.1 Contact major entities outside scientific ecosystem with possible interest in TWG3 areas	bilateral meetings/emails	April to June 2021	Mailing list	See task 2.3.3	Planned
Task 2.3.2 List major interests and players	Compile results	June 2021/September 2021		See task 2.3.3	Planned
Task 2.3.3 Opportunities event	Online event	October 2021	Microsoft Teams / Zoom	Results report	Planned
Activity 2.4 Management of the Action Plan					
Task 2.4.1. Coordination meetings to follow-up and manage the proposed actions	Meeting	April to October 2021	Microsoft Teams	Minutes of Meeting	Planned

TWG4 Action Plan

TWG4 : Information and Communication Technologies

This section only presents an introduction of the action plan, the full version is available in the Annex I - TWG4 (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Sub-coordinator: Pr Martine COLLARD (University Antilles)

Deputy: Dr Wilfried SEGRETIER (University Antilles)

Facilitator: Antony NOBOUR (CTM), Jean-François DORVILLE (Synergîle)

Number of registered members: 49

Number of women: 15 (32%), **number of men:** 32 (68%)

Estimated active members: 25

Profile of the members

The profiles of the members of the Thematic Working Group IV Information and Communications Technology is mainly academic 40%, 24% come from SME, 7% from public administration the rest come from social society and NGO.

Most of the members, 70% come from Madeira, Canary Islands, and the Azores. Mayotte is the only OR without a representative.

The TWG4 self-evaluated their level in proposal writing as a “high level” to a “very high level”, their international R&I networking as an “average level” to a “high level”, and their experience as a “low level” to an “average level” (Figure 7). Most of the members estimated their level as high in the proposal writing skill and international R&I networking (>40%). The level in participation of EU-FP programmes is for more members (>50%) as high to very high (Table 7).

The gender balance of the 49 registered members is unbalanced with 32% of females and 68% of males. This value is higher than the EU percentage of females studying in the Information and Communications Technology field, around 18% in 2018¹².

¹² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/EDN-20200423-1>

ITC in EU-FP programmes

44 H2020 projects have been identified with ORs members mainly coming from Canary Islands and Madeira. The important point is Small and Medium Enterprises are leaders in EU-FP funding projects in the thematic with 10 SMEs involved in 32 H2020 projects.

The members have declared 60 peer review papers, 12 software, 2 patterns, 16 Master / PhD, and 18 projects during the last five years.

During the phase of co-creation, the number of members increases from 35 to 49 which allows ensuring participants during the meeting higher than 18. The number of active members (answering emails and participating in the meetings) has been evaluated to 25 persons.

Potential areas in ICT were evaluated by survey and the members proposed Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, Big Data, and Machine Learning as areas of innovation of the ORs. The innovative solutions have also been sorted and placed first Smart Cities followed by Health, Tourism, Education, Energy transition, and Climate and Weather.

Scheduling of the co-creation phase

As suggested, after the Kick-off meeting it was organized four workshops and we had to hold an additional workshop to define a final action plan (FORWARD-Synergile, 2021).

- **On Tuesday January 12th 2021 - Kick-Off Meeting**, the session was spent in a round table discussion and presentation of the method.
- **On Tuesday January 19th 2021 - Workshop 1**, the session was spent in a discussion on three preliminary objectives.
- **On Tuesday January 26th 2021 - Workshop 2**, the session was spent in brainstorming to determine more precisely specific objectives and actions to achieve them.
- **On Tuesday February 2nd 2021 - Workshop 3**, the session was spent in analyzing the result of the survey conducted into the group to organize future actions according to four sub-objective branches
- **On Tuesday February 9th 2021: Workshop 4**, the session was spent in defining actions for each branch.
- **On Tuesday February 23rd 2021: Workshop 5** the session was spent in analyzing the result of the survey conducted into the group in sub-groups and in defining the final action plan.

Presentation of the Action Plan

The Action Plan of the TWG4 was validated with two (2) sub-objectives and four (4) main actions after a partial respect of the Guideline (FORWARD-ITC, 2020) and five dedicated workshops (FORWARD-Synergile, 2021).

Two sub-objectives

1. Rise our capacity of Designing an innovative ICT framework as a generic top layer

applicable to several application areas;

Main actions:

- Building a precise map of our areas of expertise in ICT - Skills, Complementary points
- Listing application domains addressed in our applied researches and regions

2. Rise our capacity of Designing ICT tools required for an innovative solution in some given application domains.

Main actions:

- Evaluating relevant ICT application domains in ORs
- Collecting requirements in ICT tools per key domain

The two actions to achieve Objective #1 will be conducted by a first sub-group. The two last actions will be applied in other seven (1) sub-groups to allow discussion between ORs experts in a transdisciplinary way (hosting member of other TWGs, which is critical transversal action to be ensured in the implementation phase)

1. SMART CITIES and TOURISM
2. e-SERVICES
3. AI AND DATA SCIENCE
4. CYBERSECURITY
5. ENVIRONMENTAL AND NATURAL RESOURCE SECURITY / NATURAL HAZARDS
6. HEALTHCARE DELIVERY SYSTEMS / ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH
7. OCEAN and CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

The list of actions

The actions list of the Thematic Action plan of the TWG4 is presented below. Only the columns: Action; Details, Date, Resource and Expected outcome are presented.

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme
of the European Union

This action plan is based on two objectives, with the main four sub-objectives and nine actions that were defined. The two main actions started at the end of March 2021, three sub-groups also started the four others will be launched since the critical mass will be met.

Table 12 List of actions of the Action Plan of the thematic working group 4 : Information and Communication Technologies

Action	Details	Venue	Start	End	Resources	Expected outcomes
To reach the Objective 1: Rise our capacity of Designing an innovative ICT framework as a generic top layer applicable to several application areas						
1.1 Building a precise map of our areas of expertise in ICT - Skills, Complementary points - Do we have to complete them?	The resulting maps should be evolutive, interactive and help to find partners to answer calls. The map should include connections between entities	Online mainly with one workshop on site if possible	MARCH 2021	NOVEMBER 2021	5 persons/month for a development engineer	Web platform able to display the map of expertise area and management and manage underlying data
1.2 Listing application domains addressed in our applied researches and regions?		Online mainly with one workshop on site if possible	MARCH 2021	NOVEMBER 2021		Additional layer on the web platform enabling to display the application domains
To reach the Objective 2: Rise our capacity of Designing ICT tools required for an innovative solution in some given application domains						
2.1 Evaluating relevant ICT application domains in ORs	These two actions will be conducted into 7 sub-groups with contact person in each sub-group					
2.2 Collecting requirements in ICT tools per key domain						

Subgroups						
SMART CITIES and TOURISM	Sub-groups should - Carry out a detailed survey inside the TWG on potential OR application domains - Identify professionals in our ORs - Identify innovative IC tools already implemented in our ORs - Conduct a discussion with other TWGs concerned - Make sure to be consistent with OR specificities	Online mostly with one workshop on site if possible	MARCH 2021	NOVEMBER 2021		Short summary based on a common model showing the opportunities of research in the domain
e-SERVICES			MARCH 2021	NOVEMBER 2021		Short summary based on a common model showing the opportunities of research in the domain
AI AND DATA SCIENCE			MARCH 2021	NOVEMBER 2021		Short summary based on a common model showing the opportunities of research in the domain
CYBERSECURITY			The sub-groups do not currently have enough members to be able to decide on a schedule.	Short summary based on a common model showing the opportunities of research in the domain		
ENVIRONMENTAL AND NATURAL RESOURCE SECURITY / NATURAL HAZARDS				Short summary based on a common model showing the		

				opportunities of research in the domain
HEALTHCARE DELIVERY SYSTEMS / ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH				Short summary based on a common model showing the opportunities of research in the domain
OCEAN and CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT				Short summary based on a common model showing the opportunities of research in the domain

TWG5 Action Plan

TWG5 : Climate Change and Energy Transition

This section only presents an introduction of the action plan, the full version is available in the Annex I - TWG5 (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Sub-coordinator: Claudio Mantero (Horários do Funchal)

Deputy: Filipe Oliveira (AREAM)

Facilitator: Lúcio QUINTAL (ARDITI)

Number of registered members: 69

Number of women: 19 (29%), **number of men:** 46 (71%)

Estimated active members: 35

Profile of the members

More than 60 persons are involved in Thematic Group 5 (TWG5) from the nine (9) ORs, a number that will grow throughout 2021 and in the following years as the different Horizon Europe project calls are launched (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021). The number of active members is around 50%.

Most of the members are from Universities (near 50%), followed by Private (SME/Large Company), Public Administration and R&D Institutions. According to the registration form data, **58%** of the members have **Energy** as their main field(s) of activity / research and **42%** fit in **Climate**. If we consider the feedback from active members (those who answered the feedback form are about 50% of the members) then that relation will become **73%** in **Energy** and **27%** in **Climate**.

The most represented ORs are Canarias and Madeira (>30), followed by Guadeloupe, La Réunion, the Azores and Martinique (>20) and the less represented regions are Saint Martin, Mayotte and French Guiana (10) (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

71% of the members are males and 29% are females, the unbalance is in the low values of the TWGs. Most of the TWGs have a percentage of females included between 35% and 52% (Table 7).

The proposal writing skills are self-evaluated by the member between an “average level” to a “high level”, with 45% who declared to have a “high level” and 11% to have a “very high level” (Table 7). The international R&I networking is self-evaluated above the “average level” with more than 50% of the members declared to have a “high level” to a “very high level”. The experience in EU-FP programmes is lower than the two first but half of the members have a positive appreciation, a “high level” to a “very high level”.

Fields of expertise and research interests

This analysis results from the information provided in the registration form (49 answers), together with the information later provided in the KoM feedback form (26 answers).

- For ENERGY (B-Sustainable Energy and Mobility) keywords were: Sustainable Energy Systems, Energy Management and Efficiency, Energy Transition; Digital transformation of the energy sector and Mobility and Transport.
- For CLIMATE (A-Earth Systems Knowledge and Adaptation): Climate Change, Environmental Law, Policy, Risk and vulnerability, Waste Management, Marine Ecology, Geospatial and volcanology.

Representativity of the thematic in EU-H2020

WP2 analysis on the CORDIS database (FORWARD-Nexa, 2020) identified 44 H2020 projects dealing with Climate Change & Energy transition with ORs members. Seven (7) of them were coordinated by ORs from six H2020 projects coordinated by SMEs bases in the ORs for an amount received of 1.834 million of euros. 13.26 million euros were received in the thematic in ORs. Canarias is the ORs leader with 30 H2020 projects. The participation of the French ORs is very small (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Organisation of the thematic working group

The TWG5 uses tools proposed by the Guideline (FORWARD-ITC, 2020) as SWOT, How-How, etc. but makes the choice to follow its own schedule to face the time issues of the member.

Conclusions and discussion along the workshop allow proposing two sub-groups to ease the work between experts and with other TWG. The subgroup A- Climate, Earth Knowledge and Adaptation (CEKA) and subgroup B- Sustainable Energy and Mobility (SEM) will ease the participation with other TWG's such as TWG3 and TWG8 (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Non-disclosure agreement

All members implicitly agree that their participation in this thematic group is not intended to obtain information they could use elsewhere and, in that way, compromising or weakening the aims of the group. When working on the specific project proposal, members / participants will have to explicitly commit to not “leaking” information competing proposals outside the group. Signing a document of confidentiality reinforcing this non-disclosure objective shall be required.

Implementation of the Action Plan

Implementation of this Action Plan (AP) will start once it is complete and approved by TWG5 members, in March 2021, before Horizon Europe calls are officially published / open, in April 2021. Activities will follow the guidelines and steps presented in the document.

Envisaged types of activities during the implementation of the AP include:

- Consult, read and select HE Cluster 5 calls considering call calendar, ie, starting with the calls for 2021.
- Evaluate and rank the calls considering topic preferences and expertise/skills, regional and ORs relevance, etc, using proposed call evaluation matrix.
- Design and develop project ideas (completing a proposal factsheet).
- Contacting and joining potential partners for a project consortium (use partner identification form).
- Project proposal writing / development (extend proposal factsheet to fulfil call criteria).
- Proposal submission.

When joining existing consortia rather than creating our own, and depending on the expected role in the project, requirements and effort will differ.

The list of actions

The actions list if the Thematic Action plan of the TWG5 is presented below. Only the columns: Action; Details, Date, Resource and Expected outcome are presented.

This action plan is based on three goals, with main seven sub-objectives and 18 actions. The actions are planned to start soon.

Table 13 List of actions of the Action Plan of the thematic working group 5 : Climate Change and Energy Transition

Activity	Detail	Venue	Start-End	Resource	Outcomes
Final tables with the appraisal of the HE Cluster 5 calls made by the coordinators group			March 2021		
Presentation to the group of the action plan and the evaluated calls table as a working tools (3 rd workshop/meeting)			March 2021		
Each member selects twelves (12) calls: six (6) calls with highest interest and six (6) second best calls from the list (4 th workshop/meeting)					
Based on the results, (sub)groups will be defined to proceed with the common draft proposal preparation using the templates already provided (5 th workshop/meeting)			April-May 2021		
Improvement and approval of long term cooperation model (6 th workshop/meeting)			April-June 2021		
Preparation of at least two common proposal project involving ORs (6 th / 7 th workshop/meeting)			June 2021 – June 2022		

Long term cooperation model for TWGs

Full implementation and long-term activities of the Forward Climate change and Energy Transition action plan requires dedicated sustainable transversal support actions. Similarly to what is proposed by TWG2, in TWG5 it will be based on volunteering, starting with the definition of a group's coordination system which ensures members' adhesion, commitment and sharing of responsibilities. Two main options are proposed for analysis and approval, which may be adapted, adopted or merged. As transversal support actions it is desirable that it becomes defined and implemented at consortium level horizontally to all 8 TWGs / ORs.

Option i - COST Actions Management System

Adoption of COST¹³ Actions Management System will ensure alignment with European standards in collaborative research management and ORs researchers receiving knowledge

¹³ https://www.cost.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/COST-013-19-Guidelines_Action_management_monitoring_assessment_Ver2019.06.pdf

on promising tools. As proposed by TWG2, the management structure could be set up as follows:

- A management committee (MC), composed of 1 representative per OR and in charge of :
 - defining the group's strategy, policy, rules and memberships
 - defining the working groups and composition
 - performing the monitoring and reporting duties
- Working groups (WG), composed of all interested members, in charge of performing the tasks required in the action plan and led by voluntary leader and vice-leader, responsible for coordinating and managing actions assigned to the WG:
 - WG 1 - Mobilize Climate, Energy and Mobility to understand and boost R&I in ORs
 - WG 2 - Build critical masses (including NGO) on targeted R&I fields to contribute to the European Research Area
 - WG 3 - FP incubator
- Thematic committees (action 5 in TWG2) composed of all interested members and led by voluntary by voluntary leader and vice-leader
- A general assembly which brings together all members to share the group's progress and achievements

Option ii - Forward Common strategy for institutional cooperation & common governance in ORs

As of March 2021 the common strategy is still being developed under Task 6.2 (WP6) of the Forward project and as thus is not closed yet but it provides already a base model mapped from the resulting work of RIS3_Net projects¹⁴ (1 and 2) plus Forward managing structure and TWGs. As proposed for discussion and approval under Forward task T6.2, the common

¹⁴ <https://www.ris3-net.eu/>

governance is as presented in the next table. TWGs management structure can be included in such models as part of the global ORs cooperation.

Table 14 Common Governance for ORs (initial proposal under T6.2)

Management Structure	Members	Functions
Steering Committee	9 members; President assigned every year, rotating between ORs; Political or R&I entity representatives of at least one member institution of each OR; Annual in person meetings;	Evaluate the R&I Strategy for ORs; Review the compliance of high – level goals; Set up goals and high level control activities; Serve as a liaison with The EC supporting decisions approved from a political and institutional perspective for ORs; Supervise the Management Team;
Management Team	3 members; Rotation: annually; Representatives from Regional R&I entities (ARDITI, ACIISI, FRCT, NEXA, CTG, GUA, MART, StMart, MAY); Annual in person meetings; Quarterly videoconference meetings;	Coordinate Thematic Groups; Promote consensus among the ORs; Implement the actions of the Common Strategy for ORs; Send proposals to the Steering Group for review and evaluation of the Common Strategy for ORs; Prepare Strategy implementation reports
Coordinators	9 members, 1 for each Thematic Group; Rotation: annually; Must be a Thematic Specialist; Videoconference meetings between coordinators every 6 months;	Manage Thematic Group; Maintain stakeholder engagement; Communicate results;

TWG6 Action Plan

TWG6 : Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering

This section only presents an introduction of the action plan, the full version is available in the Annex I - TWG6 (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Sub-coordinator : Jean-Christophe BAMBOU (INRAe)

Deputy: Jean-Luc GOURDINE (INRAE)

Facilitator: Emyly GUYON (Synergîle), Jean-François DORVILLE (Synergîle)

Number of registered members: 57

Number of women: 24 (41%), **number of men:** 35 (59%)

Estimated active members: 26

Profile of the members

The members of the thematic working group are in majority located in the Canary Islands (42%) and Madeira (15%). The other outermost regions are quite equally represented with three to five members. Mayotte does not have a representative in the TWG6.

The members are from the academic field (62%) for the majority, followed by public companies and institutes (15%) and SMEs (11%).

The TWG6 is quite balanced in gender with 41% of females and 59% of males on the 57 registered persons (Table 7). That difference is in the European standards, where 41% of females are working in the science and technology field.

The keywords used by TWG6 members to describe their activities in the profiling file are not homogenous without a clear trend. The more used keywords are Water, Environment, Natural, Sustainable, Bio-technology, Soil and Health.

Performance of ORs in EU FP funding for agriculture and biotechnology

A total of 25 projects were identified in the H2020 Framework Programme for the Research and Innovation involving the Outermost Regions and Agriculture, applied life sciences,

biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering theme, with two (2) for Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action and one (1) for an infrastructure project.

On the 25 projects, no ORs leads a project despite two (2) single participants. Seven projects were in relation to at least a SME.

Scheduling and progression of the discussions throughout the meetings

The initial planning of four (4) meetings to co-create the action plan was not followed. The methodology proposed (i.e., SWOT analysis, SMART Objective, How-How diagram) were a bit far from the usual practices of the members and the first discussion allows to perform rounder tables and more straight exchange between the members. This step was necessary to allow the members to get to know each other and begin to build the trust necessary for meaningful collaborations.

The planning was finally the following one:

- **January 14th Kick-off Meeting:** Individual presentation of each member present (the absence and new ones got the opportunity to give a 4 min introduction talk at the beginning of the following meetings)
- **January 21st 2021 Workshop #1 Define the Specific Objectives:** selection of three specific objectives
 - Design the future of ORs Agriculture and Aquaculture, sustainable and respectful of the environment
 - Inventory, map and promote bio-product endemic of the ORs to ease innovation in Health, Bio-material production and Energy
 - Make biological analysis capacity in the ORs an ace to face current and future threats (i.e., Climate Change, disease)
- **January 28st 2021 Workshop #2 Brainstorming to determine Actions to achieve the Specific Objectives:** decision to redefine the three initial specific objectives in two, more adapted for the nature of the group
 - Agro-Ecology renamed “**Agro-System**” after discussion
 - One Health concept

- **February 4th, 2021 Workshop #3 Brainstorming 2 to determine the Specific Objectives and the associated actions:** work to define list of actions related to the first specific objective of the group Agro-Ecology (using tree diagram)
- **February 11th, 2021 Workshop #4 Brainstorming 3 to determine Specific Objectives and the associated actions:** work to define list of actions related to the first specific objectives of the group “One Health Approach” (using tree diagram)
- **February 25th, 2021 Workshop #5 Draft and validation of the Thematic Action Plan:** Based on the previous meeting the TWG validate the two sub-objectives and (see the list below)
 - 14 actions in Agro-system sub-objectives and sub-group
 - 12 actions on One Health sub-objectives and sub-group

After further discussion, three other actions were added to offer full opportunity to develop true synergies between the ORs.

List of the actions

The main goal of the TWG6 is to create an active network with the capacity to address the future challenges of our regions in a relevant manner. The actions selected as a thematic action plan by the TWG6 will firstly allow the creation of exchange (i.e., ideas, data, practice) and synergies between the stakeholder in Research-Development-Innovation and agro-production and secondly makes available information, bibliography, and methodologies for future projects in research and innovation. We collectively identified the need to perform a new member recruitment campaign in ORs for stakeholder and human sciences persons). Those actions are directly related to the Green Deal strategies and to the circular economy principle.

The actions identified are included in two classes the **Agro-system** and the **One health concept** with two aspects the Biotic and the Abiotic approach. They are detailed in the table below.

Organization of the group

The thematic working group will meet at least once per month. The action will be facilitated by two or three members ready to be involved in that action as leader of the sub-group. If a sub-group does not have enough participants to conduct action or does not have a sufficient diversity of ORs a recruitment campaign will be launched. The activities of the sub-group will

be frozen until the number of minimum members defined by the TWG 6 will be reached (more than five members from three different ORs).

The list of actions

The actions list if the Thematic Action plan of the TWG6 is presented below. Only the columns: Action; Details, Date, Resource and Expected outcome are presented.

This action plan is based on two objectives, with four sub-objectives and 26 actions have been defined. The two main actions will start at the end of April 2021 (recruitment of new members and inventory of numerical data available).

Table 15 List of actions of the Action Plan of thematic working group 6 : Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering

Action	Details	Venue	Start	End	Resources	Expected outcomes
New member recruitment campaign in ORs (stakeholder and human science person)	Ease the recruitment of new members to allow the sustainability of the TWG and answer to specific needs of information or actors		March 2021	September 2021	must be determined	List of new member and flyer of presentation of the TWG6
Objective 1 : Agro-system						
Series of colloquium on Agro-system in ORs	Scientific presentations on themes related to the FP-EU Calls	Online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Series of recorded conferences and/or webinars
Development of organic alternatives to agrochemical for new bio-protectant, soil carbon sequestration, soil health and productivity	Use of agricultural residues, by-products, or non-traditional bioresources: propose a methodology	Online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report+ Opinion and review papers
Monitoring water availability in ORs for agro-system	an initial Inventory of the volume available and their location, plus a semi-annual update	Online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report and quarterly update
Bio-monitoring of water quality in ORs	Selection of the Bio-indicator, initial evaluation, and their location plus a semi-annual update	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report and semi-annual update
Digital data availability in ORs	Inventory of the numerical data available (location, format, and quality)	online	March 2021	August 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report
Increase adoption and implementation of agroecological principles at the farmer level	design actions (flyer, conference, etc) and implement them		March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	synthetic reports, recorder webinar and communication supports + Opinion and/ot Review papers
Farm to fork: setting future sustainable relationship of stakeholders in food production system at ORs	Link stakeholders across the food production system and supply chain to determine best actions to adapt the crops, the livestock production, and the agro-systems to the future constraints,	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	synthetic report and planning of actions and possibly a scientific paper.

	but also the use and the reuse of waste and by-products.					
Monitoring the use of agrochemicals in ORs	an initial inventory type and the volume of agrochemical used, (if it is possible the location of usage) plus annual update	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report and semi-annual update
Monitoring and biomonitoring contaminants and other elements in soil ecosystems of ORs	Inventory of the contaminant and other element in the soil using chemical and biological data, plus yearly update	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report and annual update
Setting up of an Innovative surveillance strategy for ORs (Pathogen/Pest anticipate emergence of the new diseases)	determine the best package of processes to monitor new diseases	online	June 2021	December 2021	must be determined	synthetic report
Farmers and exploitations (income and activities)	monitoring of the incomes and the activities of the farmer and exploitations in the ORS	online	June 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report and annual update
Assess the promotion of food production systems based on smart adaptations	determine how good the promotion of ORs food production is good or not, and to propose solutions to improve it	online	June 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report
Carbon neutrality (Carbon production), the Life cycle in ORs	evaluation of the carbon neutrality in the ORs based on full life cycle analysis	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report and annual update
Assess the sustainability of ORs agro-systems	propose a methodology of evaluation and applied it for the sustainability of each Ors	online	June 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report
Assessment of the downscaling potential of aquaculture in ORs (join actions between agriculture and aquaculture, in collaboration with the TWG8)	assess aquaculture potential in ORs for several scale from micro to medium size	online	June 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report
Monitoring biodiversity in agroecosystems	propose and implement a methodology to allow the monitoring of the biodiversity in each ORs in relation to agro-ecosystems	online	June 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report and annual update
Objective 2: One Health Approach						

Series of colloquium on One Health approach in Ors	scientific presentations on themes related to the FP-EU Calls	Online	March 2021	December 2021		Series of recorded conferences+webinar
Sub-objective 2.1 Biotic drivers						
Monitoring of new threats: Emergence / unknow diseases / pests	Propose an adapted methodology to monitor defined threats and implement it	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report and annual update
Inventory of the Usage of local product	Inventory of product and their usage in the ORs, proposed methodology to determine the usage at the ORs scale	online	March 2021	September 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report
Assessing the relations between 'endemic' symptoms and diseases to contribute to the improvement of human health in ORs	propose a methodology and assess the relation between symptom and diseases	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report
Determine the ecotoxicological impacts of antimicrobial resistance in agroecosystems	propose a methodology and determine the impact for the selected products	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report
Phytotherapy (Evaluation of biological activity of products form endemic and native (plants) species	Inventory of the used plants in ORs and propose a methodology to evaluate their biological activity	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report
Development of vaccines	co-creation of action plan to develop vaccines usable in each Ors	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report
Sub-objectives 2.2 Abiotic drivers						
Training of farmers, general population and schools for the importance of soil and water conservation	disseminate new and relevant information for soil and water conservation	online & presentation in each Ors	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report, record of training and presentation documents
Financially support scientific research to develop more biological solutions	find resource to allow the build of consortium or working group through ORs	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report & action plan
Establishing safety limits of elemental content for agricultural soils in ORs (many are volcanic, and naturally enriched with several elements)	Determine limits can be implemented in ORs to protect the soil health, production quality, and the consumer	online	March 2021	September 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report

Geochemical background of soils and soil fertility	assessment and inventory of geochemical information of soil available for ORs	Online	September 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report
Composting or vermicomposting practice for the population	Training of population through webinar and Flyer to disseminate new and relevant information	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report, record of training and presentation documents
Inspection of the industries as well as the obligation of these industries to carry out environmental cleaning and reforestation actions for example	assess and monitor actions of industry in environment management and all process of	online	March 2021	December 2021	must be determined	Synthetic report and annual update

TWG7 Action Plan

TWG7 : Biodiversity conservation and restoration

This section only presents an introduction of the action plan, the full version is available in the Annex I - TWG7 (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Sub-coordinator: Prof. Paulo Borges (University of Azores)

Deputy: Mário Boieiro (University of Azores)

Facilitator: Nuno Vasconcelos (UAc), Lina Silveira (Regional Fund for Science and Technology (regional Government of the Azores)), and Carolina Parelho (Regional Fund for Science and Technology (regional Government of the Azores))

Number of registered members: 61

Number of women: 22 (35%), **number of men:** 41 (65%)

Estimated active members: 30

Profile of the members

TWG7 is a heterogeneous group by integrating OR experts and representatives from different fields of expertise and differentiated academic and professional backgrounds. A main challenge faced was to bring people together and find common interest in proposing and discussing the activities that include the Action Plan, and for this reason, it was important to understand the composition of this TWG, as well as its evolution to keep optimal working conditions and sustainable engagement (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

The demography of the TWG7 changed along the participation process and in March 2021 the group increased its numbers of enrolled members, from 48 to 61 (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021). The OR contributing with more members remained the Canary Islands, with 20 Members, however Azores almost doubled the number of members, now with 11, the same number as Madeira island. La Réunion remained with the same number, as well as Martinique and Saint Martin. No representatives of Mayotte joined the TWG.

Most members of TWG7 still have as main affiliation the Universities. More than half the members declared to be affiliated to Universities (41 in a total of 61 members) followed by Public administration (8) and R&I Institutions. The growth of the group has also given a wider diversity of affiliations (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

The gender distribution is unbalanced with 35% of females for 65% of males. The ratio is lower than the 41% of females who are working in the science and technology field in Europe¹⁵.

The self-evaluation of the members shows that they estimated their experience in EU-FP programmes at a “very low level” to a “low level”, 63.5% of them declared that (22% declared a “very low level”). The skills in proposal writing and international R&I networking is better with fewer members who declared “very low level”, 14% (Table 7), but are low compared to the other TWGs (Figure 7).

Co-creation of the Action Plan

The methodology implemented during the co-construction of the Action Plan followed a logic of online work, during the three Workshops organized. These Workshops were working meetings and a start point to launch the second stage of offline work, to be more inclusive and allow that every member has the opportunity to collaborate (FORWARD-Synergîe, 2021).

The methodology applied follows the guidelines (FORWARD-ITC, 2020) but with an adapted timeline. This methodology also had a logic guided by a main question:

How can the TWG7 contribute to increase the participation of the OR's in the Framework Programme - Horizon Europe (2021-2027)?

As a guiding point to propose and develop actions to integrate in the TWG7 Action Plan.

The Action Plan explained

The Natural Legacy of Outermost Regions (ORs) has an outstanding value, including extraordinary landscapes and ecosystems, high numbers of endemic taxa and unique evolutionary lineages, and contribute significantly to regional and national economies (via services provided to agroforestry, fisheries, tourism) and to human/social well-being (aesthetic services). However, some human activities in ORs have (directly and/or indirectly) threatened biodiversity and the services it provides reinforcing the need to adopt a rational and multidisciplinary approach to natural resources management jointly with the pressing need to develop biodiversity restoration initiatives. Current key biodiversity erosion processes include habitat fragmentation and degradation, invasive species spread, pollution and climatic

¹⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/fr/web/products-eurostat-news/-/edn-20200210-2>

changes, some of them acting in synergy and promoting species extinctions (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Despite the acknowledged importance of Biodiversity Conservation and Restoration in ORs at regional, national and European-levels this thematic has not been a priority for research and innovation in ORs, and this has also been hindered by the intrinsic factors associated to ORs (*e.g.*, geographic isolation, low human resources, low funding) that pose strong limitations for a more active and competitive participation of ORs in European Union funding opportunities. There are several examples of successful research and innovation projects, coordinated or with the participation of regional entities from the ORs, but these illustrate the unbalanced participation of ORs in European Union funding frameworks and the lack of joint proposals from the ORs addressing key topics of general and common concern (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

This Action Plan follows the structure adopted during the discussion meetings of our group, where three subgroups addressing specific topics have been formed. The main topics analyzed were: Promote, monitor and value the biodiversity of ORs; Natural resources management and the need to protect/restore biodiversity; Capacity building – setting tools to improve communication and increase competitiveness. The actions and tasks proposed by team members were firstly discussed in each subgroup (January 2021), then presented to all team members and analyzed during an offline working period and later discussed with more detail in a general meeting (February 2021).

- A major objective of our Action Plan is to promote the unique biodiversity of ORs to key stakeholders, which we aim to achieve by identifying specific institutions and organizations in Europe and elsewhere interested in this thematic. In a second stage, we will promote the organization of open days in selected institutions of ORs.

- Long-term biodiversity monitoring in ORs is also a crucial objective of our Action Plan and will include a few more specific goals. The general goal is to monitor biodiversity change in ORs and identify its main drivers to fuel more effective conservation measures based on sound science. Several actions will contribute to this objective (and similar ones), namely the identification of in-place long-term monitoring programs, selection of efficient and effective

biodiversity indicators, identification of taxonomic experts and institutions targeting biodiversity research and housing specimen collections.

- The management of natural resources and associated conflicts with biodiversity conservation was also set as an important objective and several actions have been proposed on this topic. First, it will be necessary to identify the different risks to biodiversity in the ORs and list the key actors on this topic and their expertise. Secondly, this multidisciplinary topic will benefit from close interaction with other TWGs, particularly TWG1, TWG5, TWG6 and TWG8. Lastly, it will be important to identify calls targeting this area, where joint proposals can be prepared (FORWARD-Synergile, 2021).

The list of actions

The actions list of the Thematic Action plan of the TWG7 is presented below. Only the columns: Action; Details, Date, Resource and Expected outcome are presented.

This action plan is based on five (5) objectives, with main nine (9) sub-objectives and 39 actions have been defined. The actions are all planned and started in March. The actions are mainly offline work with data exchange. The meetings of the TWG7 are planned each two months.

Table 16 List of actions of the Action Plan of thematic working group 7 : Biodiversity conservation and restoration

Actions	Details/ Venue	Start/end	Resources	Expected results	Level of advancement
Kick-off Meeting with action/task coordinators	Online	mar/abr	Microsoft Teams	Networking	Planned
Natural resources management and the need to protect/restore biodiversity					Planned
Identify the most important risk factors (and eventual threats) driven by human activities to biodiversity in ORs		mar/jun2021			Planned
Establish a list of risk factors in ORs and their potential threat	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Create a list of key actors and their expertise	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Promote the incorporation of health and well-being surveillance as part of the biodiversity conservation and restoration monitoring, using the One Health approach.		mar/jun2021			Planned
Identify practitioners of the One Health approach in the ORs	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Identify One Health issues in the biodiversity conservation and restoration monitoring	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Identify calls on the HEU Program that can be targeted by the TWG7 group		mar/dez2021			Planned
List the calls and inform team members	Collaborative space	mar/dez2021	FW platform	List of events and email to TWG7	Planned
Organize webinar(s) with the other TWGs (particularly TWG1, TWG5, TWG6, TWG8) to reinforce capabilities to address this multidisciplinary topic and foster the preparation of calls in collaboration		mar/dez2021			Planned
Meetings with TWG sub-coordinators	Online	mar/dez2021	Microsoft Teams	Networking	Planned
Organize a webinar (with TWG6 group) on the interactions between biodiversity and agricultural systems and stress the importance to accommodate the One Health approach on the proposals submitted to HEU	Online	Sep/Oct2021	Microsoft Teams	Networking	Planned
Promote the biodiversity value of ORs for several key stakeholders					Planned
Elaborate a List of European Institutions interested in exploring the biodiversity in OR's, namely Island Biology Groups across continental Europe and others		mar/jun2021			Planned
Create a list of institutions (and contact person)	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Implement "Open day" events to raise awareness within the selected institutions		sept/oct2021			Planned
Organize "Open day"	Online	sept/oct2021	Microsoft Teams	Networking	Planned
Promote and disseminate (local and EC level) the ORs small regions, islands and archipelagos value as "living-labs", to predict the effects of global change on biodiversity, climate and land-use change, pollution, overexploitation, and biological invasions - ORs suitable to the downscaling of climate models to adequate levels					Planned

Elaborate a list of available “living-labs” in the ORs, with permanent plots available for further scientific work from external researchers (e.g. Bala, Terceira island).		mar/jun2021			Planned
Create a list of institutions (and contact person) doing long-term biodiversity monitoring	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Identify model organisms which could be used as research targets		mar/jun2021			Planned
Create a list of model organisms (and their references) used in biodiversity monitoring	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Monitoring- setting up long-term programs of mapping distribution and assessing abundance and distribution of key species and habitats (density/mortality rates; health status; density parameters)					Planned
Identify long term monitoring schemes in place, which are addressing biodiversity and environmental variables		mar/jun2021			Planned
Create a list of institutions (and contact person) doing long-term biodiversity monitoring	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Taxonomy - we need to strengthen the work on describing species diversity and maintaining reference collections					Planned
Identify the active working groups doing taxonomy research within Europe.		mar/jun2021			Planned
Create a list of experts and their field of expertise	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
List the reference institutions holding the key collections related to local OR’s biota.		mar/jun2021			Planned
Create a list of institutions (and contact person) housing biodiversity collections from ORs	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Promote the RED Listing of invertebrates in all ORs to allow future applications of LIFE projects at regional scale targeting invertebrates, namely land-snails and arthropods					Planned
Elaborate a Red Listing Training Webinar addressed to key personnel of the OR’s		mar/jun2021			Planned
Webinar organization	Online	mar/jun2021	Training materials	Capacity Building	Planned
List the reference institutions holding the key collections related to local OR’s biota.		mar/jun2021			Planned
Create a list of institutions (and contact person) housing biodiversity collections from Ors	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Create a network of ORs entities (Academic, scientific institutions, SMEs, citizens...) focusing on Biodiversity to act as a single point of contact with the European Commission - to join efforts to tackle the specificities of ORs through a single voice.					Planned
List of projects funded by the EC, focusing the Biodiversity, Conservation and Restoration topics in ORs		mar/jun2021			Planned
Create a list of projects and their contact person	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned

Identification of key Calls in The EU agenda for Biodiversity Conservation and Restoration		mar/dez2021			Planned
List the calls and inform team members	Collaborative space	mar/dez2021	FW platform	List of events and email to TWG7	Planned
Identification of EU Funding Schemes and increase the capture of EU funds, to better characterize and understand the Biodiversity status, trends and drivers in EU ORs, to better guide conservation strategies and management, and provide new opportunities for innovation		mar/dez2021			Planned
List the calls and inform team members	Collaborative space	mar/dez2021	FW platform	List of events and email to TWG7	Planned
Develop communication tools within the scientific community to reach the general public and promote excellence in science and it's public interest, and raise public awareness.					Planned
List of specific target groups in ORs for Biodiversity, conservation and restoration communication/consultation		mar/jun2021			Planned
Create a list of target groups	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Set or improve Online Biodiversity databases in ORs to manage, share and make public the Natural Legacy, Conservation activities and promote cooperation			Database		Planned
Compilation of existing online databases related to Biodiversity, conservation and restoration in each OR		mar/jun2021			Planned
Create a list of databases	Offline work	mar/jun2021	File template	List in Excel file	Planned
Follow-up Meetings with action/task coordinators	Online	may, set, nov	Microsoft Teams	Networking	Planned
General contact with the institutions/organizations dealing with Biodiversity conservation and restoration in ORs to gather new members	Online	may	FW platform		Planned
General meetings with TWG7 members	Online	june, Oct, Dez	Microsoft Teams	Networking	Planned

TWG8 Action Plan

TWG8 : Marine Science & technologies

This section only presents an introduction of the action plan, the full version is available in the Annex I - TWG8 (FORWARD-Synergile, 2021).

Sub-coordinator: Ricardo J Haroun Tabraue (University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria)

Deputy: Francisco Otero Ferrer (ABAS)

Facilitator: Almudena Suárez (FCPCT) and Noelia Díaz (FCPCT)

Number of registered members: 73

Number of women: 28 (38%), **number of men:** 46 (62%)

Estimated active members: 36

Profile of the members

The TWG8 is composed of more than 35% of Canary Islands members, followed by 16% of Madeira. Mayotte is the only not represented ORs member at this time.

The members come from for the main part from university (80%) and for local governments (18%). The TWG has SMEs and representatives of the Civil Society representatives.

The females are represented at a relatively good proportion 38% for 62% for the males. That value is close to the percentage of female who are working in science and technology in Europe, 41%¹⁶.

During the self-evaluation of the members, at their registration (Figure 7 & Table 7). The TWG8 members indicated a “low level” to an “average level” in proposal writing skills, with 10% indicated a “low level” and 10% “very high level”. The international R&I networking is above the “average level” with quite the same percentage of members who indicated a “low level” (32%) and a “high level” (39%). The experience in EU-FP programmes is at a “low level” with 20% of members who indicated a “very low level” and 36% a “low level”.

Representativity of the Thematic in ORs

From the extensive data mining activity done by the partners involved in WP2 (FORWARD-Nexa, 2020), mainly from CORDIS database¹⁷, it was identified a total of 53 Marine Sciences and Technologies projects funded by the European Commission, most of them in the

¹⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/fr/web/products-eurostat-news/-/edn-20200210-2>

¹⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu>

framework of the Horizon 2020. Canarias & Azores are the most outstanding ORs involved in marine field projects, followed by Madeira and Martinique with minor participation, whereas there was a limited participation of other French ORs in European funding schemes related to basic and applied marine research. In addition, Public Entities, followed by Research Centres, High Education Centres and Private Companies, promoted most of the projects. The global amount of funds received by ORs was about 15 million euros, corresponding to 5% of the total amount given to the European projects where OR participated.

Research Potential of the Marine Ecosystems in the Outermost Regions

The Outermost Regions have numerous potential growth engines based on their specific geographical characteristics. In the marine environment, it comprises more than half of the EU's Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) and has a potential reserve of marine resources close to 15 million km², which means having a unique on-site laboratory in three oceans for exploration in areas such as food security, climate action, energy and biotechnology, and constitutes an asset for tourism, thanks to its exceptional natural and cultural environment (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021)

Their geostrategic location places them as EU ambassadors in the Atlantic Ocean, the Caribbean and the Indian Ocean and offers them the possibility of benefiting the EU through their neighborhood relations and of spreading the influence of the EU in their respective regions. In addition, their human capital is very valuable since these regions have a better trained and more qualified workforce, better public services and more advanced technical knowledge than their neighbors, which gives them the possibility of selling services and knowledge in sectors with great added value (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

These regions are home to a unique diversity of species and ecosystems, of vital importance for biodiversity on a planetary level. In addition, together with overseas countries and territories, they have more endemic plant and animal species than continental Europe as a whole, including more than 20% of the World's coral reefs and coastal lagoons. The conservation and sustainable use of this huge biodiversity offers enormous possibilities in fields such as health, bio-pharmacy, cosmetics and in many other industrial sectors, such as active and nature tourism (ecotourism) or aquaculture of native species (food security) and renewable energies (zero emissions). Nevertheless, in most of the ORs, coherent policies for

the governance and sustainable use of the vast marine resources in their geographic environment have not yet been developed (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

The BEST initiative (Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services in European Overseas Territories), has highlighted the possibility of conducting research in prestigious European and international networks, showing various areas with important knowledge gaps such as marine biodiversity, where we do not know a large part of the processes and services that occur at the level of marine ecosystems, both coastal and high seas (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Recent specific initiatives of the DG Environment, with the MOVE and MOVE-ON projects, tries to map and identify the products and ecosystem services that marine and coastal habitats generate in the ORs. These projects seek to mobilize the few research teams linked to biodiversity in the ORs to show the economic relevance of the enormous biodiversity that these overseas territories hold (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

From the technological perspective, some experts of the ORs are in the frontline of applied research for the supply of potable water, which is mainly associated with evolved desalination technologies. The advances in the supply of this service to the local communities are a centerpiece of current research actions by a number of OR centers, such in the case of the ITC in Canarias. This technological field is also of international relevance for Third countries and it its foreseen a huge development potential in future decades (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Another keystone applied research development is the implementation of novel renewable marine energy technologies, which has been the centerpiece of the PLOCAN center and its associated network of research centers in other ORs. The European Commission has declared a target of zero emission for the coming decades and the ORs are outstanding laboratories to test and implement novel technologies for the supply of clean energy resources (FORWARD-Synergîle, 2021).

Major Research Interest of the TWG8 members

The inquiries and inputs received from the TWG8 members during the last 6 months are represented in the following figure (Figure 8), which summarizes in a cloud of words format the main research topics of interest selected by the ORs experts. The term "marine" has been removed since its presence is obvious and to allow a better analysis the rest of the terms

Table 17 List of actions of the Action Plan of thematic working group 8 : Marine Science & technologies

Actions	Details/ Venue	Start/end	Resources	Expected results	Level of advancement
Management: Successful development of the TWG management tasks in order to achieve goals within the set scope, time, quality and budget specifications.	The management of the TWG8 will be supported by Microsoft Team (MST) Tool. All the documents, online conferences, and results will be uploaded in this space.	March 2021 - December 2021	Microsoft Teams, Training materials, Templates		
A1.1. Implementation of cooperation and communication tools		Jul20 - Dec21		MST - TWG tool implemented	
Setting up online tools, Short training on using online tools, Implementing online tools	Offline work	Feb21 - Mar21	Microsoft Teams; Training materials	TEAMS Guidelines	Finished
A1.2. TWG Meetings		Jul20 - Dec21			
TWG8 Kick-off meeting	Online	févr-21	File: TWG Meetings Templates	Meeting Minutes: Advancements, agreements and next actions planning	Finished
Other TWG8 meeting	Online	Feb21 - Dec21	File: TWG Meetings Templates	Meeting Minutes: Advancements, agreements and next actions planning	In progress
A1.3. Reporting		Dec21			
First annual TWG Reporting	Offline work	Dec21	File: Report Template	TWG Report	Planned
Focusing: Selecting key Marine Sciences and Technologies research fields and subjects;	All the documents, online conferences, and results will be uploaded in this space.	March 2021 - December 2021	WP2 Guidelines and results		
A2.1. The co-creation of a <u>Marine Roadmap</u> with extensive participation of ORs members leading towards a Marine Sciences and Technologies Action Plan		Mar21 - Jun21			
Prioritizing <u>specific research areas</u>	Offline work	mars-21	File: Draft of the first version of TWG8 Action Plan	[Capacities] Definition of the main areas of interest	Planned
Creating <u>specific sub-groups</u>	Offline work	Apr21 - Jun21	Microsoft Teams: According to the first version of TWG8 Action Plan	[Networking] Creation of a channel on TEAMS for each subgroup defined	Planned
Networking: Establishment of networks between the ORs and external actors that will cooperate to build critical masses and projects on the considered thematics;	All the documents, online conferences, and results will be uploaded in this space.	April 2021 - December 2021			
A3.1. The development of an <u>Inter-regional platform</u> to foster research collaboration with Experts from ORs, other European regions and		Apr21 - Dec21			

Third Countries' Institutions with a common research domain: The marine realm.					
Creation of a <u>list of key institutions at OR and EU level in the area of Marine Science and Technologies.</u>	Collaborative space		File: key stakeholders and institutions	[Directory] Creation of a channel on TEAMS "TWG8 Actors Directory", according e.g. to the funds obtained in the area on the past H2020.	Planned
<u>A3.2. Identifying External Networking Events</u>		Apr21 - Dec21			
Task 3.2.1. Identification of events of interest organised at regional, national or at EU level, promoting among the members their active participation	Collaborative space	Apr21 - Dec21	File: Database Template	[Networking] Creation of a channel on TEAMS "TWG8 Events of interest" visibility of the OR's actors; increase the networking and the promotion of consortias	Planned
<u>A3.3. Promoting TWG Networking Activities</u>		Apr21 - Dec21			
Organisation of webinars to present a selection of successful projects in which TWG8 members have taken part	Online	Apr21 - Dec21	Microsoft Teams: Webinar	[Networking] To know the research developed by the members and increase the opportunities to build and to promote new projects	Planned
WP5 Networking event: Workshop FORWARD ULPGC "Blue Growth and Sustainable Exploitation of Marine Resources from the Ecosystem Approach"	Online	Apr21 - Dec21	Microsoft Teams: Webinar	[Networking]	Planned
Implementation: fostering the participation of OR's organizations in European R&D&I programmes;	All the documents, online conferences, and results will be uploaded in this space.	April 2021 - December 2021			
A4.1. Increase both the number of European Frame Programme projects submitted and finance in the ORs, and the promotion of a deeper integration of ORs scientists into the ERA.		Apr21 - Dec21			
Identification of calls and topics of interest for the TWG8 on Horizon Europe Programme, LIFE, DGs, etc.	Collaborative space	Apr21 - Dec21	File: Database template "List of Funding Opportunities (Funding Programme Database)"	[Proposal submissions] Creation of a channel on TEAMS "TWG8 Funding opportunities" with factsheets with	Planned

				information of the calls	
<u>Identification of active partners</u> looking for leading a consortium or to join to a consortium in forthcoming calls and funding opportunities	Collaborative space	Apr21 - Dec21	File: Database template	[Proposal submissions] Creation of a channel on TEAMS "TWG8 Partner search" (contact data, topic, abstract proposal, etc..).	Planned
A4.2. Training: participation on training activities designed in the FW Capacity Building Plan		Apr21 - Dec21			
<u>Identification and organisation of training courses, webinaris and/or infodays</u> of interest (writing proposals, reporting and audits, ERC/MSCA calls, COST Actions, etc.)	Collaborative space	Apr21 - Dec21	File: Database template	[Training] Creation of a channel on TEAMS "TWG8 Training and webinaris"	Planned
A4.3. To promote specific European calls for ORs where high relevant research groups can be integrated within local consortiums in specific Marine Sciences & Technologies topics.		Apr21 - Dec21			
<u>Position paper</u> analysing the needs for the promotion of specific European call for Ors	Offline work	Apr21 - Dec21	File: Position paper	[Report] Position paper	Planned
Dissemination: Disseminating TWG8 activities.	All the documents, online conferences, and results will be uploaded in this space.	feb21-dic21	Templates and protocol suggested		
A5.1. Dissemination of TWG8 activities through FORWARD channels		Feb21 - Dec21			
Disseminate the activities done on the context of TWG8 through FORWARD channels.	Collaborative space	Feb21 - Dec21	File: Template	[Visibility] To increase the visibility of the TWG8 activities and the FW project. Synergies with other TWGs.	Planned

ANALYSE OF THE THEMATIC ACTION PLANS

As indicated in the previous section and shown by the list of the Action Plans, each thematic working group has co-created the plans based on their specificity, interests and needs, and made its adapted choices.

Analyses presented in this section have two main goals: determine the needs of the TWG to properly operate and assess the risk to be able to submit projects to the future EU-FP calls.

This section will be shared in three parts, a first one on the functioning of the thematic working groups, a second on the objectives and sub-objectives proposed in the action plans and the last one on the actions listed.

Functioning of thematic working groups

Meeting management

The TWGs have different sizes but a distribution of members in ORs origin or affiliation not so different. The percentage of active members is around 50% for most of the group (Table 3). As shown by the Figure 4 the two most represented ORs are the same for all the TWG (*i.e.*, Canary Islands and Madeira), while the lower representation of the French ORs varies from one working group to another but is still not as high as Canary Islands and Madeira.

Supported by the initial guideline (FORWARD-ITC, 2020), TWGs have planned autonomously their own meetings. Two working groups (TWG4 & TWG6) have organized from January to February four or more workshops in respect of the initial guideline (FORWARD-ITC, 2020). This is essentially because the dates and the hours of the meetings were determined at the beginning of the co-creation phase. The other working groups organized between two and three workshops in addition to the KOM. Each group has thus applied a tailored approach considering the needs and availability (including matching times with different time zones) of the group members and the co-creation process' implementation.

It is important to highlight that meetings have been frequently completed by offline work of the members to allow the collection of further outputs and the validation of action plans on time. Those offline works have been used by all TWGs.

The limited time of the co-creation phase had for effect, to find appropriate dates to meet, to adjust the instructions of the guideline after internal discussion within the groups. All thematic working groups built on the proposed methodology during the conception of the thematic action plans and tailored their activities as long as the co-creation process and the members' interaction were progressing. The TWGs spent more time in round tables such as TWG4 and TWG6 or asked the members to apply the methods of selection and evaluation of the actions offline as TWG1 and TWG5. The adjusted methodologies proposed by the thematic groups are particularly relevant and will serve as references for future guidelines. The methodologies concerned particularly the frequency, the length, and the agenda of the meeting. They are part of the several benefits of the co-creation phase.

As indicated in the third section of this report (**THE THEMATIC WORKING GROUP**), the organisation of the TWGs foresees one Sub-coordinator, a Deputy named by the Sub-coordinator and two Facilitators. Most TWGs have appointed all roles since the very beginning, while two (TWG1 and TWG2) preferred to wait for a deputy's designation in the co-creation phase by ensuring full presence and availability of the sub-coordinators. In the future ramp-up of activities with the implementation of the action plan, the two groups will assess the need to designate a Deputy, together with WP Leader ITC and task leader Synergile. In the more labour-intensive phase of action plans' implementation, a Deputy figure may support efficient distribution of work tasks (scientific discussion and administrative management).

Four TWGs out of eight proceeded to the establishment of sub-groups. That was not done in the intention to create independent sub-groups but to ease the communication between experts on specific subjects. It is the case of TWG4 (computing sciences), TWG5 (Climate Change & Energy transition), TWG6 (Agro-system & One Health Approach), and TWG8 (Marine sciences). This approach does not go against the spirit of the FORWARD project.

Features of the TWG

Two working groups (TWG1 and TWG5) mentioned their intention to sign a nondisclosure agreement to protect information and idea exchange during the meetings. At least three TWGs made the choice to start to work as an established consortium (TWG1-TWG2-TWG5). They focus on the selection of appropriate calls and the drafting of projects. The goals for

them are the proposal edition for a maximum number of the TWG members based on the existing and future EU-FP calls.

On the other side the other TWGs are more focused on establishing the conditions to create projects with members coming from different areas and with different expertise, among other the TWG6. They remain attentive to the coming EU-FP calls.

Objective and sub-objective of the action plan

The objectives and sub-objective selected by the TWGs can be classified in two kinds (Table 18). The first one with objectives and sub-objectives focused on the preparation and the submission of proposals to EU calls. The second is based on the creation and development of environments favourable to collaboration across Outermost Regions and creation of projects.

The co-creation process adapted to the needs, requirements and interests of the TWG members. At this stage, it is difficult to fully explain why this difference appears in these eight thematic working groups, which may depend on the degree of maturity of research and collaboration within each thematic sector. In any case, all TWGs still have the submission of proposals to EU calls as an obligation step and a true motivation.

The TWG1 (Health), TWG5 (Climate Change and Energy) and TWG8 (Marine Science) are more focused on the submission of proposals. At the opposite TWG2 (Human science), TWG3 (Earth Science, Space and Universe Science), TWG4 (Computer sciences), TWG6 (Agriculture and Bio-Technology) and TWG7 (Biodiversity) put in front the conditions to be able draw the future of their expertise field and write project proposal together.

Without any intention to conclude on the relation of those two facts, this situation will be helpful to describe the dynamic of the process of collaboration between ORs experts. It will be interesting to evaluate the evolution of the action plans and the associated objectives and sub-objectives in six months after more exchange and collaboration between the members.

Table 18 List of the objectives and the sub-objectives of the Action Plans of the thematic working group

	Objectives and sub-objectives
TWG1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Management: Successful development of the TWG1 management tasks to achieve goals within the set scope, time, quality and budget specifications; ● Focusing: Selecting key research fields and subjects related with the TWG1; ● Networking: Establishment of networks between the ORs and with external actors that will cooperate to build critical masses and projects on the considered themes; ● Implementation: fostering the participation of OR's organizations in European R&D&I programmes; ● Sustainability: Prospective approach to focus on ensuring their sustainability both during the project life and even after its end; ● Dissemination: Disseminating TWG activities.
TWG2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To develop R&I collaboration within ORs; ● To turn the Working group into an incubator for Horizon Europe projects.
TWG3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EU Commission Lobby; ● Cooperation between OR's Institutions.
TWG4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rise our capacity of Designing an innovative ICT framework as a generic top layer applicable to several application areas; ● Rise our capacity of Designing ICT tools required for an innovative solution in some given application domains.
TWG5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Designing and developing project proposals for Horizon Europe: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Climate, Earth Knowledge and Adaptation ○ Sustainable Energy and Mobility
TWG6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create an active network with the capacity to address the future challenges of our regions in a relevant manner: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Design the future of the Agro-System of the ORs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Design integrated Health Management through the One Health Approach
TWG7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promote the unique biodiversity of ORs to key stakeholders; ● Long-term biodiversity monitoring in ORs; ● The management of natural resources and associated conflicts with biodiversity conservation.
TWG8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● MANAGEMENT: Successful development of the TWG8 management tasks in order to achieve goals within the set scope, time, and quality; ● FOCUSING: Selecting key Marine Sciences and Technologies research fields and subjects; ● NETWORKING: Establishment of networks between the ORs and external actors that will cooperate to build critical masses and projects; on Marine Sciences and Technologies; ● IMPLEMENTATION: fostering the participation of OR's organizations in European R&D&I programmes in the area of Marine Sciences and Technologies; ● DISSEMINATION: Disseminating TWG8 activities.

Analyse of the actions listed in the Thematic Action Plans

Analysis of the actions selected by the TWGs after almost two months of co-creation allows to propose a classification of five action types (Table 19).

The five type of actions mentioned before are:

- Mapping and inventory: related to the need of spatial data for all ORs;
- Assessment and monitoring: related to the need in recent and accurate data;
- Planning and co-creation: related to the WP5 (networking) and the need to act together;
- Dissemination and communication: related the WP8 and collaborate in the popularized knowledge and innovation;
- Encourage and Drive: related to WP4 (capacity building) and the need in human resource and financial means to create and innovate more.

Table 19 Description and enumeration of the five type of actions proposed the thematic working group in their action plans

Type of action	Description	Percentage of actions declared
Mapping and inventory	Of the skills, expertise, actors, experts, actions	22%
Assessment and monitoring	Of the biological and physical parameters, variables, actions, field of activity	18%
Planning and co-creation	Of specific actions, training, sensitization	29%
Dissemination and communication	Training of the actors, the population, sensitization, recruitment of new members	24%
Encourage and Drive	Favour research, innovation. Ease collaboration between TWGs, collaboration between actors (quadruple-helix approach)	5%

A raw analysis of the action type in proportion by the TWGs seems to indicate that the three main types are the planning and the co-creation (29%), followed by the dissemination and communication (24%), and mapping and inventory (22%). This average value of the proportion of the type of action by the TWGs also highlights the low representation of action aiming to encourage and drive. One can explain that state by the need to focus more on the needs for information on the ORs Research and Innovation ecosystem, or the need to have more time for the experts to get to know each other.

Further analysis will be conducted during Phase 2 -implementation- to evaluate how the proportion of those actions will evolve with more knowledge and networking.

The level of details of the actions is different from one TWG to another. But all the list of actions are in consistency with the objectives and sub-objectives.

To facilitate the execution of actions some TWGs decided to create sub-groups to ease the discussion between experts. The creation of sub-groups also allows the emergence of specific actions.

The list of actions proposed by the TWGs is a logical set of elements that will help to build the bridge between ORs, through the eight selected themes and well beyond. The actions and the TWGs must be supported as much as possible to maintain the motivation of the members and to not break the ongoing process.

CONCLUSION

From November 2020 to March 2021 the thematic working groups of the nine Outermost Regions were held. The Canary Island, Madeira and Azores are the most represented and Mayotte and St Martin are less in the process of the co-creation of thematic action plans.

Around 527 registered experts, 264 fully active, of the ORs and from Third Countries (currently are involved Palestine; Mexico; Tunisia; and Brazil) meet between four to six times during this period. They come from university, research centers, SME, NGO, local government, economic chamber, or innovation cluster. They worked online and offline on one action plan (or two for the more ambitious).

The organization around the Thematic Working Groups composed of at least a Sub-coordinator selected by the Steering Committee of the project, a Deputy, and two Facilitators have allowed the holding of more than 35 virtual meetings with nine ORs, but also many offline activities (i.e., survey, profiling, analysis, etc) and the edition of several documents.

The worldwide epidemic of SARS-Cov-2 modified the organisation of the thematic working Group, postpone the kick-off meeting of the sub-coordinator meeting, avoid the meetings during the FORWARD event. Fortunately, the digital tools and the TWG communication platform, always in the process of improvement, allowed the compensation of that lack. Two virtual follow up meetings with the Sub-coordinators, Deputies and Facilitator allows to create deeper synergies between the TWGs.

The action plans of the eight TWGs were presented with their objective, sub-objectives and sub-groups for the ones who made that justified choice. All the actions listed are in consistency with the thematic working groups and the FORWARD project aims.

Analysis of the action plans highlights the need for local data, at the scale of ORs, to foster the development of international collaborative projects. It also indicates that among the different types of actions three seem more relevant and chosen by the TWG: "Planning and co-creation", "Dissemination and communication" and "Mapping and Inventory".

The phase of implementation of these action plans already started in March 2021. It will run at least up to June 2022, after validation of the demand of extension. To achieve the aims of the project, there will need a high engagement of the members, which the FORWARD project

will seek to ensure throughout the next year. To be able to do what they know the best: “**find and innovate**” ORs experts will need the full support of the project partners but also from the local governments, and European Commission to convert this transoceanic dynamic into concrete actions.

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FORWARD WP3: Co-creation and implementation of thematic groups

T3.2 Thematic action plans: Report on the Action Plans co-create by the thematic working groups.

ANNEX I: The full eight Action Plans

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For the sake of readability, only selected parts are presented in the main document. The full version of each of the eight thematic action plans is compiled in this annex and will serve as an archive and working document for further analysis.

The leader of Task 3.2 (Synergîle) and the WP3 leader (ITC) want to thank the Sub-coordinators, Deputies, Facilitators, and the TWG members for the huge work done in a small amount of time.

To respect the work done by the Thematic Working Groups and the vision of their members, the action plans are presented without modification. Only the font of the text was changed to homogenize the document.

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TWG1: Health, Applied Medical Technologies, Diagnosis and Therapies

Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

ACTION PLAN OF THE THEMATIC WORKING GROUP 1

*Health, applied medical technologies, Diagnosis and
Therapies*

22/march/21

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*The TGW1 action plan is a guide, written in a collaborative manner and updated as required,
to define:*

- *context of the group activities*
- *activities to implement*
- *collecting group members info and interest*
- *set the expected outputs and workplan*

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1 THE TWG1 IN THE FRAME OF THE FORWARD PROJECT

1.1 THE FORWARD PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND STRUCTURE

General objectives

- **Improve ORs' excellence in research and their innovation potential**
- **Improve their participation in EU research and innovation funded projects**
- **Link research activities with territorial development**

Specific objectives

- **MAPPING** the ORs ecosystems in research and innovation to underline strengths, weaknesses and potentials for growth
- **CHARACTERIZE BARRIERS** to ORs participation in past EU framework programmes, and the corresponding design of effective tools to overcome existing barriers and support the implication of ORs in the next programmes
- **IDENTIFYING COMMON FIELDS OF INTEREST** and **COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES** of the different regions and define emerging specialization areas for each OR
- To accompany the **TRANSFORMATION** and **CAPACITY BUILDING** of each OR R+i ecosystem to better exploit these potentials, by improving their excellence and the mobilization of multiple type of stakeholders (research organization, companies, public authorities and civil society organizations) through a quadruple helix approach
- To support the formulation of **PARTICIPATORY AND RESEARCH-BASED ACTION PLANS** with long-term perspective
- To increase the regional, national, European and worldwide **VISIBILITY** and **RECOGNITION** of the ORs research capacities and activities in their fields of specialization
- To DEFINE ORs' friendly **TOPICS** in the future Framework Programmes
- To encourage the constitution of **CRITICAL RESEARCH MASS** through networking, exchanges and consortia with regional, national, European and global research centres
- To **FOSTER SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT** of the European ORs through the quadruple helix approach

- To **FOSTER ORS GEOGRAPHICAL INTEGRATION** within the European Union and towards Third Countries

FORWARD phases and Work Packages

At a glance, the FORWARD project consist mainly of three phases. We are currently in the **Phase 2** of the project:

As in every EU project, the general and specific objectives are organized in Work Packages (Figure 1), the corresponding tasks, etc. More specifically, the group activity is developed in the context of the **WP3 (Co-creation and implementation of Thematic Action Plans)** which aims to reinforce the actual and reveal the potential competitive advantages of the Outermost

Figure 1 FORWARD implementation (Work Packages)

1.2 THE TWG1 AIMS AND BENEFITS FROM PARTICIPATION

The TWGs are bringing together experts from the ORs, continental EU, 3rd and other countries (ref). Further expected main contributions of the TWG1 work are:

- **Foster collaboration** on common thematic areas among OR's, between OR's and third countries as well as continental Europe stakeholders to reach critical mass
- **Increase ORs** participation in the next EU framework Programs

For this TWG1 we aim to:

- ✓ *submit **at least one applications** under the calls for the EU [Horizon Europe](#) and/or the next [4th Health programme](#). The number of applications will certainly depend on the dynamics of the group itself, the opportunities created and those associated with the calls that will open*
- ✓ *organize **at least one international thematic event***
- ✓ ***at least two training activities** according to members' needs*

These aims are aligned with the training actions planned (WP4), and the networking plan (WP5), and are based on the R+i diagnostic performed (WP2), the RIS3 strategy, and the specific needs/barriers stated by R+i actors. We expect that TWG1 participants will benefit from its participation by:

- ✓ finding funding opportunities and support in the proposal development processes
- ✓ get customized guidance on choosing relevant calls, topics and types of actions
- ✓ acquire training and receive assistance on proposal writing and consortia establishment
- ✓ improving their skills when approaching EU research projects

2 BACKGROUND

Section 2 explains the rationale behind the explained objectives considering the results obtained in the WP2 Diagnostic and preliminary work in the frame of WP3.

2.1 BARRIERS STATED BY R+I ACTORS INTERVIEWED

The WP2 included a survey and interviews conducted in the 9 ORs on 2019. The main barriers to EU framework programmes participation and needs expressed by researchers and SMEs were the following:

- *Lack of technical and administrative support in proposal writing*
- *Difficulty to build partnerships and networking*
- *Small size of research groups and research centres*
- *Low participation of SMEs*
- *Lack of institutional support, public authorities support*

2.2 ANALYSIS OF PAST ORS HEALTH-RELATED PROJECTS

BY REGION

From the extensive data mining activity done in WP2, mainly from [CORDIS](#), we identified **21** funded by **H2020** in Health and applied medical technologies, diagnostics and therapies. The global amount received by ORs is **€7.5M**,

Figure 2 Number of projects by OR

corresponding to 5% of the total amount given to the projects where OR participated. By region, we concluded that **Canaries** is an outstanding OR involved in H2020 health projects (see Figure 2), followed by **Azores & Madeira** with minor participation, and finally there is a limited participation of **French ORs** in H2020. In particular, considering organizations with at least two funded projects we can see that two

Figure 3. Main H2020 players

universities, a consulting group and the Canarian Health Service are the main H2020 players (see Figure 3).

BY PROJECT TYPE

For the analysis of the grant schemes and Project types we included: 1) Collaborative projects from H2020 Challenge 1 (health), 2) Marie Curie Projects and ERANETs. The main conclusion is 74% of projects cover: Training, Networking, Capacities, etc., meaning that we were more successful in get funding towards actions supporting R+i rather than R+i itself (26%, see the following Table):

Funding Scheme	Azores	Canarias	Guayana	La Réunion	Madeira	Martinique	Total
COFUND-EJP		1					1
CSA		1					1
ERA-NET-Cofund	1						1
ERC-COG		1					1
IA		2			1		3
MSCA-IF-EF-ST		1					1
MSCA-IF-GF		1					1
MSCA-ITN-ETN		1					1
MSCA-RISE		2					2
RIA		4	1	2	1	1	9
SME-1		1		1			2
Total	1	15	1	3	2	1	23

3 THE TWG1 ACTIVITIES

3.1 COLLABORATIVE TOOLS TO BE USED

TEAMS PLATFORM

COLLABORATIVE PLATFORM 1: TEAMS

 Microsoft Teams

- **FOR MEETINGS**
- **FOR DOCS FILING**

Ex.

- Members profile
- Calls factsheet
- Meetings minutes
- ETC.

General

- Nombre ▾
- Agendas
- Reports of the meetings.
- TWG1 report on RD ecosystem
- List of members profiling TWG1_HEALTH 1...
- Member Profiles TWG1_HEALTH.xlsx
- TWG1_HEALTH_List of members profiling.xlsx

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824562

GOOGLE DRIVE

COLLABORATIVE PLATFORM 2: GOOGLE DRIVE

- **FOR COLLABORATIVE EDITING:**

Ex.

- Member profile (doc)
- Action plan
- Newsletter (events, training, calls)

 TWG members profiling

Compartido conmigo > TWG1 - FORWARD > TWG members profiling

Archivos

 EXAMPLE_SURNAME_NET...

 FROJESO_LESUCJAN...

 GARCIA_IAC_AZRES.docx

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824562

GOOGLE FORMS

More info exchange: GOOGLE FORMS

The diagram illustrates the integration of training methods. On the left, a dashed box labeled 'Google Forms' contains a purple document icon. Below it, two rounded rectangular boxes are connected by a plus sign. The first box is labeled 'PLANNED TRAINING' and contains a black checkmark. The second box is labeled 'AD HOC TRAINING' and contains an icon of crossed pencils. A large grey arrow points from the right side of these two boxes towards the right. To the right of the arrow, the text 'Ex. Short online seminars about:' is followed by a bulleted list of topics.

Ex. Short online seminars about:

- Project types (RIA and IAs)
- open or prescribed calls
- Tips for proposal writing
- Tips for the implementation section
- Etc.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 424242.

3.2 MEMBERS (SECTION TO BE UPDATED EACH 15 DAYS)

First time the R+i actors were asked about their willingness to participate in the group we received 90 responses. Second time, after further WP3 activity, they were asked again and received 82 applications from all ORs regions and other countries (Figure 4):

Figure 4. Member profiling by region/country

By institution type the universities are the great majority but also, we count with university hospitals, public administration, SMEs, etc. (Figure 5):

Figure 5. TWG1 members by institution type

The member profiling is essential to define the group sub-thematics and to enable a catalogue to serve as the basis for future partner search. In addition to basic contact info, we also asked for further information (to be completed in the drive folder) regarding 1) the European

Research Council panel more related to their interest and 2) further info about past projects, and 3) Key words

Results from ERC panel analysis

The ERC panel to be selected were the following within the Life Sciences general Panel:

The feedback received from 22 members indicated that the predominant panel is LS7, which involves the scientific areas: **LS7** *Medical technologies and tools for prevention, diagnosis and treatment of human diseases, therapeutic approaches and interventions, pharmacology, preventative medicine, epidemiology and public health, digital medicine*. The following panel is LS4, close to LS6 (see Fig. 6)

Panel	Area	Number of members
LS1	Molecules of Life: Biological Mechanisms, Structures and Functions	1
LS2	Integrative Biology: from Genes and Genomes to Systems	0
LS3	Cellular, Developmental and Regenerative Biology	0
LS4	Physiology in Health, Disease and Ageing	5
LS5	Neuroscience and Disorders of the Nervous System	1
LS6	Immunity, Infection and Immunotherapy	4
LS7	Prevention, Diagnosis and Treatment of Human Diseases	13
LS8	Environmental Biology, Ecology and Evolution	3
LS9	Biotechnology and Biosystems Engineering	1
O	Other	0

LS4: *Organ and tissue physiology, comparative physiology, physiology of ageing, pathophysiology, inter-organ and tissue communication, endocrinology, nutrition,*

metabolism, interaction with the microbiome, non-communicable diseases including cancer (and except disorders of the nervous system and immunity-related diseases)

LS6: *The immune system, related disorders and their mechanisms, biology of infectious agents and infection, biological basis of prevention and treatment of infectious diseases, innovative immunological tools and approaches, including therapies*

Figure 6. The ERC Panels selected by members

Results from key words (section to be updated each 15 days)

We performed a brief analysis of the key words provided and assigned R+i broad research interest in terms of: DISEASES, PATHOGEN/CAUSE and TREATMENT/REMEDY. The research areas found are TROPICAL DISEASES, THERAPIES (antioxidants, antiparasitic and anticancer) and TRANSLATIONAL MEDICINE (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Main R+i areas of interest

3.3 ASSETS OF THE TWG1 (SECTION TO BE UPDATED EACH 15 DAYS)

GENERAL ASSETS OF THE GROUP

to be completed after your feedback of the members

ASSETS OF THE GROUP IN TROPICAL DISEASES

to be completed after feedback of the member, preliminary text

The TWG1 presents a wide experience in the field of tropical and emerging diseases. For instance, the subcoordinator of the TWG1 is currently the director of the University Institute of Tropical Diseases and Public Health of the Canary Islands at the University of La Laguna. This Institution presents more than 15 years of experience in diagnosis, treatment, vector surveillance and prevention of tropical and emerging diseases including COVID19. Moreover, the IUETSPC collaborates with many institutions in America, Africa and Asia working in this field which has produced many scientific publications and congress communications. Some of the partners also present wide experience in antiparasitic agents, vector control and diagnosis of tropical and emerging diseases in ORs.

ASSETS OF THE GROUP IN THERAPIES

to be completed after feedback of the members

ASSETS OF THE GROUP IN TRANSLATIONAL MEDICINE

to be completed after feedback of the members

4 TWG1 SPECIFIC ACTIVITY

4.1 OBJECTIVES

Objective 1. Management: Development of the TWG1 management tasks to achieve goals within the set scope, time, quality and budget specifications.

O1.1 Implementation of cooperation and communication tools

O1.2 TWG Meetings (First international sub-coordinators meeting and training

TWG1 Kick-off meeting, further TWG1 meetings)

We would like to schedule 1 short meeting (40 mins) each 2-3 weeks rather than 1,5 h lasting meetings less often

Objective 2. Focusing: Selecting key research fields and subjects.

O2.1 Creating specific TW Sub-groups (Filling in TWG Members' profiles, Analysis of TWG1 Members' profiles,)

PLEASE REMIND THAT COMPLETING YOUR PROFILE IS ESSENTIAL

Objective 3: Networking: Establishment of networks between the ORs and external actors to build consortia

O3.1 Identifying key institutions/actors/stakeholders (ongoing collaborations + “Wishlist” institutions)

O3.2 Identifying External Networking Events

O3.3 Promoting TWG Networking Activities (TWG1 thematic event: Health in the ORs (synergy with WP5 Networking)), Subthematic Networking event (focused in the most relevant scientific area)

Objective 4: Implementation: fostering the participation of OR's organizations in European R+i programmes

O4.1 Identifying funding opportunities

O4.2 Building potential consortium (Identification of active partners, Identification of networking platforms (linked with brokerage events finding))

O4.3 Improving member's knowledge about international projects (Identification of TWG1 member's needs, general and tailored trainings)

Objective 5: Disseminating TWG activities.

Disseminate the TWG1 activities done through FORWARD channels (social media, web...), disseminate the TWG1 profiles to stakeholders outside ORs

4.2 NON-DISCLOSURE AGREEMENT

All members implicitly agree that their participation in this thematic group is not intended to obtain information they could use elsewhere and, in that way, compromising the aims of the group. When working on the specific project proposal, members / participants will have to explicitly commit with not “leaking” information, in particular to competing proposals outside

the group. Signing a document of confidentiality reinforcing this non-disclosure objective shall be required.

4.3 IDENTIFIED CALLS OF INTEREST (SECTION TO BE UPDATED EACH 15 DAYS)

Health, applied medical technologies, Diagnosis and Therapies in Horizon Europe

The European Commission defined its new Framework Programme Horizon Europe 2021-2027 with three pillars:

In the TWG1 we will prioritise when possible R+i projects rather than R+i supporting actions and/or R+i+training actions. In any case we will do our best to reach and provide a suitable option for the higher number of members as possible.

CLUSTER 1 HEALTH UNOFFICIAL DRAFT.

(TOPICS DESCRIPTION DRAFT AVAILABLE)

As to the TWG1 the proposals to be developed will fit mainly in the Pillar 2, CLUSTER 1: HEALTH. Currently we are working with a preliminary topics description provided by the Spanish national contact point ([LINK](#)). Regarding the EU4Health programme, the official draft is not available at this moment, but we are aware of its development.

WIDENING PROGRAMME

In any case the dominant research area (TROPICAL DISEASES) is not related to any of the official topic, so we preliminary found an alternative in the so called 4th Pillar ([Widening](#)

[participation and strengthening the ERA](#)), in particular we found interesting submitting a [COST ACTION](#) supporting this research field.

The 4th HEALTH PROGRAMME

The **EU4Health programme** will focus on making the best possible use of this new knowledge for the benefit of citizens and health systems. In particular, **Europe`s Beating Cancer Action plan** will support Member States in improving cancer prevention, control and care. We are still waiting for official documents to be published. The Spanish National Contact Point stated on 23/March/2021 that the first work programme draft might be published on April-May.

5 NEXT STEPS (SECTION TO BE UPDATED EACH 15 DAYS)

- 1) This version of the Action Plan will be submitted to WP3 leaders on 24/March/21
- 2) We will ask for members feedback about this doc (up to 31 March) and implement your feedback (31-March – 5 April)
- 3) We will schedule a meeting to discuss further feedback and explaining preliminary results from ERC panel and key words analysis (6-8 April)

TWG2: Social Sciences Action plan

FORWARD

Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions
WP3 • Co-creation and implementation of thematic groups

Social Sciences Action plan

Final Version

March 11th 2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation Programme under grant agreement N° 824550

Project Acronym	FORWARD
Project name	Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions
Grant agreement n°	824550
Project type	Coordination and Support action
Start date - End Date	01/06/2019 - 31/12/2021
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Responsible partner for the WP and tasks	ITC & Synergîle
Responsible partner for the document	Nexa
Type of document	Action plan
Dissemination level	Public
Contributors	Dr. Evelyne Tarnus Dr. Philippe Holstein Prof. Philippe Jean-Pierre Marine Germain
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I. INTRODUCTION

A. The Forward project

The [Forward](#) project is a European Coordination and Support Action funded under a H2020-Swafs2018-2020 call, with a total budget of 4.2 million euros for 3 years (2019-2021). Involving 24 partners from the nine European Outermost Regions (ORs) - the Azores, the Canary Islands, Guadeloupe, French Guiana, La Réunion, Madeira, Martinique, Mayotte, Saint-Martin – the project aims at improving the research and innovation (R&I) excellence of these regions as well as their participation in current and future European dedicated Framework Programmes (FP), labelled Horizon 2020 (for the 2014-2020 period) and Horizon Europe (2021-2027). To that end, the Forward project addresses several specific objectives:

1. To map outermost regions' ecosystems in research and innovation to underline the strengths, weaknesses and potentials for growth of each OR;
2. To identify actual and future fields of excellence and competitive advantages of the different regions and define emerging specialization areas for each OR and define ORs' friendly topics in the future Framework Programmes;
3. To characterize and objective barriers to ORs participation in H2020;
4. To accompany the transformation and capacity building of each OR research and innovation ecosystem to better exploit these potentials, by improving their excellence (in research, technical / technological development, uptake of research results, entrepreneurship discovery, collaboration and multidisciplinary approaches, administrative procedures and frameworks, policy impact and science) and the mobilization of multiple kind of stakeholders (research organization, companies, public authorities and civil society organizations) through a quadruple helix approach;
5. To support the formulation of participatory and research-based action plans with long-term perspective;
6. To increase the regional, national, European and worldwide visibility and recognition of outermost regions research capacities and activities in their fields of specialization;

7. To encourage the constitution of critical research mass in ORs through networking, exchanges and consortia with regional, national, European and global research centers;
8. To design and experiment effective tools to overcome existing barriers and support the implication of ORs in Horizon 2020 and future framework;
9. To foster socio-economic development of the European ORs through the quadruple helix approach;
10. To foster ORs geographical integration within the European Union and towards Third Countries, through the connection with European and international partners.

B. The thematic transregional working groups, a lever to increase ORs participation in the research and innovation Framework Programme (FP)

Despite their limited resources, the ORs embrace a large number of R&I priorities, which conducts to the fragmentation of the efforts and inhibits the creation of the critical masses necessary to exist in the globalized era of research and innovation. At the exception of the Canary, an average scientific field does not mobilize more than 30 researchers in ORs, with some being represented by only 2 people.

To overcome such critical mass and visibility issues, the Forward consortium has established 8 transregional working groups. These groups are in charge of designing and implementing thematic action plans in order to:

- foster collaboration on common thematic areas among ORs, between ORs and third countries as well as continental Europe stakeholders
- reinforce the assets of Outermost Regions in their respective fields of expertise
- increase ORs stakeholders participation in H2020/Horizon Europe projects

1. Definition of the thematic working groups

The definition of the thematics was based on the results of the diagnosis performed under Work Package N°2, notably:

- the Smart specialisation strategy domains of ORs

- the total amount of EU Contribution received by ORs stakeholders in fields of research according to the nomenclature of the European Research Council
- the potential of cooperation between the ORs (taking out fields with only one active region)
- the alignment with the Horizon Europe pillars

From this analysis, 9 thematics were selected and a call for interest was launched among the 9 ORs to recruit participants and potential coordinators, in charge of helping the group in the design and implementation of the action plans. At the end of the process, 8 thematics working groups were actually established (the Tourism topic was merged with the Social Sciences and innovation thematic), as shown in table 1.

Table 1 FORWARD thematic working groups.

N°	Thematic	Number of registered people at the launch ¹
TWG1	Health, applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies.	75 people
TWG2	Social sciences and social innovation.	111
TWG3	Earth system, space & universe sciences.	35
TWG4	Information and Communications Technology.	47
TWG5	Climate change and Energy transition.	67
TWG6	Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering.	77
TWG7	Biodiversity conservation and restoration.	52
TWG8	Marine sciences & technologies.	72

The thematic working group n°2 dedicated to Social Sciences R&I gathers 130 research and innovators from ORs (see Annex I). It is coordinated by Philippe Jean-Pierre (Prof. at the University of La Reunion) and facilitated by Nexa, the Regional Agency for Development, Innovation & Investment of La Reunion.

¹ This number is continuously evolving

Figure 1 Distribution of the group members by region

Figure 2 Distribution of the group members according to their organization status

2. Co-design of the thematic action plan for Social Sciences

To elaborate an efficient action plan, leading to a stronger participation of social scientists in the Horizon Europe programme, the working group implemented a methodology which relies on three main principles:

1. a knowledge-based approach to objectivize the actual participation, highlight the specific barriers, define a realistic and inspiring ambition and propose effective actions, inspired by successful experiments. The working group thus exploits the diagnosis performed under WP2.
2. the mobilization of a co-design process. According to the bilateral interviews and survey performed during WP2 in the partner regions, many researchers and innovators depict the Framework Programme as too complicated or unsuited to their daily realities, generating a lack of interest and involvement in the development of projects. To increase the willingness to submit proposals and the success rate of the applicants, the action plan should be based on the concrete experiences, representations and expectations of the participants.
3. the definition of synergies with other work packages of the Forward project - WP4 (capacity building), WP5 (networking), WP6 (policy-making) and other initiatives to increase the impacts and the sustainability of the actions implemented.

Considering the large number of participants in the Social Sciences R&I group, the methodology was adapted to allow each member to contribute actively and in an informed way, through 4 steps:

1. Production of a State of play of the ORs participation in H2020-projects dealing in Social sciences, to provide participant with factual information and support a common understanding of the main challenges faced by the group.

2. Profiling of Social sciences members (Background, Ambition, Expectations and Needs) through the “profiling survey” to better understand the motives of the participants.
3. Drafting of a knowledge-based ambition and a preliminary action plan to achieve this ambition which allows all participants to react and enrich to the proposed orientations.
4. Finalization of the action plan and preparation of the deliverable to be submitted to WP3 leader (ITC), based on the feedbacks provided by the group members.

This methodology was presented and discussed during the Kick off meeting of the group, held in November 2020. The Timeline of the work done by the Social sciences group is detailed in diagram 1.

Figure 3 Timeline of the action plan co-design

Table 2 Monitoring of group's members engagement

Engagement milestones	Number of respondents
1. Initial call for interest	111 (up to mid-july 2020)
2. Registration to the kick Off meeting	45
3. Profiling survey	71

4. Questionnaire on the preliminary action plan	30
5. Registration/interest in the Final Workshop	27 (up to the 2nd of March 2021)

II. ORS SOCIAL SCIENCES PARTICIPATION IN FP

While a large number of institutional discourses point out the weak participation of ORs in framework programmes (FP) and attribute this performance to structural characteristics, their actual implication remains so far a blind spot in the scientific literature. Such gap raises three main issues:

- the diffusion of deterministic and homogenizing approaches and policies, that naturalize the limited development of knowledge economy as a consequence of the permanent “handicaps” affecting these regions
- the lack of attention to the ongoing realizations and exceptional potential of the outermost regions.
- the incapacity to embrace the diverse situations of the different outermost regions and thematics in terms of research and innovation performance.

To fill the gap, the Forward project offered a unique opportunity to conduct a comparative analysis of the regional participation in the FP and question the underlying factors that explain such performance. In line with the objectives of WP3, the analysis was completed with a specific focus on social sciences. Considering the importance of these results to design an effective action-plan, this section summarizes:

- the global state of play of ORs participation in the FP7 and Horizon 2020 programmes
- their participation in competitive projects related to social Sciences
- the obstacles which hinders ORs participation in FP
- the barriers identified by group members

A. State of play

1. Global state of play of ORs

The Forward holistic diagnosis² shows that ORs are active in the Framework Programmes, with 121 FP7 and 239 Horizon 2020 projects (up to October 2020), representing a respective budget

² Under the Workpackage 2 led by Nexa, the Forward consortium produced a detailed analysis of the OR participation in FP. The results are available in [Deliverable 2.2](#) as well as in the 2 *open data* dashboards developed by Nexa:

- [Framework programmes participation dashboard](#)
- [R&I indicators](#)

of 40,8 and 80,3 M€. Almost 100 organizations have been involved in projects, and 55 in position of coordination (26 excluding mono-beneficiary projects).

Through these projects, the Outermost Regions intervene in critical fields for the EU and on global challenges that such as: earth system observation, adaptation to climate change, biodiversity & ecosystems assessments, marine technologies, infectious diseases, food security, energy transition, space sciences and social sciences.

Table 3 Key figures of ORs participation in FP

	FP7	H2020 (Up to October 2020)
Number of Projects	121	239
Number of Participations	ND	364
EU contribution (M€)	40,8	80,3
Number of active organizations	ND	94
Number of coordination	ND	55 (26 in a collaborative project)

The regional participation appears particularly heterogeneous, with a strong polarization around the Canary Islands which alone account for 62% and 67% of the participations and EU contributions (i.e. grants) awarded to the OR. This driving force is reinforced by the active contribution of the Azores and Madeira, that altogether represent 94% of such contributions. The French ORs can themselves be divided into two groups: modest regions, who play a minor yet regular role in EU projects, such as La Réunion (17 participations), Guadeloupe (15), Martinique (9), Guyane (4), and new comers whose participation remains so far limited to Forward (Mayotte and St Martin).

Figure 4 Regional participation in Horizon 2020

Compared to 274 NUTS2 regions, the Outermost Regions remain small beneficiaries of the Horizon 2020 program. The most active region, the Canary Islands, lies in the European median but well below the average EU contribution (140 M€). The Azores and Madeira belong respectively to the 20% and 30% least beneficiary regions; the French OR to the 20 least active regions.

Table 4 Relative position of the OR vis à vis European NUTS 2 regions (Data up to July 2019)

	EU contribution	Decile	Rank (274)
Açores	6 640 138 €	2	227
Canarias	41 360 710 €	5	140
Guadeloupe	1 408 306 €	1	258
Guyane	572 478 €	1	267
La Réunion	1 879 192 €	1	253
Madeira	11 772 315 €	3	212
Martinique	859 258 €	1	265
Mayotte	157 562 €	1	271
Saint Martin	294 646 €	1	270
Average Nuts 2	140 175 249 €		

Since the OR and the NUTS2 regions present a marked diversity in terms of population, the evaluation of the EU contribution per capita remains a better indicator of the actual participation. Through this lens, Madeira integrates the top 30% regions in terms of EU contribution per capita, per year. The Azores are now lying in the median (+3), while the Canary belong to the 4th decile (-1). The French ORs remain in the bottom of the ranking.

Table 5 Relative position of the OR vis à vis European NUTS 2 regions (Data up to July 2019)

	H2020 p.capita per year	Decile	Rank (274)
Açores	5,45 €	5	148
Canarias	3,80 €	4	175
Guadeloupe	0,67 €	1	248
Guyane	0,40 €	1	260
La Réunion	0,44 €	1	258
Madeira	9,26 €	7	107
Martinique	0,47 €	1	257
Mayotte	0,12 €	1	269
Saint Martin	1,65 €	2	216
Average	13,77 €		

To question the capacity of the ORs to turn their regional resources and potential into Horizon 2020 projects, the comparison with regions that presents close characteristics – in terms of population, growth domestic product per capita, tertiary education level, proportion of researchers in the employed active population – is helpful. Once again, the Açores and Madeira who remain small beneficiary regions in absolute terms present a much higher performance than most regions that share a similar trait. This highlights the ability of such regions to mobilize their globally limited research and innovation potential to participate actively in the program. At the opposite end of the spectrum, the French OR perform less than regions with close characteristics, confirming their limited involvement in the program.

Table 6 Decile position of the ORs compared to groups of NUTS2 regions

	Population < 1 M inhabitants	GDP (18 to 22 k€)	Tertiary educ 25-64; 15 to 25%	Researchers & RD personnel 0,5% employ
Açores	6	8	8	9
Canarias	5	6	6	7
Guadeloupe	2	1	2	2
Guyane	2	1	1	2
La Réunion	2	1	1	2
Madeira	8	9	8	9
Martinique	2	1	2	2
Mayotte	1	1	1	1
Saint Martin	3	2	4	4
Average EU	10 € /capita / year	5,13 € / capita / year	5,08 € / capita / year	3,59 € / capita / y.

The comparison between the regional characteristics and the participation reveals the existence of 4 groups of regions among the OR in terms of FP participation:

- **NORMAL PERFORMER**, whose participation appears in line with their characteristics and close to EU average: The Canary Islands.
- **OUTPERFORMERS**, participating much more globally than regions presenting close characteristics : The Azores & Madeira
- **UNDERPERFORMERS** : Showing abnormal limited participation considering their characteristics : Guadeloupe, Guyane, La Réunion, Martinique
- **NON-PERFORMERS**, with limited ecosystems and having no H2020 experience : Mayotte & Saint-Martin

Such results confirm the necessity to overcome the traditional “one size fits all” approach and to adopt a tailor-made strategy that reflects the regional singularities. They also question the established representations and prejudices on outermost regions which treat their geographical or socio-economic conditions as irreducible “handicaps” that would lead to their

exclusion from Horizon 2020. Despite their limited size and resources, some regions indeed rival and perform better in Horizon 2020 than many mainland regions.

2. Overview of the participation of ORs in projects related to Social Sciences Research and Innovation

The 239 H2020-projects³ involving a partner from ORs⁴ were tagged according to the thematics of the Forward Thematic Working Groups based on the description of the projects available in the summary. The analysis shows that Social sciences Research & Innovation (SSRI)-related projects constitute the major field of participation of the ORs in H2020. 53 of the 239 projects (corresponding to 112 on 364 participations) identified were tagged as related to "Social sciences"⁵.

³ From 2014 to October 2020, ORs were involved in 239 projects funded by H2020; corresponding to 364 participations (Some projects, such as FORWARD, gather several ORs partners).

⁴ Nexa's global database, based on Cordis public data.

⁵ The role of social scientists may be underestimated since the mapping only takes into account projects dealing with social sciences and not the projects that may incorporate social sciences expertise.

Figure 5 Participation per thematic working group

Social sciences also represent the largest source of EU contribution (25%) awarded to the Outermost Regions. The participation is however concentrated, with a clear lead from the Canary Islands (53% of the participation in EU contribution) and Madeira (27%), and the remarkable implication of 11 organizations (out of 67) that account for 60% of the total number of participations of the OR.

Table 7 Top participating institutions

Organizations	EU contribution	Number of participations
UNIVERSIDAD DE LA LAGUNA	2 892 647,50 €	7
UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA	2 333 977,81 €	6
CAMARA MUNICIPAL DO FUNCHAL	1 573 460,00 €	2
INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO DE CANARIAS,S.A.	1 524 501,66 €	9
HORARIOS DO FUNCHAL-TRANSPORTES PUBLICOS SA	1 445 225,92 €	1
GUAGUAS MUNICIPALES SOCIEDAD ANONIMA	1 437 376,37 €	1
ASSOCIACAO COMERCIAL E INDUSTRIAL DO FUNCHAL - CAMARA DE COMERCIO E INDUSTRIA DA MADEIRA	1 317 816,80 €	6
CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL	1 262 364,81 €	6
ARDITI - AGENCIA REGIONAL PARA O DESENVOLVIMENTO DA INVESTIGACAO, TECNOLOGIA E INOVACAO - ASSOCIACAO	1 021 857,50 €	3

MITI - MADEIRA INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES INSTITUTE - ASSOCIACAO	938 144,60 €	3
FUNDO REGIONAL PARA A CIENCIA E TECNOLOGIA	735 952,98 €	7

The projects developed contributes to all H2020 pillars (Excellence science, Industrial leadership, Societal Challenges, Science With and For Society, Widening participation) and mobilize a variety of instruments and themes.

Table 8 Types of funding schemes mobilized

Funding schemes	Number of projects
ERC	2
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) / Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks (ITN)	6
INNOVATION in SMEs	11
CSA-European Researchers' Night	5
other Coordination and Support Actions	9
Innovation Actions	10
Research and Innovation Actions	10

Table 9 Themes of the projects

Themes	Number of projects
Innovation in SMEs	11
Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions	11
Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials	6
Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research	4
Information and Communication Technologies	4
Secure, clean and efficient energy	4
Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective Societies	3
European Research Council	2
Health, demographic change and wellbeing	2

Smart, green and integrated transport	2
Develop the governance for the advancement of responsible research and innovation	1
Promote gender equality in research and innovation	1
Science with and for Society - Cross-theme	1
Spreading excellence and widening participation - Cross-theme	1

Interestingly, social sciences participation is characterized by a galaxy of small projects where the OR partner play an important role (as measured by the % of the total EU contribution of the project going to the ORs organizations), demonstrating the perceived added-value of the expertise developed in the regions.

Table 10 Comparison of the size and role played in the projects

Thematics	Average EU contribution to the project	Average % of the EU contribution going to ORs partners
TWG1_Health, applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies	7 336 094,45 €	7,01%
TWG2_Social sciences and social innovation	3 536 139,55 €	11,95%
TWG3_Earth, space & universe sciences	5 392 942,15 €	7,19%
TWG4_Information and Communications Technology	4 600 904,06 €	6,65%
TWG5_Climate change and Energy transition	16 888 298,17 €	4,78%
TWG6_Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering	6 154 281,29 €	3,42%
TWG7_Biodiversity conservation and restoration	8 953 582,40 €	6,53%
TWG8_Marine sciences & technologies	5 892 477,18 €	4,23%
Total	6 665 546,60 €	7,72%

These elements demonstrate that social sciences represent a major asset for the Outermost regions in the coming Horizon Europe, in terms of scientific excellence, innovation and connections to the major networks. However, important margins of progression remain in many regions and fields, which can be attributed to both general obstacles identified under WP2 and specific situation of social scientists.

B. Global obstacles and levers to the participation

Despite the efforts dedicated by regional stakeholders to structure their regional R&I system and to develop support schemes for FP participation, the majority of the ORs present a participation in Horizon 2020 inferior to their potential. To explain this paradox, the 4 main determinants identified by the literature on FP participation have been scrutinized and tested extensively in each OR:

- connection to the most successful organizations that dominate the FP scene;
- the maturity, dynamic and effectiveness of the regional research and innovation system;
- the characteristics, strategy and policies of regional research and innovation organizations toward H2020;
- the individual factors which determines the will to apply or not to calls for projects (self-eviction mechanism) and the chance of success.

This analysis, based on an original methodology developed by Nexa⁶, highlighted three main inhibiting the participation of ORs participation in the Framework Programmes

- Inadequate public policies
- A poor connectivity of ORs to major European networks
- Participation in FP relies on few organizations and few people

For each of this barrier, the underlying causes and consequences were analyzed and synthetized in “problem tree” diagrams to facilitate their comprehension and propose a synthetic vision. Representatives from the ORs then joined in a Mutual Learning Event in October 2019 to design actions to address such issues. These following sections are extracted from the MLE report produced by Nexa for WP2.

1. Obstacle #1: European, national, regional public policies do not enough support the participation of outermost regions in the European Research Area

The first major challenge identified is related to public policies, for they have a systemic impact on regional innovation systems, on the organizations’ performance and

⁶ The methodology is available online [here](#).

strategies as well as on individual experience. They can also stimulate or inhibit the development of powerful research and innovation connections with major European stakeholders.

Yet, the ongoing public policies do not enough support the participation, because of three major phenomena:

- Knowledge economy remains at this stage a secondary priority in regions that are still in convergence. In many ORs, policy makers thus tend to privilege convergence and basic infrastructures development over a long-term effort for research and innovation. This inhibits the transition toward knowledge economy and increases the gap with European regions, that dedicate a larger share of their resources to research and innovation.
- The second obstacle stems from the gap between the Smart Specialization Strategies principles and objectives defined in each region and the effective allocation of ERDF funds. The two are frequently handled by different managing structures and the objectives of RIS3 are not necessarily embodied in the design of public intervention or selection process of the funded operations.
- The third issue stems from the substitution effect between structural funds and other EU competitive funds. The relatively large and easy accessible regional envelopes can deter stakeholders to submit proposals to Horizon 2020, leading to a reduced participation.

Figure 6 Diagram of the causes and sub causes leading to the lack of synergy in public policies

Following this analysis, the Forward partners defined the strategic and operational objectives to overcome the identified causes and subcauses. These elements were synthesized in a “solution tree” presented below. Such tree attaches a lot of importance on how to make the transition toward knowledge economy a desirable objective for policymakers and implement the synergy of funding objective. This concept designates the strategic use and coordination of available funding sources to support the sustained development of the regional innovation system and maximize “the impact of public investment” (Elena Perez et al. 2014), for instance by mobilizing ERDF to support infrastructure and capacity building, international mobility and networking activities that will increase the chance of FP participation.

Figure 7 Design and implement more effective policies and funding schemes to increase the performance of the regional R&I system and FP participation

2. Obstacle #2: A lack of strategy impedes the connection of ORs to major European networks

Because of their competitive nature, research and innovation Framework programmes are characterized by cumulative mechanisms leading to the concentration of the participation around a limited number of stakeholders, constituting according to Simen G. Enger (2017) “oligarchic networks”. Indeed, integrating a successful consortium necessitates to be known and identified as a valuable partner, which would bring a decisive added value to the project and increase the chances of funding. As a consequence, the connection to the members of

these dominant networks constitutes both a major obstacle and lever to increase the participation of the OR in Horizon 2020.

The analysis conducted under WP2 highlighted the fact that international connections remain unexploited as the consequence of three major issues:

- Regional research and innovation organizations are, for most of them, not globalized, meaning that they tend to operate on a regional basis and develop few connections with top players
- The fields of excellence of the OR enjoy a limited visibility at the EU level, which can reduce the chances of regional institutions to be considered as valuable partners that need to be included in consortia
- Despite existing relations with successful networks, the ORs seldom capitalize on these relations to develop H2020 projects.

Figure 8 Diagram of the causes and sub causes leading to the lack of integration in major European networks

Following this analysis, partners transformed the barrier into a priority lever and, for each cause and sub causes identified the appropriate action to take, leading to a solution tree. They particularly worked on two levers: accompany the “globalization” of regional organizations through an increased mobility and active lobbying; and setup a common communication strategy to reinforce the visibility of OR domains of excellence.

Figure 9 Priority n°2 - Create a collaborative strategy to integrate major European networks and create critical masses

3. Obstacle #3: Few organizations are involved in FP

In all the OR, a limited number of organizations are involved in Horizon 2020, leading to three main consequences:

- The regional level of participation remains low, in the absence of successful candidates
- The participation can become vulnerable, dependent on the will and ability of such structures to develop more projects and handle the existing
- The rest of the regional organizations remain out of the major research and innovation networks.

To explain such phenomenon, three main causes were identified:

- Regional innovation systems remain immature and still need to be structured to develop world/European competitive organizations
- Regional organizations are facing a lack of EU culture, and don't exploit the full potential of EU programmes which they do not know.
- Members of these institutions frequently hesitate to engage in FP, because they are not encouraged to and supported in the best possible ways.

Figure 10 Diagram of the causes and sub causes leading to the concentration of FP participation in few organizations in OR

To overcome these barriers, the Forward partners defined levers to increase the capacity of regional organization to engage in FP, their level of European culture and offer to their personnel the best possible environment for project development and management.

Figure 11 : Priority n°3 - Foster the FP-shift in R&I organizations

C. Individual barriers and expectations of Social Sciences group's members

Besides the systemic obstacles presented above, individual representations, capacities and strategies can exercise a major influence on the FP performance of an organization or a region. To better understand potential knowledge and capacities gaps, beliefs, fears and intrinsic motivational levers expressed by stakeholders, Nexa thus launched an online survey among the social sciences group members. 38 of the 131 registered members answered the questionnaire.

1. International connectivity

The respondents were asked to indicate whether they were connected to partners in continental Europe, in ORs, in their regional basins or elsewhere and to describe the strength of their partnership⁷ 26 % of them have no international networks, while 65% are connected with continental European partners in advanced collaboration (64% of the collaborations belonged to stage 2 to 5). 42% of the respondents are connected with partners in their regional basins and mainly in soft partnerships.

⁷ The scale of "Partnership strength" is inspired from Rakhmatullin et al. "Transnational cooperation and value chains" in Gianelle et al. *Implementing Smart Specialisation Strategies. A handbook*. 2016.

Figure 12 International connectivity and level of strength of the partnerships

These results demonstrate a real potential of existing collaboration to develop FP projects, if these partners were to be involved in existing successful consortia. However, this potential remains relatively under-utilized since only 9 respondents have already been involved in an FP project (see next section).

2. EU knowledge and experience

The group is characterized by a modest level of EU experience and a relative theoretical rather than practical knowledge of the Framework Programmes. Only 9 people (23%) have already been involved in a FP project (as coordinator or partner). Moreover, if almost 50% of the respondents state to be familiar with "H2020 pillars" or "NCP", only 1 on 5 have already heard of major H2020-project development tools (such as Cordis or participant portal), that are frequently used by successful applicants.

Figure 13 FP project experience

Figure 14 FP practices and knowledge

3. Analysis of self-selection behaviors

15 statements were tested to better understand the obstacles perceived by the group members.

First, the results confirm that the majority of the respondents are willing to collaborate at EU level (>95%). Interestingly, contrary to a common stance affirming that the calls for projects launched under Horizon 2020 do not match the ORs fields of expertise, the respondents do not feel excluded from the programming. Indeed, only 21% state that their research domains do not have any interest for Europeans, and only 26% claim that FP only fund applied

research. Moreover, only 34% of the respondents think that their research is not competitive enough for FP, showing a high opinion of one's scientific quality. The most important obstacle lies in the perceived "return on investment" of applications (76% of the respondents indicate that the efforts to be in EU projects are too important compared to the chances of success). Aware of the level of competition (one respondent on 2 thinks that "H2020 is mainly for built big organizations") and affected by the lack of knowledge, networks, time and support, many respondents present a classic self-selection pattern, and decide not to apply. This is also confirmed by the free statements given by the respondents. However and quite interestingly, few of them link this lack of resources to the strategy of their organizations.

Figure 15 Perception of the obstacles and levers

4. Levers of motivation and ambition

To better capture the intrinsic drivers of Social Sciences stakeholders, the respondents were invited to indicate whether the suggested levers constitute (or not) motives for them to participate in Horizon Europe projects. If all propositions received positive feedbacks (from 68 to 92% of adhesion), the "Collective" and "Goal oriented" levers look more acclaimed than the others.

Figure 16 % of adhesion to the suggested motives

Figure 17 Analysis of Motives

Interestingly, levers which are related to funding and to the competition discourse received less approval than the others (“Access to funding”, “To be more competitive in your field”, “To challenge yourself”).

The survey also measured the personal ambition of the respondents. 66% of them - 25 people - intend to submit at least a project in the next programming (68% of them targeting one project and as a partner) and 76% set as an objective to get funded (29 people). These results show that the stakeholders are intrinsically motivated and feel rather confident in terms of chance of success.

Figure 18 Personal objectives in terms of submission

Figure 19 Personal objectives in terms of success

5. Expectations

Finally, the specific expectations of the respondents toward this working group and action plan were also collected. 23 actions, organized within 6 categories, were submitted to the group's prioritization:

- Boosting your connectivity with partners
- Developing your interest in participating in EU projects
- Developing your technical skills
- Developing your other soft skills
- Anticipating future calls for proposals
- Improving ORs social sciences visibility towards EU partners

The analysis shows that the respondents principally look for :

- technical training - particularly to identify their added value at EU level, to better understand EU policies in their respective fields of research, as well as to better know how to define Impacts of research –
- networking within ORs and with continental EU partners. Importantly, the connection with geographical basins as well as the development of other (soft) skills are not high-priority actions for the group.

Figure 20 Expectations from respondents regarding the Forward Working Group

III. ACTION PLAN FOR ORS SOCIAL SCIENCES

Considering the regional R&I characteristics and dynamics in each OR, the "territorial experience" of the R&I ecosystems in terms of FP participation, the FP knowledge, experience and ambition of the social sciences group members, and the forthcoming opportunities in Horizon Europe, the ambition of the Social Sciences R&I group is to address European and OR's social challenges through the collaborative production of knowledge and solutions, supported by a stronger participation in the European Research Area and the associated Horizon Europe programme.

With respect to the regional diversity, our objective regarding Horizon Europe is to:

Systematize and accelerate the dynamics of more advanced regions: the Azores, the Canary Islands, Madeira,

- Increase the participation of starting regions: Guadeloupe, Guyane, La Reunion, Martinique,
- Develop the participation of new coming regions: Mayotte, Saint-Martin.

To reach this challenging and realistic ambition, the following action plan foresees two strategic objectives supported by a transversal support action:

- To develop R&I collaboration within ORs (A)
- To turn the Working group into an incubator for Horizon Europe projects (B)

To ensure the sustainability of the action plan, we propose adopt a distributed coordination system (C) to mobilize and mutualize existing resources in the different regions and to identify European funding sources.

A. Develop R&I collaboration within ORs

The knowledge economy paradigm has changed the perception of small scales and "isolated" economies. Based on information and immateriality rather than mass consumption and economy of scale, it gives small economies the opportunity to develop singular and knowledge-intensive activities for niche markets. ORs have therefore invested to structure their regional R&I system. However, many challenges remain acute: constitution of critical

masses, R&I policies design, implementation and evaluation, innovation diffusion, industrial transition, effective entrepreneurial discovery process, etc.

The Forward Social Sciences working group represents a unique opportunity to bring together researchers and entrepreneurs around the development of knowledge economy in ORs. To do so, the first strategic objective aims at creating the conditions for research collaboration, through two specific objectives:

- To mobilize Humanities and Social sciences to understand and boost R&I in ORs
- To build critical masses on targeted R&I fields in Social Sciences

1. Mobilize Humanities and Social sciences to understand and boost R&I in ORs

As shown by the diagnosis performed under Forward work package 2, the scientific literature on regional research and innovation systems in the Outermost Regions remains so far limited. This constitutes a major challenge to design efficient public policies and action, at regional, national and European level. Mobilizing the Research efforts from ORs to better understand the genealogy of these systems, their dynamics and their performance, and elaborate levers to boost R&I would therefore be a great step forward for ORs stakeholders and policy-makers.

To implement this specific objective, three priority actions are identified:

action 1: Develop an original expertise on small and/or remote regional R&I systems

action 2: Mobilize the knowledge produced to contribute to the design and implementation of regional, national and European policies regarding R&I in the OR, such as Research Excellence, Innovation Capacities, Smart Specialization, Horizon Europe participation, etc.

action 3: Encourage the use of Responsible Research and Innovation principles - which *implies that societal actors (researchers, citizens, policy makers, business, third sector organizations, etc.) work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society* - in the Social Sciences Research & Innovation fields

2. Build critical masses (including NGO) on targeted R&I fields to contribute to the European Research Area

Due to their singular position, history, and socio-political trajectories, the outermost regions have coped, for decades, with social issues that have now become central on the global scene, such as social cohesion and inclusion, multiculturalism, poverty prevention, rural development, sustainable economies, etc. Separately, outermost regions have developed knowledge, skills and specific added value in topics at the heart of current and future European policies. Together, the ORs can increase the volume and excellence of their research activities and develop innovative and sustainable solutions that not only address their challenges but also the needs of other regions.

The second specific objective is thus to build critical masses on a limited number of R&I fields. Such fields will be identified according to the R&I keywords (as declared by the social sciences group's members in the profiling survey) and their potential contribution to Horizon Europe themes and calls, as well as to the Ten Core Issues in Socio-Economic Research as defined by the EC.

This specific objective is supported by two priority actions:

action 4: Map priority fields/research issues with EU added value, and animate dedicated subgroups that will implement a networking plan to increase the connections and cooperation between the ORs.

action 5: Raise awareness on ORs stakeholders and initiatives through the conception and dissemination of a directory of stakeholders, a handbook of inspiring projects and an observatory of EU projects on humanities and social sciences involving ORs

B. Turn the Social Sciences R&I group into an incubator for Horizon Europe projects

Because of their collaborative and competitive nature, Framework programmes are characterized by a strong concentration, materialized by the extensive domination of a few stakeholders, who benefit from the cumulative advantages induced by prior participation.

Interviews undertaken during Forward diagnosis as well as the results from the Social Sciences group's survey show that stakeholders are aware of the level of competition and of the effort needed to develop performant networks. They also confirm the existence of self-eviction mechanisms, choosing not to apply, because they feel either "not as good as other", lacking knowledge about the programmes, or cannot find the appropriate support from their organization or regional services in charge of FP development.

It is therefore critical to develop a synergic support programme, regionally-grounded with interregional joint activities, based on capacity building, connexion strategy and professional support to develop proposals. The objective here is to increase the willingness and capacity of stakeholders to get in and build successful projects.

To turn the Forward Social Sciences group into an incubator for FP projects, which makes the participation desirable and easy, three specific objectives are designed:

- Define and implement a joint capacity-building programme for Social Sciences between ORs
- Connect with EU dynamic organization in domains of expertise
- Detect project opportunities and support the development of proposals

1. Define and implement a joint capacity-building programme for Social Sciences between ORs

The Forward diagnosis has shown a high heterogeneity in terms of participation in the FP but also in terms of support services; some regions lacking proper tools. To increase social scientists participation in all ORs, it is thus proposed to bring regional forces together into a joint programme dedicated to Social Sciences stakeholders, allowing newcomers regions to benefit from more advanced ones.

To be efficient, this programme will have to take into account the specific needs of social sciences stakeholders (defining impacts of the research, adapted technology-readiness level,

multidisciplinary approaches) and should also take into consideration the European Union policies⁸ on the subject.

This specific objective is supported by one priority action :

action 7: Identify volunteer institutions in all ORs to co-create and implement a joint programme aiming at empowering Social Sciences R&I stakeholders, according to their specific FP knowledge and experiences (through activities such as webinars to demystify Horizon European, provision of easy-to-use starting tools, webinars to share good practices, testimonials...)

2. Connect with EU dynamic organizations in domains of expertise

"Newcomers to European research, seeking funding without well-developed networks and with no prior experience, are likely to fail" (Enger 2017). To enter the "FP club", researchers and innovators must first connect with EU dynamic organizations.

To reach this specific objective, the group will implement the following priority action:

action 8 : Identify the main EU champions in the R&I fields (as defined in action 5) and implement activities to start collaborations (online meetings to promote the ORs expertise, for instance)

3. Detect opportunities and support the development of proposals

Regular participants in FP do anticipate the publication of calls in their research domains. Through NCP, national thematic groups and research networks, they suggest topics to the EC and are informed, in advance, of the forthcoming calls. They also benefit from the professional support of their Europe services to ensure the development of the most competitive proposals, receiving strategic advice and feedbacks from their support team and assigning them technical tasks.

⁸ Integration of social sciences and humanities in Horizon 2020, European Commission, 2020

To develop such strategic approaches within the Forward social sciences group, two actions will be implemented:

- **action 9:** Examine the workprogrammes and organize Ideation workshops in each sub groups (defined in action 5)
- **action 10:** Provide expert support all along the project development cycle: from the proposal ideas to the negotiation phase after selection; this action requests coordination between ORs regional support organizations.

C. Build long-term perspective through a distributed coordination system

Finally, to ensure the implementation and long-term activities of the Forward Social Sciences Action plan, a dedicated transversal support action is foreseen. Based on a call for volunteers, this action will start with the definition of a group's coordination system which ensures members' adhesion and commitment, but also the effective implementation of the priority actions by sharing responsibilities among members.

To align on European standards in collaborative research management and get knowledge on promising tools for ORs researchers, the coordination system will be inspired from the COST actions management system⁹. At this stage (to be discussed with the group's members), the management structure could be set up as follows:

- A management committee (MC), composed of 1 representative per OR and in charge of:
 - defining the group's strategy, policy, rules and memberships
 - defining the working groups and composition
 - performing the monitoring and reporting duties

⁹ https://www.cost.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/COST-013-19-Guidelines_Action_management_monitoring_assessment_Ver2019.06.pdf

- Working groups (WG), composed of all interested members, in charge of performing the tasks required in the action plan and led by voluntary leader and vice-leader, responsible for coordinating and managing actions assigned to the WG :
 - WG 1 - Mobilize Humanities and Social sciences to understand and boost R&I in ORs
 - WG 2 - Build critical masses (including NGO) on targeted R&I fields to contribute to the European Research Area
 - WG 3 - FP incubator
- Thematic committees composed of all interested members and led by voluntary by voluntary leader and vice-leader (to be defined within action 5)
- A general assembly which brings together all members to share the group's progress and achievements

ANNEX I

Table 11 Research & Innovation Keywords describing the members' expertise

Fields	Number
Tourism	24
Innovation	19
Environment	17
Social innovation	17
Education	14
ICT	13
Entrepreneurship	10
Institutions/policies	7
Inequality	5
Urban planning	4
Agriculture	3
Business	3
Circular economy	3
Employment	3
Gender	3
Health	3
Finance	2
Marine	2
Marketing	2
Migration	2
Participatory science	2
Poverty	2
+ a serie of keywords with only 1 representant	17

Figure 21 Interests in Horizon Europe (Themes showing interest from more than 9 respondents)

Table 12 Ten Core Issues in Socio-Economic Research in EU Member States ¹⁰

Core Issues	Sub-Topics
Democracy	Governance, Institutions, Citizenship, Electoral Behaviour, Political Parties, Values, Role of State/Regional, National and European Level.
Economic Performance	Employment, Labour Markets Financial Markets, Fiscal Policy, New Economic and Work Models, Firms' Behaviour Globalisation economic consequences
European Development	European Union, Enlargement, European Culture, European History, Europe and Rest of the World.
Environment	Sustainable Development & Human Behaviour, Economic Mechanisms/Incentives, International Agreements/ Regulations, Nature and Society.
Health	Demographic and Household Change, Ageing, Youth, Lifestyle (Work and Leisure), Individual
	Life-Course Analysis, Living Conditions. Health Care delivery
Knowledge & Learning	Knowledge Society, Education & Training, Life- long Learning, ICT development & impacts, Media, Languages
Multi-Ethnic Societies	Identity, Migration, Racial Discrimination, Xenophobia Globalisation- social and cultural consequences
Quality of Life	Urban/Rural ñ Sustainable Communities, Cultural Heritage, Transport & Mobility, Crime, Public Safety & Security.
Science, Technology & Innovation	Science and Society, Ethics, Public Understanding of Science, Science Policy, History of Science.
Welfare State	Social Welfare and Social Security Pensions,
	Social Capital, Social Cohesion, Poverty & Exclusion

¹⁰ Extracted from "Implementation of the European Research Area in the Social and Human Sciences", European commission, 2003.

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TWG3: Earth Science, Space and Universe Science

**Forward project Thematic Working
Groups
TWG3 - Earth Science, Space and Universe
Science**

Draft proposal of Action Plan

11/03/2021

Version 1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 824550

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Introduction

The Action Plan (AP) for the Thematic Working Group 3 (TWG3), dedicated to the Earth, Space and Universe Sciences, is designed as a common vision co-created in a bottom up methodological approach by the TWG3 Members, during online and offline work (from January to March 2021). The AP construction was lead by a subcoordinator, an expert and high profile person in the thematic of the group, Eng. Pedro Silva, from AIRCenter (Azores, Portugal), supported by his team: Eng. Rui Martins (AIRCenter) and Eng. Mariana Ávila, as deputies, as well as Lina Silveira (FRCT), Marta Vergilio (FRCT) and Eduardo Braga (CCIA), as facilitators.

The TWG's main goal is to contribute to the advance/increase of the participation of ORs in Framework Programs – e.g. Horizon Europe (2021-2027) – and include concrete and achievable common objectives/actions/tasks in the AP - to be implement by TWG3 Members, with the support of the managing team, mentioned above and lead by Eng. Pedro Silva.

Within the Forward project, the TWGs are created as a tool enhancing the potential of collaboration and networking in a common acknowledgement. The AP includes a guide of activities to implement with the goal of engaging the TWG3 Members in the implementation of this common work plan.

It is expected that this TWG, as well all the other seven, to last during and beyond the duration of FORWARD project (December 2021), as a seed of this project to the benefit of its Members. This tool will support: creating critical mass and networking; promoting the ORs R&I community of experts participation in FP; promoting of ORs excellence in science and; the awareness of its added value.

Members profile

TWG3 profile evolution

As each TWG is heterogeneous, with the integration of OR experts and representatives from different fields of expertise and differentiated academic and professional backgrounds, the challenge is to bring together and find common interests to define the activities that integrate the AP. This is why it is important to understand the composition of this TWG, as well as its evolution, to keep optimal working conditions, from the work platform to the methodology, priorities, actions and the promotion of a sustainable engagement.

The TWG3 composition has changed along the process of construction of the Action Plan, from January to March 2021. This evolution is important to understand as the Action Plan is a product of a co-constructive process and therefore it reflects the profile of its Members.

Profile in January 2021

The TWG3 had its Kick off with an online event on January 18th, with 19 Members enrolled at that time, from the seven Outermost regions, except from Mayotte and Saint Martin. Having the most representation from Canary Islands and Azores, with four participants each, followed by Reunion Island and Guadalupe, with three participants each, as illustrated in Figure 1.

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Figure 1 Number of enrolled Members in TWG3, per Region in January 2021.

The affiliation of TWG3 Members in January 2021 is dominated by Universities, with almost half the members affiliated to higher education institutions (nine Members), followed by R&I Institutions (four Members) as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Number of TWG3 Members per affiliation in January 2021.

The form provided at the time of registration of Members in each TWG allowed the construction of a word cloud, which helped to illustrate and highlight the dominating words related to the fields of expertise of the Members in this TWG. The words “PBH’s”,

Figure 4 TWG3 Members skills in participating in Framework programs, from January 2021.

Profile in March 2021

The TWG Members' origin changed along the process and, in March 2021, the group has increased in number of enrolled Members, from 19 to 27 Members (almost double, as illustrated in Figure 5).

The dominating region is now Madeira, with seven Members. The biggest difference is that the group ended up having representatives from the nine ORs, even if just one from French Guiana, one from Saint Martin and one from Mayotte (Figure 5).

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Figure 5 Number of enrolled Members in TWG3, per Region, in March 2021.

The TWG3 Members, in March, still maintain their main affiliation in Universities (n=12), as illustrated in Figure 6, followed by R&D Institutions (n=8) and Public Administration (n=3). The growth of the group has also resulted in a wider diversity of affiliations, although the main profile of the TWG3 are academics. It is relevant, also, to highlight that we have also a quite diverse representation in the private/entrepreneurship sector, taking in to account the whole group, with representatives from SME's, Business Incubator/Innovation Center and Large company that contribute with a diverse vision of the thematic.

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Figure 6 TWG3 Members affiliation up until the enrolled members in March 2021.

In terms of dominating words related to the fields of expertise of the Members enrolled in March comparatively to the ones that started in January in this TWG, dominating words are, as the most frequent, the “PBHs” still remains relevant, as well as “remote” and “sensing”, bit we can also see other words, as “entrepreneurship” and “programming” that did not had a highlight before,

Figure 7 Words of expertise chosen by the TWG3 Members in March 2021

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In terms of experience and knowledge in Framework Programs, the TWG3 group, in March 2021, has more Members with high level (from 12 in January to 15 in March) with experience in writing proposals in H2020. Although we have two more Members in March that declared to have a very low level of skills in writing proposal, the biggest difference in this category is that we have three new members that declare to have very low level of skills in writing proposals. A category we did not had in January, as you can see from Figure 4 to Figure 7.

When we analyze the networking skills, the biggest difference is in the low level skills category, that raised from four to nine members declaring this lack of skill.

The skills in the area of Framework Programs participation have increased in the low skills category from seven to 11 members affirming they lack this skill. The Members that indicated to have very high skills in FP participation has remained the same, in the number of 3. The new configuration of skills of the TWG3 Members can be analyzed in Figure 8.

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Figure 8 TWG3 Members Skills to participate in Framework programs, from March 2021.

This diverse composition of Members lead to an Action Plan in which everyone could identify their vision and needs. It was a challenge, but the sub-coordinator was conscience and, therefore, we have applied a diverse methodology that integrated everyone and promoted online and offline participation.

Methodology

The starting point for the TWG3 was the methodology indicated by the FORWARD WP3 leader, divided into three stages: 1) the Kick off; 2) the preparation of the Action Plan; 3) and the implementation of the plan as a goal. (Figure 9).

Figure 9 Action Plan development methodology for TWG's, adjusted to the TWG3 (Source: WP3 TWG Guidelines and TWG3 Workshop III presentation)

The methodology implemented during the co-construction of the Action Plan followed a logic of online work, during the three Workshops organized. These Workshops were implemented as work meetings and the starting point of a second stage of work, as an offline exchange of ideas. This duality between the workshops and offline work, according to the sub-coordinator orientation, allowed the group exchange of ideas to be more inclusive and allow that every Members had the opportunity to collaborate.

In the first Workshop (on the 5th February), it was presented the inputs concerning the aspects to be addressed in each of the four components of the SWOT matrix, so it could be prioritized. After prioritizing through an online form, participants gave their feedback about the objectives to establish as indicators to overcome each issue mentioned.

Then, during the second Workshop (on the 24th February), the TWG3 was distributed in two subgroups, each one simultaneously developing a brainstorming session designated to define and discuss the specific actions to implement, in order to address the different objectives highlighted in the previously workshops: Sub-group 1 – Strategic positioning; Sub-group 2 – OR's Capacitation (Table 1).

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Table 1 Sub-groups created during the second workshop to brainstorming about the actions that should be included in the Action Plan.

Sub Group 1 – Strategic Positioning	Sub Group 2 – OR's Capacitation
1. Extreme difficulty for most OR's institutions to get involved in competitive consortia in FP-funded calls for projects in the domain of TWG3	1. Existence of robust and relevant operational/monitoring infrastructures in OR's at the Earth's coastal/marine, terrestrial, atmospheric components and Space Observation/Monitoring levels
2. Blue Economy and Copernicus program assumed as flagships initiatives by the EU	2. Lack of EU funding to maintain/improve the (already existing) relevant operational/monitoring infrastructures in OR's at the Earth's coastal/marine, terrestrial, atmospheric components and Space Observation/Monitoring levels
3. EU Outermost Regions and Overseas Territories seen as strategic areas to test, implement and strengthen EU's cohesion and sustainability policies	3. Lack of qualified and available human resources in some key areas related to the domain of TWG3, in each OR
4. Islands (as most ORs are) globally assumed as "Living Labs" - Excellent geographic location, islands are amazing case studies for developing new scientific knowledge	4. Lack of motivation/resources causing high difficulty in involving in an EU-funded (FP) application different relevant ORs actors (I&D sector, Public Administration, Private Sector and further relevant Stakeholders).
5. Long-term established collaborations with other research groups outside ORs	5. Closer proximity/familiarity between I&D sector (Public and Private), Public Administration, Private Sector and further relevant Stakeholders in ORs
6. Very high (scientific/technical) specificity and competitiveness of many topics of FP-funded calls for projects in the domain of TWG3 makes unviable/unaffordable the participation of most OR's institutions	6. COVID-19 pandemic can limit the strengthening of the networks and development of the work in the field
7. Small dimension and influence of most OR's institutions acting in the domain of TWG3:	

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 2021-2027
 Horizon Europe
 Research and Innovation
 Programme
 Grant Agreement No. 101019150

The discussion in the subgroups were lead by the sub-coordinator and the deputy, that were the moderators contextualizing the contribution in a SMART analyzes context¹. Offline, it was sent the conclusions and it was requested inputs, to follow up in the next Workshop.

Lastly, the third Workshop (on the 4th March) was a conclusion of the process, as it gave the opportunity for the Members to exchange ideas, in order to determine the specifics of each task, intended to surpass certain objectives, list the actions and request Members to be in charge of the actions to be implemented, as well as others points of the Action Plan. This methodology was guided by a main question: “How can the TWG7 contribute to increase the participation of the OR’s in Framework Programs - Horizon Europe (2021-2027)?”, as a guiding point to propose and develop actions to integrate the TWG3 Action Plan. The sub-coordinator oriented the conversation and, at the end, the proposals were included and the AP shared with the Members to request more inputs.

¹ S.M.A.R.T. is an acronym that is used to guide the development of measurable goals: Specific; Measurable; Achievable; Realistic; Time bound

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Figure 10 Methodology to achieve the Action Plan for TWG3, as a conclusion and wider image of the roadmap towards the co-creation of the AP

Action Plan guidelines and challenges

The Action Plan orientation/guidelines to take into account when defining the actions/tasks for its implementation are the following:

- ✓ Adapt the goal to apply to specific measures that can be verified and measured;
- ✓ Have in mind that the group has only 12 months to implement (target short, medium and long time actions and their articulation in time), within and beyond the FORWARD project;
- ✓ Actions must be attained through the joint forces of the TWG3 members: *much more can be achieved by collaboration than competition*;
- ✓ Make full use of the potential and resources that the TWG3 Members have together, in terms of capacity sharing, networking, experience and knowledge;
- ✓ No budget is allocated to the TWG's actions;
- ✓ Empower the group by strengthen the collaboration between the Members, the TWG's and other networks that you can identify as relevant to the TWG3 goals.

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These guidelines helped TWG3 to keep focused on goals and define, together, actions that were possible to implement taking into account that this is a non-financed group of volunteer experts. This was also a chance to think “out of the box” and focus the actions definition solely on the *added value* of the expertise and joint knowledge that the TWG3 is able to have. It has been also a challenge, along the process, to keep the Members engaged by solely appealing to a common recognition of the importance and advantages of participating in the TWG. Therefore, it was important and still is important to reinforce along the Workshop and activities to integrate in the AP the advantages of the network opportunities, mutual creation of sources of information that can be of an added value for its members and knowledge transfer, which that can bring, as well, exchange of experiences in FP.

The Action Plan explained

Within the framework of increasing OR participation on coming European FP funding opportunities, the Action Plan focuses on specific actions in two main lines: 1) enabling Strategic Positioning of the OR by defining common agendas and priorities, identifying synergies and better coordinate OR interest representation in the EC and 2) Build Capacity by stimulating OR organizations to lead projects and increase networking efforts in areas that build upon existing capacity while carrying consultation between industry and public entities.

This Action Plan was developed based on the joint vision of the partners involved in this TWG and translated into actions considered as main priorities that can lead to an increase of the OR participation on coming European FP funding opportunities. These actions are a result of the common understanding of what is considered as strengths of weaknesses common to the OR in the topic of Earth Science, Space and Universe.

Vision and closure notes

Our vision for the coming decade is to monitor and decisively contribute to reach the UN sustainable development goals, summarized in 3 main global challenges: climate change, digital transformation and population dynamics. This should be done through

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an international, distributed and collaborative network and contribute to foster job creation and knowledge driven economic development based on scientific excellence. In order to do so, OR should explore its strengths, such as those associated with its geographic location, the recognition as living labs, existing operational monitoring infrastructures, qualified human resources and proximity between I&D sector (Public and Private), the Public Administration, Private Sector and further relevant stakeholders.

The FP funding opportunities are excellent tools to bring together experts from different parts of the world that share the same vision and that are willing to work together in order to contribute to the UN sustainable development goals. However, sometimes these collaborations are not maintained beyond the duration of an action/project and are not explored in other areas. Also, in some cases the institutions are not open to new collaborations with different partners.

For all of the reasons described above, this TWG believes that only joining, strengthening and creating new efforts through scientific collaborations between the OR can lead to a wider vision of what is needed and can be developed for tackling the 3 main global challenges.

TWG4: Information and Communication Technologies

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550.

TWG4 – Information and Communication Technologies

Thematic Action Plan

SUB-COORDINATOR	Martine Collard	(University of Antilles)
DEPUTY	Wilfried Segretier	(INRAE)
FACILITATOR	Antony Nobour	(CTM)
CO-FACILITATOR	Jean-François DORVILLE	(SYNERGÎLE)

This report describes steps, discussions and conclusions held with the members of the group to come up with the action plan to be implemented during next months.

Profile of the members

The profiles of the member of the Thematic Working Group IV Information and Communications Technology is mainly academic 40%, 24% come from SME, 7% from public administration the rest come from social society and NGO.

Most of the members, 70% come from Madeira, Canaries Island, and the Azores. Mayotte is the only OR without a representative.

44 H2020 projects have been identified with ORs members mainly coming from Canarias islands and Madeira. The important point is Small and Medium Enterprises are leaders in EU-FP funding projects in the thematic with 10 SMEs involved in 32 H2020 projects.

The members have declared 60 peer review papers, 12 software, 2 patterns, 16 Master / PhD, and 18 projects during the last 5 years.

During the phase of co-creation, the number of members increases from 35 to 49 that allows insuring a number of participants during the meeting higher than 18. The number of active members (answering to emails and participant to the meetings) has been evaluated to 25 persons.

Potential areas in ICT were evaluated by survey and the members proposed Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, Big Data, and Machine Learning as areas of innovation of the ORs. The innovative solutions have also been sorted and place first Smart Cities followed by Health, Tourism, Education, Energy transition, and Climate and Weather.

Scheduling

As suggested, after the Kick-off meeting it was organized four workshops and we had to hold an additional workshop to define a final action plan.

In brief

- **On Tuesday January 12th 2021 - *Kick-Off Meeting***, the session was spent in a round table discussion and presentation of the method.
- **On Tuesday January 19th 2021 - *Workshop 1***, the session was spent in a discussion on three preliminary objectives.
- **On Tuesday January 26th 2021 -*Workshop 2***, the session was spent in brainstorming to determine more precisely specific objectives and actions to achieve them.
- **On Tuesday February 2nd 2021: *Workshop 3***, the session was spent in analyzing the result of the survey conducted into the group to organize future actions according to four sub-objective branches

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- **On Tuesday February 9th 2021: *Workshop 4***, the session was spent in defining actions for each branch.
- **On Tuesday February 23rd 2021: *Workshop 5*** the session was spent in analyzing the result of the survey conducted into the group in sub-groups and in defining the final action plan.

Progression of the discussions throughout the meetings

Kick-Off Meeting

Step summary: The round table already showed a high level of diversity into the group both in the areas of research in computer science and in the preferred areas of application.

Workshop 1

Step summary: Keeping in mind that our overall objective was "to rise our capacity to submit and win EU FP calls", we followed two lines of work: 1) Focusing on useful ICT areas 2) Focusing on relevant application domains.

Thus, three specific objectives based on the on-line form filled by the members were discussed without being sorted:

1) Designing ICT tools required for an innovative solution in each application

domain as Health, Smart cities, Tourism or ... in our ORs

2) Designing an innovative ICT framework as a generic top layer applicable to

several application areas (as health, tourism, ...) in our ORs

Example : data management, e-services, cybersecurity, ...

3) Conducting a critical analysis of our (TWG4 members) complementarities with a

view to responding to an EU call for our ORs: strengths and needs.

A SWOT analysis was applied and showed weaknesses of Objective 3)

Workshop 2

Step summary:

Since the Objective 3) seems finally to overlap Objective 1), two objectives were selected only:

- 1) To rise our capacity of designing an innovative ICT framework as a generic top layer applicable to several application areas (as health, tourism, ...) in our ORs
- 2) To rise our capacity of designing ICT tools required for an innovative solution in each application domain (Health, Smart cities, Tourism, ...) in our ORs.

The two objectives were declined in two branches of actions.

It was also discussed the idea to identify sub-groups in the TWG that would each focus on a specific domain.

A survey was decided to be conducted to determine in which branch (line of work) the TWG4 members want to be involved to collect an action plan.

The Miro board (www.miro.com) with the how-how diagram was shared with the members to harvest their contributions.

Workshop 3

Step summary: According to the survey conducted into the thematic working group, we discussed the two more popular sub-objectives and the determination of the tasks associated:

To reach Objective 1)

1.1. Building a precise map of our areas of expertise in ICT - Skills, Complementary points

To reach Objective 2)

2.1. Evaluating relevant ICT application domains in ORs

The list of tasks in each sub-objective was shared with the members to complete them on Teams Microsoft and Google Drive

1.1 Building a precise map of our areas of expertise in ICT - Skills, Complementary points - Do we have to complete them?

Defining the goal: what are the deliverables (map)

Define a) the information to store and display b) the data structure c) how to display it

Take a taxonomy as reference

Proceed up down to develop the map

The resulting map should be evolutive, interactive and help to find partners to answer to calls

The map should include connections between entities

Defining a timeline to deliver the map

Carrying out a detailed survey for TWG members on 1) their research areas, skills, interests 2) the application domains they worked on

Define the level of granularity of the information we want to collect

First study previous answers each member gave: build a first map

List complementary questions to ask to members

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Identify clusters of collaboration on sub fields

Identify overlapping fields

Highlight the complementary aspects in the TWG

Share the files into the group for filling information

Drawing the map of ICT areas covered in the TWG with all criteria

Define the knowledge structure

Identifying which sub-area is missing and look for new members in our regions

Organizing colloquiums on recent research fields and technologies

Defining strategies to find other people related to the WG

2.1 Evaluating relevant ICT application domains in ORs

Carrying out a detailed survey inside the TWG on potential OR application domains in which innovation is expected using ICT

First establish a summary of our previous answers

Define the granularity level of the information we want to collect

Build a specific form to be filled out by members (especially new ones)

Make sure to be consistent with OR specificities

Proceed by iteration

Identifying professionals in our Ors

Build a specific survey for them

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Compare the answers with objective 1.1 results

Identifying innovative IC tools already implemented in our Ors

Conducting a discussion with other target TWG - Which ones?

Workshop 4

Step summary: We discussed the two other sub-objectives and the determination of the tasks associated:

To reach Objective 1)

1.2 Listing application domains addressed in our applied researches and regions?

What was our involvement? (from objective 1. Rise our capacity of Designing an innovative ICT framework as a generic top layer applicable to several application areas (as health, tourism, ...) in our Ors)

To reach Objective 2)

1.2 Collecting requirements in ICT tools per key domain - Regions that are concerned (from objective 2. Rise our capacity of Designing ICT tools required for an innovative solution in each application domain (Health, Smart cities, Tourism, ...) in our ORs Map)

1.2 Listing application domains addressed in our applied researches and regions?

For each application domain addressed in the TWG, define criteria able to reflect

1) the involvement in this area 2) acquired skills and knowledge

Draw the map of ICT domains addressed in the TWG with all criteria

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Kind of extension could be conducted easily to other of our regions?

2.2 Collecting requirements in ICT tools per key domain - Regions that are concerned'

Target precise relevant appl. domains to focus on

Use the EU calls as a reference

Make sure that Innovation is important

Conduct a discussion with other target TWG - Which ones?

Workshop 5

Step summary: The Action Plan was validated with two (2) sub-objectives and four (4) main actions

Two sub-objectives

1. Rise our capacity of Designing an innovative ICT framework as a generic top layer applicable to several application areas;

Main actions:

- Building a precise map of our areas of expertise in ICT - Skills, Complementary points
- Listing application domains addressed in our applied researches and regions

2. Rise our capacity of Designing ICT tools required for an innovative solution in some given application domains.

Main actions:

- Evaluating relevant ICT application domains in ORs
- Collecting requirements in ICT tools per key domain

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- The two actions to achieve Objective 1) will be conducted by a 1st sub-group.
- The two last actions will be applied in other 7 sub-groups:
 2. SMART CITIES and TOURISM
 3. e-SERVICES
 4. AI AND DATA SCIENCE
 5. CYBERSECURITY
 6. ENVIRONMENTAL AND NATURAL RESOURCE SECURITY / NATURAL HAZARDS
 7. HEALTHCARE DELIVERY SYSTEMS / ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH
 8. OCEAN and CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

Pairs were selected to lead the sub-groups. The list of sub-groups will circulate to see if there are, other candidates.

TWG5: Climate change and Energy Transition

FORWARD

Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost
Regions

WP3 • Co-creation and implementation of
thematic groups

Action Plan for
Climate change and Energy Transition
(TWG5)

March 23th 2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and
innovation

Programme under grant agreement N° 824550

Project Acronym	FORWARD
Project name	Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions
Grant agreement n°	824550
Project type	Coordination and Support action
Start date - End Date	01/06/2019 - 30/06/2022
Workpackage	WP3
Deliverable name	Action Plan for Climate change and Energy Transition (TWG5)
Responsible partner for the WP and tasks	ITC & Synergîle
Responsible partner for the document	ARDITI Madeira
Type of document	Action plan
Dissemination level	Public
Contributors	Lúcio Quintal (ARDITI) Claudio Mantero (Horários do Funchal) TWG5 members
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1 Aim of this Action Plan

This action plan for the TWG5 is a guide for the activities to implement, embracing the different group members' interests, clarifying the roles, the expected outputs and the common work plan. Once the first version is ready and agreed with the leading group, everyone is expected to participate in its further construction and update, so that it becomes clear to all the participants how to guide and proceed in future TWG5 activities.

1.1 Overall FORWARD project goals

The overall objective of the FORWARD project (Fostering Research Excellence in EU Outermost Regions¹), involving partners from all of the 9 European Outermost Regions (OR's), is to improve excellence in research and their innovation potential to strengthen their participation in EU research and innovation funded projects, in particular in the Horizon Europe Framework Programme² (2021-2027), linking research activities with territorial development, particularly the Smart Specialization Strategies³ (S3/RIS3). The project aims at facilitating the collaboration and networking among representatives of the quadruple helix (university, SMEs, government, civil society) at regional level, between ORs, and with their counterparts from EU Members States and Third Countries at international level. Activities related to diagnosis of R&I, training, collaboration, networking and policy making are central to the project implementation.

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¹ <https://forward-h2020.eu>

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe_en

³ <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/what-is-smart-specialisation->

1.2 Objective of TWG's and TWG5

The thematic working groups created in FORWARD WP3 (Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans) aim at bringing together OR's experts and representatives from European and Third Countries' institutions who operate in a common strategic domain, which in our case is "Climate change and Energy transition". These thematic working groups and their action plans will contribute to:

- **Reinforce the actual and reveal the potential competitive advantages** of Outermost Regions in their respective sectors or fields of expertise, and the identification of common interests;
- **Consolidate the thematic working groups**, composed of experts from ORs or from non-EU / third countries, for the definition and implementation of thematic action plans in accordance with WP2;
- **Foster collaboration on common thematic areas** among ORs, between ORs and third countries as well as continental Europe's stakeholders.

Table 1 FORWARD thematic working groups

N°	Thematic
TWG1	Health, applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies
TWG2	Social sciences and social innovation
TWG3	Earth system, space & universe sciences
TWG4	Information and Communications Technology
TWG5	Climate change and Energy transition
TWG6	Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering
TWG7	Biodiversity conservation and restoration
TWG8	Marine sciences & technologies

1.2.1 TWG5 scope and goals

The working group dedicated to "Climate Change and Energy Transition" is one of the eight thematic groups created under the FORWARD project. In line with FORWARD overall objectives, the main objective of this thematic group is **to strengthen the cooperation of the ORs in the areas of Climate, Energy and Mobility** by bringing together researchers, project managers, company directors, public administrators and

civil society representatives, to significantly increase regional and ORs participation in joint research projects in the next EU Framework Programme , Horizon Europe (2021-2027).

As an objective to be achieved **2 or more applications submitted** under the calls for the EU Horizon Europe in the field of Climate Change, Energy Transition and Mobility (Cluster 5) and other clusters considered relevant. The number of applications will certainly depend on the dynamics of the group itself, the opportunities created and those associated with the calls that will open.

More than 60 people are involved in Thematic Group 5 (TWG5) from the 9 ORs, a number that will grow throughout 2021 and in the following years as the different HE project calls are launched.

1.2.2 Reference process guide for the Action Plan (AP)

The FORWARD WP3 process guide for design the Action Plan is summarized as follows.

STEP 1	STEP 2	STEP 3
<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forward and WP3 introduction to the members - Launch each thematic working group, provide all the necessary information for members to be ready to work 	<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-construct thematic action plans by connecting with ORs' thematic communities at local level. - At least 4 workshops ensuring quadruple helix approach will be organized to draft thematic action plans. 	<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement thematic action plans drafted in STEP 2. - Connect with ORs' thematic communities at local level. - Organize web meetings, local meetings, work sessions while ensuring quadruple helix approach.

For each step it will be carry out a number of online meetings, using provided Teams platform and other offline tools to exchange information and develop common approaches to research and innovation fields, aiming at the next EU calls.

STEP 1 is concluded for TWG5 ✓

STEP 2: WORKING SESSIONS ENSURING QUADRUPLE HELIX APPROACH

(27th Jan-Feb-19th Mar 2021) ✓

<p>OBJECTIVES :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-construct thematic action plans based on stakeholders' practical needs, interests, potentials, and experiences, extracted from WP2 diagnosis matrix and by connecting with ORs' thematic communities at local level. - Work sessions ensuring quadruple helix approach will be organized to draft thematic action plans. 	<p>OUTPUTS :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The results of the work will feed and fine-tune the content of WP4, WP5 and WP6. The action plans should identify quantitative objectives to demonstrate and evaluate their efficiency. This will feed WP7. - Each thematic working group will draft a report of the thematic action plan they will defined.
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(if needed, see details in reference document D3.1 – Guidelines, pages 16-24)

To ensure and promote the quadruple helix approach within the group members, specific activities will be organized using mind mapping tools such as **MIRO**⁴. Comparable tools are essential to empower the cooperation field and to make easier matchmaking to build new thematic networks within the ORs, and to expand such capabilities to EU wider networks to raise the chance to enter into a successful proposal preparation consortium.

Most meetings are recorded and saved in Teams (with previous participants' permission) to become available for those unable to participate or wanting to review them. Users may access the video recording of the sessions under TEAMS -> MEETINGS -> FILES -> RECORDINGS -> "Name of the meeting" (available as an MP4 file).

Kick-off meeting for TWG5 took place on the 27th January 2021. The participation was of 50% of registered members and the following subjects have been presented (timing indicates where each part is on the recording): 00:00:00 - Welcome notes and agenda; 00:04:53 - FORWARD project introduction; 00:15:50 - Work Package 3 and the Thematic Working Groups; 00:27:30 - Thematic Working Group 5 profile: who are we?; 00:40:20 - Thematic Working Group 5 profile: who am I? (all participants); 01:18:45 - TWG5: Key findings of the WP2 mapping (R&I ecosystem) for the nine Outermost Regions; 01:42:55

⁴ <https://miro.com/>

- Action plan proposal + Questions & Answers + Next steps: calendar for workshops;
01:55:10 - Closing remarks.

All presentations used during KoM are available in the folder "Meetings -> Files -> REPORTS OF THE MEETINGS -> KoM_TWIG5_27012021" (in PDF).

The second working session, on the 9th of February 2021, was dedicated to: Presentation of "new" members; Conclusions and discussion of the feedback form: composition of the group; main fields and subfields of research by order of importance to the member; subgrouping of TWG5: Presentation of candidates to coordinate subgroup **B-Energy (Karim Juhoor)** and subgroup **A-Climate (Ignacio Gafo)**; participation other TWG's (e.g. in TWG3 and TWG8); Next workshops / working sessions.

The third working session, on the 19th of March 2021, was dedicated to: Discuss and approve the draft of Action Plan-> feedback and suggestions from members; Presentation of first cluster 5 call selections for CEKA (Climate, Earth Knowledge and Adaptation) and SEM (Sustainable Energy and Mobility); Mapping group expertise and topic of calls; Calendar of actions.

STEP 3: ACTION PLAN IMPLEMENTATION (April 2021 – June 2022)

<p>OBJECTIVES :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement thematic action plans drafted in Step 2. - Connect with ORs' thematic communities at local level. - Organize web meetings, local meetings, work sessions while ensuring quadruple helix approach 	<p>OUTPUTS :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The results of the work will feed and fine-tune the content of WP4, WP5 and WP6. - Update as much as possible the Action Plan document to facilitate to follow up - Provide KPI to the WP7 leaders.
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(if necessary, see details in reference document D3.2 – Guidelines, pages 25-26)

After the approval of the draft action plan (in March 2021), TWG5 will continue with online working sessions, to start working on potential project calls and other TWG5 activities as previewed in the current document.

Versions of this document will be included and shared in "TWG5 Teams -> General -> Files -> Action Plan".

1.3 Relation of WP3 and TWGs with other WPs

Relevant for Capacity Building (WP4), Networking (WP5), Policies / Common Strategies (WP6) and C&D (WP8).

2 Summary of TWG5 thematic key findings in ORs

Resulting from FORWARD WP2 Diagnosis of the ORs R&I Ecosystems and completed with TWG5 members' profile and feedback, a summary document was prepared and presented during the KoM:

- 44 H2020 projects dealing with Climate change & Energy transition
- 7 Projects coordinated by OR's from which 6 H2020 projects **coordinated by SMEs** based in the ORs for an amount received of 1,834 millions euros
- 13.268.166,34 € received in the thematic in ORs
- Canarias (Spain) strongly leading with 30 H2020 projects.
- Very small participation of French OR

Figure 1 General overview of TWG5 key findings
OR's involvement in H2020 Projects under Climate change and Energy transition

TYPE OF ACTIONS ANALYSIS	%
Innovation action	35,0%
Research and Innovation action	34,0%
Coordination and support action	11,0%
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks (ITN)	10,0%
SME instrument phase 1	6,0%
COFUND (European Joint Programme)	2,0%
ERA-NET Cofund	2,0%
Total	100%

Thematic	%
Secure, clean and efficient energy	57,0%
Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials	15,0%
Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions	10,0%
Smart, green and integrated transport	6,0%
Research infrastructures	4,0%
Advanced materials	2,0%
Euratom	2,0%
Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research	2,0%
Space	2,0%
Total	100%

Figure 2 Summary of Type of Actions and Thematics

Another document on TWG5 thematic key findings is the summary report "**TWG5 Climate Change & Energy Transition**", produced by Consulta Europa (2020) and also available under shared files of TWG5 space in Teams. It includes: i) Presentation of the

region & its Research Institutions; ii) State of the art of the OR participation in EU projects; iii) Thematic distribution in the OR; iv) Alignment with the OR RIS3.

2.1 Other reports related to ORs

The following reference reports / documents on ORs for this thematic or related themes are currently available:

- Report on "**Energy in the EU Outermost Regions**", Eduardo Maldonado et al., 2017;
- Report on "**Transport accessibility for the EU Outermost Regions (ORs)**", Laurie Pickup, Claudio Mantero et al., 2017;
- Study on the "**Physical accessibility of the Outermost Regions**", TRT, SEO, Prognos, CENIT, July 2019;
- Report on "**Digital accessibility and ICT for the Outermost Regions**", Philippe Baudouin et al., 2017;

Previous documents are shared under folder "GENERAL -> FILES -> Reference documents -> Reports ORs".

This section will be completed by members. It's important that members share framework documents at OR level, which can help to define a possible common approach at a cross-cutting level between energy transition and climate change. Such insights are essential to define cooperation areas on the already existing evidences.

2.1.1 Further insights required?

If considered important in certain fields where no information/data exists or more complete / updated information is required, members may conduct specific analysis in order to produce such information. A subgroup coordinator must be defined, and for each OR a contact person will carry the regional analysis and compilation of data / information.

3 TWG5 members profile and fields of expertise

As of February 2021, TWG5 is composed of **69 members** from all ORs. Most members are from Universities (near 50%), followed by Private (SME/Large Company), Public

Administration and R&D Institutions. According to the registration form data, **58%** of the members have **Energy** as their main field(s) of activity / research and **42%** fit in **Climate**. If we consider the feedback from active members (those who answered the feedback form are about 50% of the members) then that relation will become **73%** in **Energy** and **27%** in **Climate**. The most represented are Canaries and Madeira (total >30 persons), followed by Guadeloupe, La Réunion, the Azores and Martinique (total >20 persons) and the less represented regions are Saint Martin, Mayotte and French Guiana (total <10 persons). Initial analysis of the group profile is presented in the document “4.FORWARD. TWG5_Members Profile” in KoM.

3.1.1 Fields of expertise and research interests

This analysis results from the information provided in the registration form (49 answers), together with the information later provided in the KoM feedback form (26 answers). In the registration form, members have been asked about field of expertise + keywords (1 and 2). In the KoM feedback form it was asked to indicate the main field between Energy, Climate and Mobility, and then to complete previous answer with further details / sub-fields, by order of importance.

For ENERGY (B-Sustainable Energy and Mobility), TWG5 members fields of expertise include:

Sustainable Energy Systems (renewable energies, including photovoltaic, passive smart sensing, marine / wave energy, biogas / biofuels, hydrogen, microbial fuel cells, offshore wind, biomass, geothermal, hydrothermal, hydro-chemistry, decarbonized mobility, energy storage systems);

Energy Management and Efficiency (namely in buildings); **Power grids** (distributed generation incl. grid isolated systems, mini-grids and microgrids; smart grids)

Energy Transition; Circular Economy; Process and Product Engineering; Blue economy; Citizens involvement; **Energy governance;** District heating; **Sector regulation and public policies; Mobility and Transport;** Thermal comfort and ventilation; Virtual power plants.

Digital transformation of the energy sector (data analysis, artificial intelligence, neural networks, deep machine learning, Internet of things, creation of digital twins).

For **CLIMATE (A-Earth Systems Knowledge and Adaptation)**, TWG5 members fields of expertise include:

Climate Change; climate **projections**; climate **modelling**; climate **impacts** mitigation / **adaptation** plans (mainly in the context of ORs island territories); atmospheric dynamics and precipitation systems;

Environmental Law, Policy development and governance; **risk and vulnerability** studies; **Waste management**; **Marine ecology**; **Social identification about climate change**; GHG balance; physical oceanography, water masses and ocean circulation; **Impact in health and diseases**; Climate Model dynamical / statistical downscaling; Sea level rise (incl. coastal erosion, flooding and morpho-dynamics, storm surge, shoreline prediction); Smart adapted agriculture; Geospatial and volcanology.

The fields of expertise identified have been summarized on a Excel table and are associated with concrete members (in many cases to several persons) and can be mapped to topics in particular calls for proposals. That way it will be easier to identify / create “subgroups” of members that may/will get involved in writing project proposals addressing concrete research topics / fields (available in folder “Working documents” in TWG5 Teams space).

Table 2 Summary table of TWG5 fields of expertise: SEM and CEKA

TWG5 fields of expertise and interests SEM (Sustainable Energy and Mobility)	TWG5 fields of expertise and interests CEKA (Earth Systems Knowledge and Adaptation)
<p>Sustainable Energy Systems (SES)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SES renewables photovoltaic SES renewables wind SES renewables offshore wind SES renewables marine / wave energy SES renewables biogas / biofuels SES renewables microbial fuel cells SES renewables hydrogen SES renewables biomass SES renewables geothermal / hydrothermal SES renewables hydro-chemistry <p>SES passive smart sensing</p> <p>SES energy storage systems</p> <p>SES virtual power plants</p> <p>Energy Management and Efficiency (EME)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EME buildings EME power grids / distributed generation EME power grids / isolated systems EME power grids / mini-grids EME power grids / microgrids EME power grids / smart grids EME district heating EME thermal comfort and ventilation <p>Energy Transition (ET)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ET Circular Economy ET Blue economy ET Citizens involvement ET Process and Product Engineering ET Energy governance ET Sector regulation and public policies <p>SEM Mobility and Transport (MT)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MT decarbonized mobility <p>Digital transformation of the energy sector</p>	<p>Climate Change (CC)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CC climate modelling (dynamical / statistical downscaling) CC climate projections CC climate impacts mitigation CC climate impacts adaptation plans CC atmospheric physics and dynamics / precipitation CC Social identification about CC CC GHG balance CC physical oceanography, water masses and ocean circulation CC Impact in health and diseases CC Sea level rise (coastal erosion, flooding and morphological changes) CC Smart adapted agriculture (?) CC Impact on Tourism <p>Environmental Law</p> <p>Policy development and governance</p> <p>Risk and vulnerability studies</p> <p>Waste management</p> <p>Marine ecology</p> <p>Geospatial and volcanology</p>

4 TWG5 organization

The proposed approach for the functioning and structure / organization of TWG5 is, taking as a reference FORWARD guidelines for the “Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans”, to match as much as possible skills, fields of expertise and research interests of members, with the main goal of developing and submitting as many as possible project proposals under the calls for Horizon Europe in the field of Climate Change, Energy Transition and Mobility (Cluster 5).

Most members of the group are mainly interested in **Energy topics (58%) while 42% are more interested in Climate topics**. Mobility lies between both. By subgrouping and

matching existing skills with those required by the project calls for EU co-funded projects, everyone's expectations will be fulfilled.

4.1 Subgrouping

Taking into account TWG5 members' expertise fields, initial subgroup proposal was: A) climate science, resiliency, volcanology, geospatial; B) sustainable energy (use and supply); C) transport and smart mobility; D) ocean and marine. Following the feedback received and the discussion among TWG5 members, subgroup C was dropped and its scope (transport and smart mobility) was integrated in Subgroup B. Subgroup D was also dropped and its scope (address the climate change and energy transition for the ocean and marine topic) was integrated in Subgroup A, resulting in the following names (as proposed by Artur Gil / Ignacio Gafo):

subgroup A) Climate, Earth Knowledge and Adaptation (CEKA)

subgroup B) Sustainable Energy and Mobility (SEM)

As a result of the members' participation in a feedback form, **Mr. Ignacio Gafo** (External Advisor at ACIISI Canarias) was elected the contact person for subgroup A); and **Mr. Karim Juhoor** (CEO of EFUZIF, in La Réunion) was elected as the contact person for subgroup B). A summary of their profiles can be consulted under "Meetings -> Files -> 2nd meeting 09Feb2021 -> Profiles candidates subgroups A and B".

Subgroup contact persons / coordinators are expected to animate the discussion and suggest themes and strategies for preparing proposals with partners and networks.

Whenever necessary, in view of specific tasks/aims, dedicated ad-hoc subgroups will be created. Two such cases are: i) When writing concrete proposal(s) and ii) To conduct a study or analysis in a certain (sub)field.

4.2 Support tools

Main supporting tool is **Microsoft Teams**⁵, which is provided and managed by project partner **SYNERGILE** (WP3 co-leader, together with "Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias - ITC"). Group members are registered as "guests" and to properly access Teams space

⁵ <https://www.microsoft.com/>

they need to login with user and password provided when they have been registered. E.g. you will need it to use chat during meetings. Instructions / manuals on how to use Teams have been shared with users by Synergile. Specific questions on functioning of Teams can be addressed to TWG5 facilitator, who will forward them to Synergile.

Excel based tools will also be used, as is the case of the Call Evaluation Matrix. Excel files can be integrated, shared and edited directly inside Teams space.

Suggested mind mapping tool is **MIRO**. There are other tools which integrate with Teams, including mind mapping.

Members shall suggest additional tools, either integrated in Teams or external tools.

4.3 Non-disclosure agreement

All members implicitly agree that their participation in this thematic group is not intended to obtain information they could use elsewhere and, in that way, compromising or weakening the aims of the group. When working on the specific project proposal, members / participants will have to explicitly commit with not “leaking” information, in particular to competing proposals outside the group. Signing a document of confidentiality reinforcing this non-disclosure objective shall be required.

5 Implementation of Action Plan

Implementation of this Action Plan (AP) will start once it is complete and approved by TWG5 members, in March 2021, before Horizon Europe calls are officially published / open, in April 2021. Activities will follow the guidelines and steps presented in the document.

Envisaged types of activities during the implementation of the AP include:

- Consult, read and select HE Cluster 5 calls considering call calendar, ie, starting with the calls for 2021.
- Evaluate and rank the calls considering topic preferences and expertise/skills, regional and ORs relevance, etc, using proposed call evaluation matrix.
- Design and develop project ideas (completing a proposal factsheet).

- Contacting and joining potential partners for a project consortium (use partner identification form).
- Project proposal writing / development (extend proposal factsheet to fulfill call criteria).
- Proposal submission.

When joining existing consortia rather than creating our own, and depending on the expected role in the project, requirements and effort will differ.

5.1 About HE Cluster 5

As stated in Cluster 5 (Climate change and energy transition) draft WP, the overarching driver for this cluster is to accelerate the twin **green and digital transitions** and associated transformation of our economy, industry and society with a view to achieving **climate neutrality** in Europe by 2050. This encompasses the transition to greenhouse gas neutrality of the energy and mobility sectors by 2050 at the latest (as well as that of other sectors not covered by this cluster), while boosting their competitiveness, resilience, and utility for citizens and society. Activities of this work programme support the implementation of the Paris Agreement and the **United Nations Sustainable Development Goals**⁶. By creating more jobs, accelerating economic and social transformation, faster digitalisation and by generating innovation-based and inclusive growth, activities will aid Europe's recovery in the wake of the Covid-19 crisis, contributing directly to the Commission priorities of a **European Green Deal**⁷, a **Europe fit for the digital age**⁸, and an **economy that works for the people**⁹. The European Commission's strategic vision "**A Clean Planet for All**"¹⁰ outlines that the move to climate neutrality – along with faster digitalisation and accelerated economic and societal changes – will transform the energy and mobility sectors in the coming decades making them increasingly intertwined. **Research and Innovation** will heavily influence the speed at which these transitions can take place, directly affecting the associated costs, impacts and co-benefits such as better air and water quality, increased

⁶ <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age_en

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/economy-works-people_en

¹⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/strategies/2050_en

employment, social inclusion, sustainable resource management (including the circular economy and biodiversity), and reduced dependency on fossil fuels. Beyond the inevitable social transitions and lifestyle changes, a key contribution to success is the development of a wide portfolio of – from a lifecycle perspective – cost-effective climate neutral alternatives for emitting activities, based on often in combination with enhanced sector coupling, digitalisation, system integration and leveraging, whenever appropriate, the existing Earth observation and monitoring programme **Copernicus**. The rate at which **European research and innovation actions** succeed in developing, upscaling, implementing, and commercialising such innovative solutions will steer EU's future competitiveness of its existing and newly emerging industries in European and global markets.

As defined in HE strategic plan, cluster 5 is composed of 9 Intervention areas, which link to strategic R&I areas as indicated in the following matrix:

Overview of links between intervention areas (HE SP) and strategic R&I areas of the Strategic Plan document

X – strong link, o – link (less strong as for 'X')

Intervention areas as in Horizon Europe legal base	Climate Science and Solutions	Energy Supply	Energy Systems and Grids	Buildings and Industrial Facilities in Energy Transition	Communities and Cities	Industrial Competitiveness in Transport	Clean Transport and Mobility	Smart Mobility	Energy Storage
Strategic research and Innovation areas									
Develop knowledge and more efficient climate action									
Climate science and solutions	X		o		o		o		
Develop cross-sectoral solutions to decarbonise the energy and mobility sectors									
Batteries		X	X	X	o	o	X		X
Hydrogen		X	o	o		o	o		X
Communities and cities	o	o	X	X	X		o	X	o
Emerging breakthrough technologies and climate solutions	o	X	X	X	X	o	X	o	X
Develop cost-efficient, zero-carbon energy systems									
Renewable energy		X	X	o	X		o		o
Energy Systems and grids		X	X	o	X		X		X
CC(U)S		X		X					
Energy storage		X	X	X	X		o	o	X
Leveraging public and private investments in the Clean Energy Transition		X	X		X				

(continues in next page)

Develop demand side solutions to decarbonise the energy system										
Empowering citizens			o	X	X	X		o	o	o
Decarbonising building stock			o	X	X	X		o		X
Industrial facilities in energy transition			o	X	X					o
Develop low-carbon and competitive transport solutions across all modes										
Towards zero-emission road transport (2ZERO)				o	o	o	X	X		
Rail				o		o	X		X	
Cleaner and competitive aviation							X	X		
Waterborne transport			o	o		o	X	X	X	
Impact on human health and environment	0					o		X		
Develop seamless, smart, and safe mobility systems										
Mobility and Safety for Automated Road Transport						o	X		X	
Competitive and innovative transport infrastructure				o	X		X		X	
Future transport network and integrated traffic management			o	o		o	X		X	
Multimodal freight logistics and passenger mobility services				o		o	X		X	
Transport safety across modes							X	X	X	

Cluster 5 intervention areas and their link to strategic R&I areas

(Ref: "ANNEX 5 - HORIZON EUROPE CLUSTER 5", pages 24-25)¹¹

Why the EU supports energy research and innovation ->

https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/research-area/energy-research-and-innovation_en

Mission area: Climate-neutral and smart cities -> https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe/missions-horizon-europe/climate-neutral-and-smart-cities_en

https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe/missions-horizon-europe/adaptation-climate-change-including-societal-transformation_en

¹¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/pdf/horizon-europe/annex-5.pdf>

https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/research-area/environment/climate-action_en

Research and innovation for the European Green Deal ->
https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/european-green-deal_en

2030 energy goals -> https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/strategies/2030_en

- Key targets for 2030:
- At least 40% cuts in greenhouse gas emissions (from 1990 levels)
- At least 32% share for renewable energy
- At least 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency

5.1.1 Cluster 5 Destinations (topics / calls)

Destinations are packages of actions around which each Work Programme (WP) part within Pillar II was designed. *Destinations* are a series of coherent packages aimed at contributing to the expected impacts set out in HE Strategic Plan and provide the policy narrative for the calls and actions included in the WP. In the WP, the text of the *destination* reflects the expected impact as set out in the Strategic Plan and each *destination* is implemented by means of calls for proposals.

5.1.2 HE Cluster 5 WP calls are grouped in 6 destinations:

- 1 – Climate sciences and responses
- 2 – Cross-sectoral solutions for the climate transition
- 3 – Sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply
- 4 – Efficient, sustainable and inclusive energy use
- 5 – Clean and competitive solutions for all transport modes
- 6 – Safe, Resilient Transport and Smart Mobility services for passengers and goods

5.1.3 Destinations relate to identified Expected Impacts as indicated in next table.

Table 3 Destinations and their relation with expected Impacts (ref: HE Cluster 5 draft work-programme, Nov 2020)

Expected Impact (Strategic Plan)	Destination (Cluster 5 work programme)
i. Transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society and economy enabled through advanced climate science, pathways and responses to climate change (mitigation and adaptation) and behavioral transformations.	1. Climate sciences and responses
ii. Clean and sustainable transition of the energy and transport sectors towards climate neutrality facilitated by innovative crosscutting solutions.	2. Cross-sectoral solutions for the climate transition
iii. More efficient, clean, sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply through new solutions for smart grids and energy systems based on more performant renewable energy solutions.	3. Sustainable, secure and competitive energy supply
iv. Efficient and sustainable use of energy, accessible for all is ensured through a clean energy system and a just transition.	4. Efficient, sustainable and inclusive energy use
v. Towards climate-neutral and environmental friendly mobility through clean solutions across all transport modes while increasing global competitiveness of the EU transport sector.	5. Clean and competitive solutions for all transport modes
vi. Safe, seamless, smart, inclusive, resilient, climate neutral and sustainable mobility systems for people and goods thanks to user-centric technologies and services including digital technologies and advanced satellite navigation services.	6. Safe Resilient Transport and Smart Mobility services for passengers and goods

With the existing information of fields of expertise of members, it becomes more or less straightforward to map members expertise / profiles to HE cluster 5 expected impacts and destinations and thus to concrete project calls / topics.

5.1.4 Cluster 5 links to other clusters in Pillar II of HE

The following table indicates how cluster 5 links to other clusters of HE. Taking into account existing expertise, that several members of TWG5 also participate in other TWG's and obviously the fact being part of TWG5 doesn't prevent the group from developing a project proposal in any of the other HE clusters.

Table 4 (ref: EC proposal for Horizon Europe, RTD/C5, 2020)

Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health impacts of climate change, energy production/consumption, transport emissions and mobility patterns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Societal dimension of transformation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection of critical infrastructure • Cybersecurity • Climate-related disaster risk management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manufacturing • Low-carbon, clean, circular industries • Artificial Intelligence and Robotics • Advanced Materials • Space 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioeconomy • Circular economy • Environmental observation

5.2 Cluster 5 Work-Programme and Project Calls

As of writing of this document, cluster 5 ‘Climate, Energy and Mobility’ work-programme (WP) 2021-2022 is not yet officially published, but its 3rd draft from Nov 2020 is available on different sites on the Internet. The WP is organized by *destinations* and for each *destination* concrete topics and calls for proposals are presented. The following is the example of call **C5-D1-CSR-05-2021: Maximising the impact and synergy of EU climate change research and innovation**, which is presented under Destination 1 (Climate sciences and responses), (sub)topic “Pathways to climate neutrality”.

C5-D1-CSR-05-2021: Maximising the impact and synergy of EU climate change research and innovation

<i>Conditions related to this topic</i>	
<i>Expected EU contribution per project</i>	The EU estimates that an EU contribution of between EUR 2 and 5 million would allow these outcomes to be addressed appropriately.
<i>Type of action</i>	Coordination and support action
<i>Procedure</i>	To ensure a balanced portfolio covering all two areas, grants will be awarded to applications not only in order of ranking but at least also to one project that is the highest ranked within each area, provided that the applications attain all thresholds.

Expected Outcomes: (please consult pages 24-25 of Cluster 5 WP).

Scope: Actions should cover one of the following areas: (please consult pages 26-28 of Cluster 5 WP).

Call requirements are published with the opening of the call in EC’s **Funding and Tenders Portal**¹² (Single Electronic Data Interchange Area - SEDIA).

¹² <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>

Some calls mention islands: e.g. C5-D4-B4P-10-2022: Designs, materials and solutions to improve resilience, preparedness & responsiveness of the built environment for climate adaptation; or call C5-D3-RES-62-2022: Demonstration of innovative plug-and play solutions for system management and renewables storage in off-grid applications. In this case both expected to open only in 2022.

Analyzing, evaluating, ranking and prioritizing each call (selected ones or even all calls) and then joining the most appropriate subgroup of members, with not only related research skills and research interests but also networking and proposal writing skills, will certainly lead to developing and submitting successful project proposals.

Joining other / existing consortiums (also) working in such calls is certainly also a good approach to become partner in a project. In this case the participation of a higher number, or all, of OR partners will obviously be less likely than in the case that the proposal and consortium is built by OR's.

5.3 Mapping expertise and topic calls

Fields of expertise identified in “3.TWG5 members profile and fields of expertise” can be associated with concrete member persons and can be mapped to topics in concrete calls for proposals. The Excel table indicates the expertise of each member (it will be available in Teams under “working documents”). That way it will be easier to identify / create “subgroups” of members that will get involved in writing and submitting project proposals addressing concrete research topics / fields.

5.4 Call evaluation matrix

The proposed evaluation matrix can be used to analyze, evaluate, rank and prioritize calls, starting will calls to open in 2021.

Table 5 Overview of the evaluation matrix (new version 2)

Draft evaluation of HORIZON 2021-2022 budgetary research proposals in TWG5					
Code and name of Action	Type of action	Estimated number of projects and individual Budget MM Euros	Relevance and OR potential advantages	Possibility to join into a EU Wide Consortium	Justification
e.g. HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-01-03: Market Uptake Measures of renewable energy systems	CSA	2x5	Medium	High	Experience of partners and due to the international cooperation envisaged the OR situation will facilitate to join a large consortium. No pilot, only networking. Relevant budget.
...

A member or a group of members will evaluate calls where “they” would like to participate. “They” means specific organization(s) in the region or at OR level, which contain the requirements to fulfill a certain role in the project (coordinator, WP leader, scientific/research partner, demonstrator, etc).

It should be considered among the 8 TWG’s to establish a common practice for tasks such as the evaluation matrix, the partner identification form or the proposal factsheet.

5.5 Partner identification form

Potential project partners can be described / presented using the proposed identification form.

Partner Identification Form

GENERAL INFORMATION

PROFILE

BACKGROUND AND EXPERIENCE

Please briefly present the partner organisation.

What are the activities and experience of the organisation in the areas relevant for this application?

What are the skills and expertise of key staff/persons involved in this application?

LEGAL REPRESENTATIVE

CONTACT PERSON

Experience in previous international projects (funded by EU or any international body programme)

Figure 3 Overview of the partner identification form

5.6 Proposal factsheet

A project idea related to a selected call will then be drafted in the project idea / proposal factsheet (template for measure / activity / pilot description), to be used as a reference / overview to the proposal (e.g. to discuss with potential partners outside TWG5).

Table 6 Overview of the project proposal factsheet / description

Call C5-D.....-.....-.....:*Call title*

TEMPLATE FOR MEASURE/ACTIVITY/PILOT DESCRIPTION

Name of the measure	<insert here>
Demonstration city	<city / region>
Name contact person, organisation and contact information	<name> <organisation> <direct contacts>

Relevant measure categories

Innovative elements, unique selling points of the measure (max 50 words)

City Region background

Target Groups

Short description of the measure/pilot/activity (max 100 words)

Outcomes

Macro objectives met by the measure and estimated impact

Partners involved

Time planning

Draft Budget

Regional strategic/legal framework

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents;programCode=HORIZON>

5.7 Description of Actions

Main / top level actions for TWG5 will consist of designing and developing project proposals for HE. FORWARD TWG guidelines provide templates for description of actions using the Excel template provided, consisting of:

Identify and describe Actions (Objectives, Activities and Tasks): Specific Objective 1..N, each with a calendar of planned Activities and Tasks.

Gantt chart of Activities and Tasks: Start; End; Resources; Contact Person for activity; Other co-organizers; Expected results; Level of advancement.

Once an activity / action has been identified and decided by the group it needs to be described using the template (to be available in “working documents” folder).

6 Other EU instruments for R&I

In addition to calls under Cluster 5 destinations, other financing and cooperation R&I initiatives shall be considered as some of them will be very important for e.g. for researchers and SME's as specific beneficiaries. That's the case of **Marie-Curie (Researcher Mobility)**, **SME INSTRUMENT (Innovation Actions)** and **Fast Track to Innovation (FTI)**, as existed in H2020 and now called **Postdoctoral Fellowships (PF)**

i. **MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE (MSCA) (Researcher Mobility)**

Innovative Training Networks (ITN): ITN drive scientific excellence and innovation. They bring together universities, research institutes and other sectors from across the world to train researchers to doctorate level.

Individual Fellowships (IF): IF are great opportunities if you are an experienced researcher looking to give your career a boost by working abroad. They offer exciting new learning opportunities and a chance to add some sparkle to your CV.

Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE): RISE funds short-term exchanges of personnel between academic, industrial and commercial organisations throughout the world. It helps people develop their knowledge, skills and careers, while building links between organisations working in different sectors of the economy, including universities, research institutes and SMEs.

European Researchers' Night (NIGHT): This is a Europe-wide public event dedicated to popular science and fun learning. It takes place each year in September. Around 30 countries and over 300 cities are involved.

Table 7 8 Overall calendar of activities (last phase to be detailed in June 2021)

Activity description (16-04-2021 to 18-05-2021) in order to define which calls in HE cluster5 (2021) will be tackled by the group	Date / Deadline							
	16/04/2021	20/04/2021	27/04/2021	30/04/2021	04/05/2021	11/05/2021	18/05/2021	19-05 onwards
Present this calendar to members, including complete list of calls for 2021 (Excel table) and the calls already proposed for the top6 by members (18 calls / topics as of 16042021)								
Close the selection of potential calls for 2021 (overall top6) When proposing a call members need to take into account not only their personal / regional interested but also the potential interest for the other OR regions. To be considered a maximum of 30 calls								
TWG5 coordinators share with members the final selection of proposed 30 potential calls (as above) for 2021, including a summary / abstract based on the evaluation matrix criteria								
TWG5 group online meeting to discuss about selection of calls and related issues (to be confirmed on the 27th of April)								
Via an online form to be provided, members make a final choice on which call proposals they want to become involved (maximum 2 projects to be personally involved), indicating what shall be their role/contribution for proposal development and which organizations they would propose to involve from their region and the role of such organizations in the project (this is of course indicative and subject to change). From this point onward participants must commit themselves with the proposal development / writing and with not sharing information with potential competing proposals outside the group (for the same call)								
Based on the proposed calls, coordinators select the 4 most promising calls to be addressed in TWG5, including the list of members (and their role) to become involved in each proposal. After this point a working subgroup for each call shall be created								
By the 18 of May the group shall have agreed on wich calls to participate for 2021 and who will become involved in each call								
Next steps and calendar to be defined according to each specific call deadline and typical FP proposal development process. Prior to start working on the project proposal, participants will be required to sign a non-disclosure / commitment agreement in order to continue involved in the proposal								

i. SME INSTRUMENT (SME support)

The dedicated SME instrument encourages for-profit SMEs to put forward their most innovative ideas with an EU dimension. The instrument aims to fill gaps in funding for high-risk innovation and close-to-market activities to give a strong boost to breakthrough innovation. It targets highly innovative SMEs with a strong ambition to develop, grow and internationalise. It covers the whole innovation cycle, the focus being on delivery of new products, services or processes on the market (Phase 1 - Feasibility study; Phase 2 - Innovation actions; Phase 3 - Commercialisation).

ii. Fast Track to Innovation (FTI)

FTI is a fully-bottom-up innovation support programme promoting close-to-the-market innovation activities open to industry-driven consortia that can be composed of all types of participants. It can help partners to co-create and test breakthrough products, services or business processes that have the potential to revolutionise existing or create entirely new markets, under the helm of the Enhanced European Innovation Council (EIC) pilot.

7 Long term cooperation model for TWGs

Full implementation and long-term activities of the Forward Climate change and Energy Transition action plan requires dedicated sustainable transversal support actions. Similarly to what is proposed by TWG2, in TWG5 it will be based on volunteering, starting with the definition of a group's coordination system which ensures members' adhesion, commitment and sharing of responsibilities. Two main options are proposed for analysis and approval, which may be adapted, adopted or merged. As transversal support actions it is desirable that it becomes defined and implemented at consortium level horizontally to all 8 TWGs / ORs.

7.1 Option i - COST Actions Management System

Adoption of COST¹³ Actions Management System will ensure alignment with European standards in collaborative research management and ORs researchers receiving

¹³

https://www.cost.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/COST-013-19-Guidelines_Action_management_monitoring_assessment_Ver2019.06.pdf

knowledge on promising tools. As proposed by TWG2, the management structure could be set up as follows:

- A management committee (MC), composed of 1 representative per OR and in charge of :
 - defining the group's strategy, policy, rules and memberships
 - defining the working groups and composition
 - performing the monitoring and reporting duties
- Working groups (WG), composed of all interested members, in charge of performing the tasks required in the action plan and led by voluntary leader and vice-leader, responsible for coordinating and managing actions assigned to the WG:
 - WG 1 - Mobilize Climate, Energy and Mobility to understand and boost R&I in ORs
 - WG 2 - Build critical masses (including NGO) on targeted R&I fields to contribute to the European Research Area
 - WG 3 - FP incubator
- Thematic committees (action 5 in TWG2) composed of all interested members and led by voluntary by voluntary leader and vice-leader
- A general assembly which brings together all members to share the group's progress and achievements

7.2 Option ii - Forward Common strategy for institutional cooperation & common governance in ORs

As of March 2021, the common strategy is still being developed under Task 6.2 (WP6) of the Forward project and as thus is not closed yet but it provides already a base model mapped from the resulting work of RIS3_Net projects¹⁴ (1 and 2) plus Forward managing structure and TWGs. As proposed for discussion and approval under Forward Task 6.2, the common governance is as presented in next table. TWGs management structure can be included in such model as part of the global ORs cooperation.

¹⁴ <https://www.ris3-net.eu/>

Table 8 Common Governance for ORs (initial proposal under T6.2)

Management Structure	Members	Functions
Steering Committee	<p>9 members</p> <p>President assigned every year, rotating between ORs</p> <p>Political or R&I entity representatives of at least one member institution of each OR;</p> <p>Annual in person meetings;</p>	<p>Evaluate the R&I Strategy for ORs;</p> <p>Review the compliance of high – level goals;</p> <p>Set up goals and high level control activities;</p> <p>Serve as a liaison with The EC supporting decisions approved from a political and institutional perspective for ORs;</p> <p>Supervise the Management Team;</p>
Management Team	<p>3 members;</p> <p>Rotation: annually;</p> <p>Representatives from Regional R&I entities (ARDITI, ACIISI, FRCT, NEXA, CTG, GUA, MART, StMart, MAY);</p> <p>Annual in person meetings;</p> <p>Quarterly videoconference meetings;</p>	<p>Coordinate Thematic Groups;</p> <p>Promote consensus among the ORs;</p> <p>Implement the actions of the Common Strategy for ORs;</p> <p>Send proposals to the Steering Group for review and evaluation of the Common Strategy for ORs;</p> <p>Prepare Strategy implementation reports</p>
Coordinators	<p>9 members, 1 for each Thematic Group;</p> <p>Rotation: annually;</p> <p>Must be a Thematic Specialist;</p> <p>Videoconference meetings between coordinators every 6 months;</p>	<p>Manage Thematic Group;</p> <p>Maintain stakeholder engagement;</p> <p>Communicate results;</p>

8 Further considerations

From idea to project: some considerations on the steps of creating and submitting a project proposal.

Step 1 – Idea related to a call (Evaluation matrix + proposal Factsheet)

Step 2 – Joining together **partners** / Consortium (networking skills)

Step 3 -> project **proposal writing** / development and submission (proposal writing skills)

Step 4 -> EC experts **evaluation** (some consultants provide useful pre-evaluation services)

Step 5 -> Project **execution** (You've won the call, now good luck)

Other parts / aims of TWGs APs:

Networking

Establishment of networks between the ORs and external actors that will cooperate to build critical masses and projects on the considered thematic.

Sustainability

Prospective approach to focus on ensuring their sustainability both during the project life and even after its end.

Dissemination

Disseminating TWG activities.

**TWG6: Agriculture, applied
life sciences, biotechnology,
and bio-systems engineering**

TWG6 – Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering

Thematic Action Plan

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This report describes the steps, the discussions, the main issues, and conclusions held by the members of the thematic working group 6 (Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering). Our objective was to co-create the action plan in respect of the sub-objectives. This co-creation phase was particularly intense push the set six meeting in two months.

Profile of the members

The members of the thematic working group are in majority located in the Canary Islands (42%) and Madeira (15%). The other outermost regions are quite equally represented with 3 to 5 members. Mayotte does not have representative in the TWG 6.

The members are from academic field (62%) for the majority, follow by public companies and institutes (15%) and SME (11%).

The keywords used by TWG6 members to describe their activities in the profiling file are not homogenous without a clear trend. The more used keywords are Water, Environment, Natural, Sustainable, biotechnology, Soil and Health.

Performance of ORs in EU FP funding for agriculture and biotechnology

A total of 25 projects were identified in the H2020 Framework Programme for the Research and Innovation involving the Outermost Regions and Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and bio-systems engineering theme, with two (2) for Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action and one (1) for an infrastructure project.

On the 25 projects, no ORs leads a project despite two (2) single participants. Seven projects were in relation to at least a SME.

Scheduling and progression of the discussions throughout the meetings

The initial planning of four (4) meetings to co-create the action plan was not followed. The methodology proposed (i.e., SWOT analysis, SMART Objective, How-How diagram) were a bit far from the usual practices of the members and the first discussion allow to perform rounder tables and more straight exchange between the members. This step was necessary to allow the members to get to know each other and begin to build the trust necessary for meaningful collaborations.

The planning was finally the following one:

- **January 14th Kick-off Meeting:** Individual presentation of each member present (the absence and new ones got the opportunity to give a 4 min introduction talk at the beginning of the following meetings)
- **January 21st 2021 Workshop #1 Define the Specific Objectives:** selection of three specific objectives
 - Design the future of ORs Agriculture and Aquaculture, sustainable and respectful of the environment
 - Inventory, map and promote bio-product endemic of the ORs to ease innovation in Health, Bio-material production and Energy
 - Make biological analysis capacity in the ORs an ace to face current and future threats (i.e., Climate Change, disease)

- **January 28st 2021 Workshop #2 Brainstorming to determine Actions to achieve the Specific Objectives:** decision to redefine the three initial specific objectives in two, more adapted for the nature of the group
 - Agro-Ecology renamed “**Agro-System**” after discussion
 - One Health concept

- **February 4th, 2021 Workshop #3 Brainstorming 2 to determine the Specific Objectives and the associated actions:** work to define list of actions related to the first specific objective of the group Agro-Ecology (using tree diagram)
- **February 11th, 2021 Workshop #4 Brainstorming 3 to determine Specific Objectives and the associated actions:** work to define list of actions related to the first specific objectives of the group “One Health Approach” (using tree diagram)
- **February 25th, 2021 Workshop #5 Draft and validation of the Thematic Action Plan:** Based on the previous meeting the TWG validate the two sub-objectives and (see the list below)
 - 14 actions in Agro-system sub-objectives and sub-group
 - 12 actions on One Health sub-objectives and sub-group

After further discussion three other actions were added to offer full opportunity to develop true synergies between the ORs.

List of the actions

The main goal of the TWG6 is to create an active network with the capacity to address the future challenges of our regions in a relevant manner. The actions selected as a thematic action plan by the TWG6 will firstly allow the creation of exchange (i.e., ideas, data, practice) and synergies between the stakeholder in Research-Development-Innovation and agro-production and secondly makes available information, bibliography, and methodologies for future projects in research and innovation. We collectively identified the need to perform a new member recruitment campaign in ORs for stakeholder and human sciences persons)

The actions identified are described below in detail:

Agro-System

- Series of colloquium on Agro-system in ORs
- Development of organic alternatives to agrochemical for new bio-protectant, soil carbon sequestration, soil health and productivity
- Monitoring water availability in ORs for agro-system
- Bio-monitoring of water quality in ORs
- Digital data availability in ORs
- Increase adoption and implementation of agroecological principles at the farmer level
- Farm to fork: setting future sustainable relationship of stakeholders in food production system at ORs
- Monitoring the use of agrochemicals in ORs
- Monitoring and biomonitoring contaminants and other elements in soil ecosystems of ORs
- Set up of an Innovative surveillance strategy for ORs (Pathogen/Pest anticipate emergence of the new diseases)
- Famers and exploitations (income and activities)
- Assess the promotion of food production systems based on smart adaptations
- Carbon neutrality (Carbon production), the Life cycle in ORs
- Assess the sustainability of ORs agro-systems
- Assessment of the downscaling potential of aquaculture in ORs
- Monitoring biodiversity in agroecosystems

One Health concept

Sub-objective 2.1 Biotic drivers

- Monitoring of new threats: Emergence / unknow diseases / pests
- Inventory of the Usage of local product
- Assessing the relations between 'endemic' symptoms and diseases to contribute to the improvement of human health in ORs
- Determine the ecotoxicological impacts of antimicrobial resistance in agroecosystems

- Phytotherapy (Evaluation of biological activity of products form endemic and native (plants) species)
- Development of vaccines

Sub-objectives 2.2 Abiotic drivers

- Training of farmers, general population and schools for the importance of soil and water conservation
- Financially support scientific research to develop more biological solutions
- Establishing safety limits of elemental content for agricultural soils in ORs (many are volcanic, and naturally enriched with several elements)
- Geochemical background of soils and soil fertility
- Composting or vermicomposting practice for the population
- Inspection of the industries as well as the obligation of these industries to carry out environmental cleaning and reforestation actions for example

Organization of the group

The thematic working group will meet at least once per month. The action will be facilitated by two or three members ready to be involved in that action as leader of the sub-group. If a sub-group does not have enough participants to conduct action or does not have a sufficient diversity of ORs a recruitment campaign will be launch. The activities of the sub-group will be freeze until the number of minimum members defined by the TWG 6 will be reached (more than five members from three different ORs)

TWG7: Biodiversity conservation and restoration

Forward project Thematic Working Groups

TWG7 - Biodiversity conservation and restoration

Draft proposal of Action Plan

09/03/2021

Version 1

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Introduction

Outermost regions (ORs) are among the most ecologically vulnerable territories of the European Union (EU). Indeed, their small size, isolation and high level of endemic biodiversity, make them particularly exposed to anthropogenic biodiversity erosion drivers (e.g. habitat degradation, pollution, spread of invasive species, climatic changes) threatening natural ecosystems on a global scale and the communities which rely on them. For this reason, it is important to promote the ORs as living labs of biodiversity and provide guidance to help the ORs and the EU on the needs in research, development, and innovation at the ORs scale. Consequently, it is critical to have more clear goals and improve joint efforts to support actions that will allow more participation of ORs researchers in EU Framework Programme.

Therefore, the Action Plan for the TWG7, dedicated to the “Biodiversity Conservation and Restoration”, is designed as a common vision co-created from a bottom-up methodology by the TWG7 Members, during online and offline work, from January 2021 to March 2021. The Action Plan construction was led by a sub-coordinator, an expert and high profile person in this Thematic, Professor Paulo A. V. Borges, from University of the Azores (UAc-GBA-cE3c) (Azorean Biodiversity Group/Center for Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Changes), supported by the following team: Mário Boieiro (UAc-GBA-cE3c), as deputy, Lina Silveira, (Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia -FRCT), Carolina Parelho (FRCT) and Nuno Vasconcelos (UAc), as the three facilitators.

The TWG’s general goal is to contribute to the increase of the participation of the OR’s in Framework Programs - Horizon Europe (2021-2027) and aims to be accomplished by addressing specific objectives included in the Action Plan (AP). The AP will be implemented by TWG7 Members, with the support of the managing team, mentioned in the previous paragraph and led by Prof. Paulo A. V. Borges.

The TWG was created as a tool to enhance the collaboration and networking in a common framework. The Action Plan includes a set of activities, engaging the TWG7 members in the collection, analysis and report of valuable information on Biodiversity conservation and restoration in ORs. It’s expected that this TWG to last beyond the

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duration of FORWARD project, as one of the most important outputs of this project is to foster cooperation within and between ORs and engage the OR's R&I experts in FP participation and the promotion of OR's excellence in science.

Members profile

TWG7 profile evolution

TWG7 is a heterogeneous group by integrating OR experts and representatives from different fields of expertise and differentiated academic and professional backgrounds. A main challenge faced was to bring people together and find common interest in proposing and discussing the activities that include the Action Plan, and for this reason, it was important to understand the composition of this TWG, as well as its evolution to keep optimal working conditions and sustainable engagement.

Profile in January 2021

The TWG7 composition has changed along the process of construction of the Action Plan, from January to March 2021. This evolution is important to be understood as the Action Plan is a product of a co-constructive process and therefore it reflects the profile of its Members.

The TWG7 had its Kick-off with an online web event in 12th January with 48 Members enrolled at that time, from eight ORs (except from Mayotte). Most members were from Canary Islands, followed by Madeira and Réunion Island (Table 1).

Table 1 Number of enrolled Members in TWG7, per Region, in January 2021

TWG7 Members January 2021	
Region	Number of Members
Canary Islands	18
Madeira	9
Réunion	6

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Guadeloupe	5
Azores	4
Martinique	2
French Guiana	3
Saint-Martin	1
Mayotte	0
TOTAL	48

The TWG7 Members came mostly from academia, with more than half the members declaring to be affiliated to Universities (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Number of TWG7 Members per affiliation category in January 2021

The word cloud that was built taking the survey from the registration form has identified the fields of expertise of the Members in this Thematic Working group. The words “ecology”, “conservation”, “species”, “management”, “environmental” and “ecosystems” were the dominating ones (Figure 2).

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Figure 3 TWG7 Members skills on participation in Framework programs.

Profile in March 2021

The demography of the TWG7 changed along the participation process and in March 2021 the group has increased its numbers of enrolled Members, from 48 to 61 (Table 2). The OR contributing with more members remained the Canary Islands, with 20 Members, however Azores almost doubled the number of Members, now with 11, the same number as Madeira island (Table 2). Réunion Island remained with the same number, as well as Martinique and Saint Martin. No representatives of Mayotte joined to the TWG.

Table 2 Number of enrolled Members in TWG7, per Region, in March 2021.

TWG7 Members – March 2021	
Region	Number of Members
Canary Islands	20
Madeira	11
Réunion	6
Guadeloupe	6
Azores	11

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Martinique	2
French Guiana	4
Saint-Martin	1
Mayotte	0
TOTAL	61

In March, most team members of TWG7 still have as main affiliation the Universities (Figure 4). More than half the members declared to be affiliated to Universities (41 in a total of 61 members) followed by Public administration (8) and R&I Institutions (5) (Figure 4). The growth of the group has also given a wider diversity of affiliations, although the main profile of the TWG7 are academics.

Figure 4 TWG7 Members affiliation in March 2021

In terms of expertise, the difference between January and March 2021 was due to new enrolled Members from the scientific areas of Health¹ and terrestrial biology.

In terms of experience and knowledge in Framework Programs, the TWG7 group in March 2021 had more Members with high level (from 15 to 18) and low level (from 24 to 32) of experience in writing proposals in H2020. The number of very high level remained the same (Figure 5). When we analyze the networking skills, we can see that most members have high or low level skills. The number of Members with high skills in

¹ Tropical diseases, emerging pathogens, diagnosis and therapy; drug discovery; animal pathology, infectious diseases; biotoxins; animal production; emerging diseases

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Framework Programs participation has increased from 15 to 18, although the number of Members with low level of skills has increased even more, from 20 to 26 Members. The Members that indicated that have very high skills in FP participation has remained the same, being only 3. The new configuration of skills of the TWG7 Members can be analyzed in Figure 5.

Figure 5 The points of the TWG7 Members Skills, indicated by them during the enrollment, in Framework programs, from March 2021

Methodology

The TWG7 was integrated in the methodological context indicated by the FORWARD WP3 partners that was divided in three stages: the Kick off as step 1, the preparation of the Action Plan, as step 2, and the implementation of the Plan as a goal and defined as step 3 (Figure 6).

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Figure 6 Action Plan methodology adapted to the TWG7. Source: WP3 and TWG7 Workshop III presentation.

The methodology implemented during the co-construction of the Action Plan followed a logic of online work, during the three Workshops organized. These Workshops were working meetings and a start point to launch the second stage of offline work, in order to be more inclusive and allow that every Members has the opportunity to collaborate (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Methodology adopted to achieve the Action Plan for TWG7. Presented during the Workshop III (23.02.2021), as a conclusion and wider view of the roadmap towards the co-creation of the AP

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In the first Workshop, it was presented the inputs concerning the aspects areas to be addressed in each one of the four components of the SWOT matrix so it can be prioritized. After prioritizing through a form application, the participants gave their feedback about the objectives to establish as indicators to overcome each issue mentioned.

Then, during the second Workshop the TWG7 was distributed in 3 subgroups, each one simultaneously developing a brainstorm session designated to define and discuss the specific actions to do in order to address the different objectives highlighted in the previously workshops: Group 1 - Lobbying stakeholders; law and welfare; Human activities effects on biodiversity; Group 2 - Promote and monitoring ORs biodiversity; Group 3 - Capacity building.

Lastly and during the third Workshop, a Brainstorm was performed in order to determine the specifics of each task, intended to surpass certain objectives, listed in the Action Plan: person in charge, co-organizer(s), start and end date for the implementation and others.

This methodology also had a logic guided by a main question: How can the TWG7 contribute to increase the participation of the OR's in Framework Programs - Horizon Europe (2021-2027)? As a guiding point to propose and develop actions to integrate in the TWG7 Action Plan.

Action Plan guidelines and challenges

The Action Plan orientation has guiding lines in order to take into account when defining the actions/tasks for its implementation, as the following:

- ✓ Adapt the goal to apply to specific measures that can be verified and measured;
- ✓ Have in mind that we have at least 12 months to implement (target short, medium and long-time actions and their articulation in time), within and beyond the FORWARD project;
- ✓ Actions must be attained through the joint forces of the TWG7 members: *much more can be achieved by collaboration than competition;*

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- ✓ Make full use of the potential and resources that the TWG7 Members have together, in terms of capacity sharing, networking, experience and knowledge;
- ✓ No budget is allocated to the TWG's actions;
- ✓ Empower the group by strengthen the collaboration between the Members, the TWG's and other networks that you can identify as relevant to the TWG7 goals.

These guidelines will help the TWG to keep focus on goal achievement and define together actions that are possible to implement taking into account that this is a non-financed group of volunteer members. This was a chance to think “out of the box” and focus the definition of actions solely on the *added value* of the expertise and joint knowledge that The TWG7 is able to have as a group on the thematic of Biodiversity, conservation and restoration in the OR's. It has been also a challenge, along the process, to keep the Members engaged by solely appealing to a common recognition of the importance and advantages of participating in the TWG. Therefore, it was and still is important to reinforce the advantages of the network opportunities, mutual creation of sources of information and knowledge transfer for future participation in European Funding Programs.

The Action Plan explained

The Natural Legacy of Outermost Regions (ORs) has an outstanding value, including extraordinary landscapes and ecosystems, high numbers of endemic taxa and unique evolutionary lineages, and contribute significantly to regional and national economies (via services provided to agroforestry, fisheries, tourism) and to human/social well-being (aesthetic services). However, some human activities in ORs have (directly and/or indirectly) threatened the biodiversity and the services it provides reinforcing the need to adopt a rational and multidisciplinary approach to natural resources management jointly with the pressing need to develop biodiversity restoration initiatives. Current key biodiversity erosion processes include habitat fragmentation and degradation, invasive species spread, pollution and climatic changes, some of them acting in synergy and promoting species extinctions.

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Despite the acknowledged importance of Biodiversity Conservation and Restoration in ORs at regional, national and European-levels this thematic has not been a priority for research and innovation in ORs, and this has also been hindered by the intrinsic factors associated to ORs (e.g. geographic isolation, low human resources, low funding) that pose strong limitations for a more active and competitive participation of ORs in European Union funding opportunities. There are several examples of successful research and innovation projects, coordinated or with the participation of regional entities from the ORs, but these illustrate the unbalanced participation of ORs in European Union funding frameworks and the lack of joint proposals from the ORs addressing key topics of general and common concern.

This Action Plan follows the structure adopted during the discussion meetings of our group, where three subgroups addressing specific topics have been formed. The main topics analyzed were: Promote, monitor and value the biodiversity of ORs; Natural resources management and the need to protect/restore biodiversity; Capacity building – setting tools to improve communication and increase competitiveness. The actions and tasks proposed by team members were firstly discussed in each subgroup (January 2021), then presented to all team members and analyzed during an offline working period and later discussed with more detail in a general meeting (February 2021).

- A major objective of our Action Plan is to promote the unique biodiversity of ORs to key stakeholders, which we aim to achieve by identifying specific institutions and organizations in Europe and elsewhere interested on this thematic. In a second stage, we will promote the organization of open days in selected institutions of ORs.

- Long-term biodiversity monitoring in ORs is also a crucial objective of our Action Plan and will include a few more specific goals. The general goal is to monitor biodiversity change in ORs and identify its main drivers to fuel more effective conservation measures based on sound science. Several actions will contribute to this objective (and similar ones), namely the identification of in-place long-term monitoring programs, selection of efficient and effective biodiversity indicators, identification of taxonomic experts and institutions targeting biodiversity research and housing specimen collections.

FORWARD Thematic Working Group 7 – Biodiversity conservation and restoration ACTION PLAN

- The management of natural resources and associated conflicts with biodiversity conservation was also set as an important objective and several actions have been proposed on this topic. First, it will be necessary to identify the different risks to biodiversity in the ORs and list the key actors on this topic and their expertise. Secondly, this multidisciplinary topic will benefit from close interaction with other TWGs, particularly TWG1, TWG5, TWG6 and TWG8. Lastly, it will be important to identify calls targeting this area, where joint proposals can be prepared.

Vision and notes

Oceanic islands have long fascinated scientists due to their unique biotas and ecosystems, which encompass a large number of endemic species. As biodiversity is decreasing on a global scale, its loss is felt particularly on Islands, where species are disappearing at faster rates due to human activities.

In this context, the Thematic Working Group TWG7 - Biodiversity Conservation and Restoration, pursues the following long-term vision:

- ✓ Use the Outermost regions (ORs) as a model system (“living-labs”), to investigate ecological and evolutionary mechanisms responsible for shaping island biotas;
- ✓ Identification of EU Funding Schemes and increase the capture of EU funds, to better characterize and understand the Biodiversity status, trends and drivers in EU ORs, to better guide conservation strategies and management, and provide new opportunities for innovation;
- ✓ Promote the RED Listing of invertebrates in all ORs to allow future applications of LIFE projects at regional scale targeting invertebrates, namely land-snails and arthropods;
- ✓ Develop communication tools within the scientific community to reach the general public and promote the excellence in science and its public interest, and raise public awareness;
- ✓ Be able to create databases that can support researchers in ORs with the following key thematic:

FORWARD Thematic Working Group 7 – Biodiversity conservation and restoration
ACTION PLAN

- i. Identification of the most important risk factors (and eventual threats) driven by human activities to biodiversity in ORs;
- ii. List of key actors and their expertise;
- iii. List practitioners of the One Health approach in the ORs;
- iv. Elaborate a List of European Institutions interested in exploring the biodiversity in OR's, namely Island Biology Groups across continental Europe and others;
 - a. Elaborate a list of available “living-labs” in the ORs, with permanent plots available for further scientific work from external researchers (e.g. BALA, Terceira island).
- v. List sites for collecting long-term ecological data to evaluate species distributions and abundance at multiple spatial and temporal scales;
 - a. Identify and list model organisms which could be used as research targets;
- vi. Identify and list the active working groups doing taxonomy research within Europe;
- vii. List the reference institutions holding the key collections related to local OR's biota;
- viii. Compilation of existing online databases related to Biodiversity, conservation and restoration in each OR.

The long-term implementation of a critical mass and connectivity among ORs and between ORs and continental Europe is therefore the ultimate goal of this TWG7, dedicated to the “Biodiversity Conservation and Restoration”.

TWG8: MARINE SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGIES

Forward – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

TWG8 ACTION PLAN - Draft

MARINE SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGIES IN THE OUTERMOST REGIONS:

*A RAINBOW OF OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE LOCAL SCIENTISTS, THE MEMBER STATES
AND THE INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH COMMUNITY*

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FORWARD project:

Objectives & structure (WPs)

Critical mass and connectivity among ORs and between ORs and continental Europe are some of the main obstacles ORs faced with to access EU framework programme. The aim of the WP3 is to reinforce the actual and reveal the potential competitive advantages of Outermost Regions in their respective sectors of fields of expertise and the identification of common interests. To fulfil this aim, a number of thematic working groups, composed of experts from ORs or from other countries, will be established and they will meet and work together for the definition and implementation of thematic action plans in accordance with WP2 results and with the feedback of ORs R&I communities.

This action plan will contribute to foster collaboration on Marine Science and Technologies among ORs, between ORs and third countries as well as continental Europe stakeholders.

As a result of the analysis of the survey and the interviews conducted in the 9 ORs on 2019, the TWG8 Action Plan has been designed following the WP2 (Mapping and diagnose) conclusions and linked to the following barriers and needs expressed by researchers and SMEs:

- Lack of technical and administrative support in proposal writing.
- Difficulty to build partnerships and networking.
- Small size of research groups and research centres.
- Low participation of SMEs.
- Lack of institutional support, public authorities support.

Aligned with the training actions planned in WP4 and based on the R&I regional ecosystems analysis, the RIS3 strategy, and specific needs of R&I actors in order to

enhance their participation in Horizon Europe and other EU research programmes, TWG8 members will benefit from:

- knowledge on the different funding opportunities and the proposals processes;
- customize guidance on choosing relevant HE topics and types of action;
- training and assistance on proposal writing to increase researchers' and SMEs skills for their participation in EU research projects;
- support for the development and direction of the project and preparation of proposals;

Aligned with WP5 activities aimed at the establishment of consortia and development of specific projects and more long-term oriented ones to facilitate the emergence of new and/or improved long-lasting linkages with relevant co-operation partners inside and outside the EU, TW8 members will be benefit from:

- The participation in the scientific conferences organised by FORWARD project;
- The promotion of tailored events to facilitate networking such as workshops and/or webinars;
- The promotion and participation in infrastructure exchange projects such as AQUAEXCEL 3.0.

[General Goals of the FORWARD Action Plan on Marine Sciences & Technologies](#)

The main activity of the TWG8 is to make the most of the FORWARD Consortium to promote and reinforce the excellence in marine sciences, bringing together the major capacities of the experts located in OR, basic and applied research centers, with the new opportunities that offers the Horizon Europe and other funding schemes coming from the European Commission.

As specific goals, the drafting process of the Action Plan on Marine Sciences and Technologies want to develop synergies with key actors, mainly in the ORs to:

- The co-creation of a Marine Roadmap with extensive participation of ORs members leading towards a Marine Sciences and Technologies Action Plan
- The development of an Inter-regional platform to foster research collaboration with Experts from ORs, other European regions and Third Countries' Institutions with a common research domain: The marine realm.
- Increase both the number of European Frame Programme projects submitted and finance in the ORs, and the promotion of a deeper integration of ORs scientists into the ERA.
- To promote specific European call for ORs where high relevant research groups can be integrated within local consortiums in specific Marine Sciences & Technologies topics.

Background:

Outermost Region Participation in European funding schemes related with Marine Sciences & Technologies

From the extensive data mining activity done by the partners involved in WP2, mainly inside Cordis, it was identified a total of 53 Marine Sciences and Technologies projects funded by the European Commission, most of them in the framework of the Horizon 2020.

Figure 1 Number of projects by OR

A more detailed analysis revealed that Canarias & Azores are the most outstanding ORs involved in marine field projects, followed by Madeira and Martinique with minor participation, whereas there was a limited participation of other French ORs in European funding schemes related to basic and applied marine research. In addition Public Entities, followed by Research Centres, High Education Centres and Private Companies, promoted most of the projects.

Figure 2. Number of projects by type of organization

The global amount of funds received by ORs was about 15 million euros, corresponding to 5% of the total amount given to the European projects where OR participated.

Figure 3 H2020 projects by organization (at least 2 funded projects)

Research Potential of the Marine Ecosystems in the Outermost Regions

The Outermost Regions have numerous potential growth engines based on their specific geographical characteristics. In the marine environment, it comprises more than half of the EU's Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) and has a potential reserve of marine resources close to 15 million km², which means having a unique on site laboratory in three oceans for exploration in areas such as food security, climate action, energy and biotechnology, and constitutes an asset for tourism, thanks to its exceptional natural and cultural environment

Their geostrategic location places them as EU ambassadors in the Atlantic Ocean, the Caribbean and the Indian Ocean and offers them the possibility of benefiting the EU through their neighborhood relations and of spreading the influence of the EU in their respective regions. In addition, their human capital is very valuable since these regions have a better trained and more qualified workforce, better public services and more advanced technical knowledge than their neighbors, which gives them the possibility of selling services and knowledge in sectors with great added value.

These regions are home to a unique diversity of species and ecosystems, of vital importance for biodiversity on a planetary level. In addition, together with overseas

countries and territories, they have more endemic plant and animal species than continental Europe as a whole, including more than 20% of the World's coral reefs and coastal lagoons. The conservation and sustainable use of this huge biodiversity offers enormous possibilities in fields such as health, bio-pharmacy, cosmetics and in many other industrial sectors, such as active and nature tourism (ecotourism) or aquaculture of native species (food security) and renewable energies (zero emissions). Nevertheless, in most of the the ORs, coherent policies for the governance and sustainable use of the vast marine resources in their geographic environment have not yet been developed.

The BEST initiative (Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services in European Overseas Territories), has highlighted the possibility of conducting research in prestigious European and international networks, showing various areas with important knowledge gaps such as marine biodiversity, where we do not know a large part of the processes and services that occur at the level of marine ecosystems, both coastal and high seas.

Recent specific initiatives of the DG Environment, with the MOVE and MOVE-ON projects, tries to map and identify the products and ecosystem services that marine and coastal habitats generate in the ORs. These projects seek to mobilize the few research teams linked to biodiversity in the ORs in order to show the economic relevance of the enormous biodiversity that these overseas territories hold.

From the technological perspective, some experts of the ORs are in the frontline of applied research for the supply of potable water, which is mainly associated with evolved desalination technologies. The advances in the supply of this service to the local communities are a centerpiece of current research actions by a number of OR centers, such in the case of the ITC in Canarias. This technological field is also of international relevance for Third countries and it its foreseen a huge development potential in future decades.

Another keystone applied research development is the implementation of novel renewable marine energy technologies, which is been the centerpiece of the PLOCAN

center and its associated network of research centers in other ORs. The European Commission has declared a target of zero emission for the coming decades and the ORs are outstanding laboratories to test and implement novel technologies for the supply of clean energy resources.

Major Research Interest of the TWG8 members

The inquiries and inputs received from the TWG8 members during the last 6 months are represented in the following two figures, which summarizes in a cloud of words format the main research topics of interest selected by the ORs experts. In the second version (January 2021), the term "marine" has been removed since its presence is obvious and to allow a better analysis the rest of the terms.

Figure 4 TWG8 Members' Research interest September 2020

Horizon Europe Structure

Figure 6 Outline of the Pillars and other actions included in Horizon Europe

Pillar I

The Excellent Science Pillar aims to increase the EU's global scientific competitiveness. It supports frontier research projects driven by top researchers through:

- the European Research Council (ERC);
- the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) fellowships for experienced researchers, doctoral training networks and exchanges;
- and research infrastructures (INFRA)

Pillar II

Within Pillar II “Global challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness”, there are programmed 5 European Missions, which may also benefit from actions carried out within other parts of the Programme as well as complementary actions carried out under other Union funding schemes.

The following 5 European Missions are the major response of the European Commission to the challenges defined by the UN Sustainable Development Goals for 2030:

- Adaptation to Climate Change (+ Social Transformations)
- Cancer
- Healthy Oceans, Seas, Coastal and Inland Waters
- Carbon Neutral and Smart Cities
- Soil Health and Food

In this sense, the **Mission Healthy Oceans, Seas, Coastal and Inland Waters** tries to respond to several SDGs, mainly Goal 6: Clean Water & Sanitation and Goal 14: Life Below Water. In addition, this Mission targets the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development launched by the International Oceanographic Commission of the UNESCO (2021-2030).

This Mission is trying to respond to one of the main priorities of the European Commission: A European Green Deal. More specifically, the actions will support diverse Directives of the DG Environment, such as Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the Water Framework Directive and the Strategy for Plastics; whereas in the case of the DG Maritime Affairs & Fisheries will support the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive and other management tools associated with International Ocean Governance (High Seas / UN Law of the Sea).

Another important aspect to be considered inside the Mission Healthy Oceans, its linkage with the evolving Copernicus system, with the implementation of the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS).

In September 2020, the Commission published a keystone document denominated as **Mission Starfish 2030**¹ with 5 overarching objectives:

- (i) Filling the knowledge and emotional gap,
- (ii) Regenerating marine and freshwater ecosystems,
- (iii) Zero pollution,
- (iv) Decarbonising our ocean
- (v) Waters revamping governance

Most of these objectives are in a preliminary stage in most of the ORs, with many lacks of information or not data available for its full implementation.

Pillar III

The Innovative Europe Pillar aims to make Europe a frontrunner in market-creating innovation via the European Innovation Council (EIC). It also helps to develop the overall EU innovation landscape through the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) which fosters integration of the knowledge triangle of education, research and innovation.

Other EU Funding Opportunities

Inside the new Horizon Europe, the **European Partnerships** are initiatives to overcome fragmentation of research efforts where the EU, together with private and public partners, commit to jointly support the development and implementation of a program of research and innovation activities (https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe/european-partnerships-horizon-europe_en#types-of-partnership). Depending on the type of partnership the partners could represent industry, universities, research organizations, bodies with a public service remit at local, regional, national, or

¹ European Commission, Sept. 2020. **Mission Starfish 2030: Restore our Ocean and Waters.** Report of the Mission Board Healthy Oceans, Seas, Coastal and Inland Waters

international level (e.g., R&D funders) or civil society organizations, including foundations and NGOs.

Partnerships are foreseen across 5 areas:

- health;
- digital, industry and space;
- climate, energy and mobility;
- food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment; and
- partnerships across themes

It seems that in the near future, the most relevant partnerships related with the TWG8 will be some of those included in the area of “food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment”, such as the European Partnership for rescuing biodiversity to safeguard life on Earth, and the European Partnership for a climate neutral, sustainable and productive Blue Economy, among others.

In this sense, Partnerships will represent an opportunity to get financial support for ORs R&D teams, providing they have the capacity to interact with the key actors in mainland Europe and other countries to be competitive in the calls. And the later could be helped to achieve by training and other activities throughout the FORWARD execution.

Research, development, and innovation provide alternative approaches to those of tourism as the main and practically unique socioeconomic income source in the ORs. However, it is also important to realize that this approach needs commitment from the teams involved, as well as adaptation to the competent level of the project execution (language, capacities, qualified human resources, timing, digital, etc.) associated with a strong support from their respective regional authorities showing clear signals to the European Commission of the added-value for the ERA of the Outermost Regions.

Sub-thematic areas to be considered inside the FORWARD Action Plan on Marine Sciences & Technologies

Upon the results of the Workshop conducted in Feb 5th with more than the 34 TWG8 attendants from a total of 69 members registered, different research topics have been highlighted as potential research areas which deserve stronger commitments and policy tools from the decision-maker sphere to foster the excellence in marine research in the ORs.

The experts have identified the existence of local expertise, together with a clear alignment with the European / global dimension of the research challenges and future social demands for future development under foreseen Horizon Europe or other European or International funding schemes.

In the following paragraphs, we have outlined some of the sub-thematic topics that have been considered of relevance for the ORs in the marine realm. These topics are in a preliminary stage from the diverse inputs that active members of the TWG8 sent and are not yet fully developed:

[Ocean literacy.](#)

Oceans cover 71% of our planet's surface, and are the source of most life on Earth, offering a major contribution to the regulation of weather and climate, driving the water cycle that dominates land and atmosphere, providing most of our oxygen, and feeding much of the human population.

As we all know, the Oceans are the main part of their territory for the ORs with progressively greater impacts on the economy and the social fabric. Pollution, habitat degradation and overexploitation of natural resources, lead to climate change and ocean acidification and threaten the health of the ocean in unprecedented ways.

Despite the consensus in the need to acknowledge the importance of the ocean in people's life, ocean topics are not clearly included in the current regional/national

curricula and only punctually are considered in some projects on the responsibility of more interested teachers. Moreover, better public understanding of the ocean is an important part to acknowledge and guarantee a better and healthier planet as the more people know, the more they are willing to support policies to keep the ocean healthy. So, this knowledge should be provided somehow throughout the public teaching/learning educational process.

Considering that the ocean is the defining feature of our planet and that our lives depend on its health, understanding the ocean is essential to understanding and protecting our environment, the sub-topic of the oceans and specifically improving literacy about the relevance and functioning of the oceans is vital for the ORs. Projects that can interest students and teachers on the topic, which can integrate outreach actions, activities to build small ROVs and autonomous robots, repositories of learning resources that provide "ready-to-use ideas", and many others are valued by decision-makers.

[4.2. Marine Conservation and Biodiversity.](#)

In addition to the lack of knowledge and / or lack of data on specific taxonomic groups or on the effectiveness of extant conservation measures in the marine waters of the Outermost Regions, another little-analysed aspect of marine biodiversity is the connectivity and migratory routes of species whose life cycles span more than one OR, such in the case of the archipelagos of Macaronesia with seabirds, turtles, cetaceans and various fish, invertebrates and macroalgae. This lack of knowledge also affects the large coastal and oceanic extensions linked to ORs, which host a unique potential of habitat bioengineers (seagrass, seaweeds, corals, etc.), sometimes intensively affected by local and global stressors. This singularity can be promoted as natural in-situ laboratories for ERA including a biodiversity conservation perspective.

Other relevant aspect, which is already a world social and scientific concern, is the pollution of marine litter, mainly related to plastics and microplastics, with clear negative effects on biodiversity, trophic chains and ecosystem services.

Another member of the TWG8 pointed out in relation with marine mammals, the need of a monitoring programme of the health surveillance for resident populations (or management units) of marine mammals in the ORs, in order to appropriately assess and monitor risk factors and threats to their conservation, as well as using them as bioindicators of human health associated with the good environmental status of the marine areas where these animals reside (One Health Initiative).

The massive arrivals of *Sargassum*, observed since 2011 along the Caribbean coast, raise some interested and not yet resolved scientific and applied questions, such as what to do with this enormous biomass, which arrives regularly and impacts too many coastal areas? Some research have been done to study different ways of storing algae, improving alginate extraction processes, and their uses in new biomaterials such as a bioplastic and a new type of cardboard.

Specific actions such as partnerships in Biodiversity, within the LIFE Program or within other European funding scheme developed under H2020 as the “Co-funded European Partnerships using a program co-fund action”, the most convenient for the Outermost Regions (ORs). These partnerships involve EU countries, with research funders and other public authorities at the core of the consortium. It is expected that they somehow will continue what the former ERA-Net Cofund projects were doing in H2020 but at a longer term (about 7 years) within Horizon Europe. This type of projects was composed of partners that were able to fund R&D, and for doing it they launched transnational calls to fund research teams in the agreed topics, which were co-funded by the EC (e.g., see current open call in BiodivERsA). These partnerships can reinforce the knowledge and responsible uses of marine biological resources, for industrial purposes under the framework of sustainable blue growth policies for diverse marine and maritime sectors,

such as marine energies, aquaculture, marine biotechnology, ecotourism, artisanal fisheries, seabed mining, etc., together with the maintenance of environmental quality.

Sustainable Aquaculture

The aquaculture potential of the ORs, especially low impact aquaculture and IMTA, needs to be reinforced as a food security mechanism in these regions, supporting nature-based solutions, which can be integrated with the biodiversity bounty of the ORs and could be easily developed in MPAs. The promotion of larger number of sustainable aquaculture practices is an aspect that can be directly linked with the TWG7. Create a network of ORs entities (Academic, scientific institutions, SMEs, citizens...) focusing on biodiversity and marine aspects to act as a single point of contact with the European Commission - to join efforts to tackle the specificity of ORs through a single voice. Examples of similar Networks are: <https://www.islands2030.org/> or <http://octa-innovation.eu/>.

New Sensing tools and techniques for the environmental stewardship.

Development of novel sensing enabling technology applied to marine ecosystems (coastal and high sea) with global potential impact, fostering R+D innovation capabilities and local knowledge transfer to the private industry. Technological areas of relevance are remote sensing, marine robotics, operational oceanography, ocean monitoring and coastal pollution control, risk prevention systems and biodiversity monitoring. The ORs should promote their oceanic strategic position within ERA where all these tools and techniques can be tested and easily monitored.

Additionally, the ORs oceanic strategic position can be also employed for operational monitoring and forecasting of (1) high surf & storm surge events, and related research (e.g. wave modelling & observations, wave climate projections), (2) marine litter detection and 3D seabed reconstructions (e.g. 3D images combined with Machine Learning techniques useful to determine the consequences of possible climatic catastrophes in the coastal and sandy areas) and (3) pelagic Sargassum spp algae surface

drift & stranding, and related research (e.g. Lagrangian particle modelling, ocean currents, ocean observations). These actions already promoted by the French meteorological service (Météo-France) operating at various ORs centres can be extended to other regions to develop projects in its areas of expertise (meteorology, climatology, surface oceanography).

Case study of Sargassum biomass stranding in coastal areas: Innovative methods of observation and modeling the dynamics of these brown seaweeds at several scales are foreseen, requiring a multidisciplinary approach among researchers. The modeling and forecasting of *Sargassum* strandings are essential to design effective integrated risk management strategies and correspond to a strong and pressing demand from civil society. This operational challenge relates to both event forecasting (i.e. on a one-week scale) and long term forecasting (one to several months). Another transversal actions can integrate the development of low-cost sensing tools to monitoring (e.g. long-range communication devices) offshore marine farms in remote environments.

[Coastal water desalination and sanitation.](#)

Fundamental research on fully-decarbonized water desalination and sanitation is one of the key priorities for the Canaries OR. Among other technological advances, the development of novel solar technology based on micro-nano-structured multifunctional metal panels capable of ultra-efficient photo-thermal energy conversion and water interfacial evaporation, are potential research lines to be explored with synergies with other experts in ORs and European research centres.

The industrial desalination technologies have evolved from the first thermal-evaporation plants to the reverse osmosis plants, which are the most used nowadays (IDA, 2018), with a decreasing specific energy consumption. Membrane processes are also applied to treated wastewater, in order to reuse it for irrigation purposes.

The current major challenges in membrane desalination can be classified in the following main three groups: 1) minimisation of the power consumption, 2) optimisation

of the membranes for a higher flow and the minimisation of fouling and 3) minimisation of the environmental impact, improving the management of brine disposal (development of zero liquid discharge (ZLD) systems).

In the RUPs regions, due to water scarcity, a wide range of currently available innovative desalination technologies and systems have to be tested and improved. In order to increase the existing knowledge, the purpose is to study potential emerging technologies for industrial desalination applications, besides the increase of studies in renewable energies application on fully-decarbonized water desalination and coastal sanitation and on discharge to the sea (brine and treated water discharges). These are the key priorities for the Canaries OR. Different specific actions could be realised:

- An entire series of emerging desalination technologies is being developed and drawing the interest of both the scientific community and the industrial water sector. Forward osmosis in combination with other membrane technologies is conceived as the most promising emerging desalination technology.
- Recent research has devoted extensive efforts to study new materials (zeolites, carbon nanotubes, graphene derivatives, etc.) that can be applied to emerging water treatment technologies such as forward osmosis, microbial cell desalination or capacitive deionisation (CDI).
- the exploitation of the potential osmotic gradient between brine and a low-saline solution in order to produce energy is being fully developed, using technologies such as FO and PRO.
- Marine and wind energies off-shore solutions for desalination.
- Among other technological advances, the development of novel solar technology based on micro-nano-structured multifunctional metal panels capable of ultra-efficient photo-thermal energy conversion and water interfacial evaporation, are potential research lines to be explored with synergies with other experts in ORs and European research centres.

4.6. Sustainable Artisanal Fisheries.

Artisanal fisheries in oceanic island systems, with discontinuous shelves, are by their nature highly sensitive and tend to overexploit the target species. Furthermore, these multi-species and multi-gear fisheries are often data poor. On the other hand, some of these island systems present a great tourist and urban development that adds great pressure on coastal marine ecosystems, either through coastal infrastructures (ports, marinas, etc.), pollution and also recreational fishing. This set of disturbances makes the ecological systems of the oceanic islands highly vulnerable to the effects of climate change, with a high risk of biodiversity loss and productivity imbalances. It is proposed to carry out ecosystem approaches to assess the status of fishery resources that allow the adequate management of these artisanal and recreational fisheries through common indicators and reference points, in the context of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) oriented to achieve Good Environmental Status. Within these oceanic island systems, we can include the Canaries, Madeira, Azores, Guadeloupe, Martinique, La Reunion and also some of the Greek Aegean islands.

4.7. Development of marine biotechnologies.

The ORs constitute an important breeding ground for microbial biodiversity that has not yet been studied very much. However, more and more molecules of interest or innovative technologies are produced from bacteria (production of biomass for energy recovery, production of materials used in the composition of new materials, production of therapeutic molecules, etc.). Thus, bio-electrochemical devices are also increasingly studied allowing the production of renewable energy or the synthesis of molecules of interest. These tools can also be used for the depollution by bioremediation of environmental matrices.

Case study of bio-electrochemical devices: At the Université des Antilles, the microbial fuel cell is a device for the production of clean and continuously renewable electricity which operates thanks to the action of microorganisms such as bacteria and / or microalgae. Research has shown that marine and mangrove sediments are

environments in which these bacteria called electroactive grow. Their natural metabolism allows them to breathe on solid conductive materials, thus allowing the collection of electrons used to power electrical devices. This technology would make it possible to offer an alternative to fossil fuels in the long term and in the medium term, to offer supply systems for small clean energy needs, particularly in isolated areas requiring point sources of energy.

Implementation of the TWG8 Action Plan

Objectives, Actions, Achievements

The TWG8 Action Plan has five main objectives:

- **[MANAGEMENT] O1:** Successful development of the TWG8 management tasks in order to achieve goals within the set scope, time, and quality.
- **[FOCUSING] O2:** Selecting key Marine Sciences and Technologies research fields and subjects
- **[NETWORKING] O3:** Establishment of networks between the ORs and external actors that will cooperate to build critical masses and projects on Marine Sciences and Technologies;
- **[IMPLEMENTATION] O4:** fostering the participation of OR's organizations in European R&D&I programmes in the area of Marine Sciences and Technologies;
- **[DISSEMINATION] O5:** Disseminating TWG8 activities.

Table 1 TWG8 objectives, actions and tasks

O1	Management: Successful development of the TWG management tasks in order to achieve goals within the set scope, time, and quality.	Start/end
A1.1	A1.1. Implementation of cooperation and communication tools	Jul20 - Dec21
T1.1.1	Setting up online tools, Short training on using online tools, Implementing online tools	Feb21 - Mar21
A1.2	A1.2. TWG Meetings	Jul20 - Dec21
T1.2.1	TWG8 Kick-off meeting	Feb21
T1.2.2	Other TWG8 meeting	Feb21 - Dec21
A1.3	A1.3. Reporting	Dec21
T1.3.1	First annual TWG Reporting	Dec21
O2	Focusing: Selecting key Marine Sciences and Technologies research fields and subjects;	Start/end
A2.1	A2.1. The co-creation of a <u>Marine Roadmap</u> with extensive participation of ORs members leading towards a Marine Sciences and Technologies Action Plan	Mar21 - Jun21
T2.1.1	Prioritizing <u>specific research areas</u>	Mar21
T2.1.2	Creating <u>specific sub-groups</u>	Apr21 - Jun21
O3	Networking: Establishment of networks between the ORs and external actors that will cooperate to build critical masses and projects on the considered thematic;	Start/end
A3.1	A3.1. The development of an <u>Inter-regional platform</u> to foster research collaboration with Experts from ORs, other European regions and Third Countries' Institutions with a common research domain: The marine realm.	Apr21 - Dec21
T3.1.1	Creation of a <u>list of key institutions at OR and EU level in the area of Marine Science and Technologies.</u>	Apr21 - Dec21
A3.2	A3.2. Identifying <u>External Networking Events</u>	Apr21 - Dec21
T3.2.1	Task 3.2.1. Identification of events of interest organised at regional, national or at EU level, promoting among the members their active participation	Apr21 - Dec21

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A3.3	A3.3. Promoting <u>TWG Networking Activities</u>	Apr21 - Dec21
T3.3.1	Organisation of webinars to present a selection of successful projects in which TWG8 members have taken part	Apr21 - Dec21
T3.3.2	WP5 Networking event: Workshop FORWARD ULPGC "Blue Growth and Sustainable Exploitation of Marine Resources from the Ecosystem Approach"	Sep21
O4	Implementation: fostering the participation of OR's organizations in European R&D&I programmes;	Start/end
A4.1	A4.1. Increase both the number of European Frame Programme projects submitted and finance in the ORs, and the promotion of a deeper integration of ORs scientists into the ERA.	Apr21 - Dec21
T4.1.1	<u>Identification of calls</u> and topics of interest for the TWG8 on Horizon Europe Programme, LIFE, DGs, etc.	Apr21 - Dec21
T4.1.2	<u>Identification of active partners</u> looking for leading a consortium or to join to a consortium in forthcoming calls and funding opportunities	Apr21 - Dec21
A4.2	A4.2. Training: participation on training activities designed in the FW Capacity Building Plan	Apr21 - Dec21
T4.2.1.	<u>Identification and organization of training courses, webinars and/or infodays</u> of interest (writing proposals, reporting and audits, ERC/MSCA calls, COST Actions, etc.)	Apr21 - Dec21
A4.3	A4.3. To promote specific European call for ORs where high relevant research groups can be integrated within local consortiums in specific Marine Sciences & Technologies topics.	Apr21 - Dec21
T4.3.1.	<u>Position paper</u> analysing the needs for the promotion of specific European call for ORs	Apr21 - Dec21
O5	Dissemination: Disseminating TWG8 activities.	Start/end
A5.1	A5.1. Dissemination of TWG8 activities through FORWARD channels	Feb21 - Dec21
T5.1.1	Disseminate the activities done on the context of TWG8 through FORWARD channels.	Feb21 - Dec21

Table 2 List of TWG8 achievements

Title of achievement
Directory of Marine Sciences & Technologies Actors
List of external networking events for TWG8 interests
EU funding opportunities database; Lists of partners search created
List of training activities
Position paper for the implementation of new and specific OR's EU funding programmes
Organisation of webinars to present a selection of successful projects
WP5 Networking event: Workshop FORWARD ULPGC "Blue Growth and Sustainable Exploitation of Marine Resources from the Ecosystem Approach"

Methodology

The following dynamics and mechanisms will be used to implement the different tasks contributing to the creation of a working space for a collaborative work among the members of the group:

- Collaborative space (TEAMS)
- Webinars
- Offline work
- Emails
- Use of common templates
- Google/Microsoft FORMS
- Surveys

Indicators

A list of indicators will help to monitor the implementation of the activities and help to detect and correct possible deviations.

Table 3 Indicators to monitor TWG8 Actions

Area	Task	Indicator	Nº
Management	T1.2.2	Nº meetings	> 4
Management	T1.2.2	Nº participants/meeting	> 15
Networking	T3.1.1	Nº actors identified	> 20
Networking	T3.2.1	Nº events identified	> 10
Networking	T3.3.1; T3.3.2	Nº webinars/workshops	> 5
Implementation	T4.1.1	Nº calls/topics identified	> 10
Implementation	T4.1.2	Nº partners search elaborated	> 25
Implementation	T4.1.2	Nº proposals submitted	> 2
Implementation	T4.2.1	Nº trainings identified	> 8
Dissemination	T5.1.1	Nº news generated	> 3

Contingency Plan

A contingency plan will help us to anticipate potential risks and redirect efforts in helping to achieve TWG8 goals.

Table 4 TWG8 Contingency Plan: potential risks and levels

Area	Risk	Level (L, M, H)	Contingency Plan
Management	Lack of knowledge on the use of Microsoft TEAMS Platform	L/M	Training material on how to use the platform available for the members.
Management	Poor attendance of participants in meetings	L	Organization of short meetings (less than 1.5 hour) sending the agenda at least 1 week in advance.
Networking	Lack of interest to participate on the webinars to present a selection of successful projects	M	Offer this webinars as an achievement in terms of dissemination in their current funded projects (H2020, etc.).
Networking	Low number of “partner search template” filled and received from members.	L/M	Communicate the importance to have their profiles to be able to support those searching topics/calls of interest.
Implementation	Lack of interest to build joint proposals due to confidentiality issues.	M/H	Signature of confidentiality and Non-disclosure Agreements
Dissemination	Low number of news generated	L/M	Use of templates and models to help writing news and communicate to WP8 the activities developed within the group.